

HIGH TEMPERATURE EXPOSURE IN PREGNANCY AND ADVERSE MATERNAL AND NEONATAL OUTCOMES: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS

Deliverable number D2.6

Updated systematic review

HIGH HORIZONS – D2.6

[GRANT NO. 101057843]

Deliverable Information	
Title	High temperature exposure in pregnancy and adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes: a systematic review and meta-analysis* *Original title: Updated systematic review
Deliverable number	D2.6
WP number	WP2
Author(s)	Darshnika P Lakhoo, Nicholas Brink, Amy Wise, Ijeoma Solarin, Stanley Luchters, Marlies H Craig, Gloria Maimela, Lebogang Radebe, Matthew F Chersich
Lead beneficiary	Wits RHI
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Due date	Original due date: 31 December 2023 New due date: 29 February 2024

History of Changes	
Version 0.1	01 February 2024
Version 1.0	21 February 2024

This document is issued within the frame and for the purpose of the HIGH Horizons project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Framework Programme under Grant Agreement number 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478. The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein do not necessarily reflect the official views of the European Commission or UKRI. The dissemination of this document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission and UKRI are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This deliverable is subject to final acceptance by the European Commission. This document and its content are the property of the HIGH Horizons Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the HIGH Horizons project and the document are properly referenced. Each HIGH Horizons Partner may use this document in conformity with the HIGH Horizons Consortium Grant Agreement provisions.

Table of Contents

List of tables.....	4
List of figures	4
Abstract.....	8
List of acronyms	10
Definitions.....	11
1 Introduction	13
1.1 Heat impacts on health	14
1.2 Vulnerable populations	15
1.3 Pregnant women and newborns	16
1.4 Current understanding and knowledge gaps.....	19
1.5 Purpose of review	20
2 Methodology	21
2.1 Eligibility criteria	21
2.2 Information sources.....	22
2.3 Search strategy	22
2.4 Selection process	23
2.5 Data collection process.....	23
2.6 Data items.....	23
2.7 Study risk of bias assessment.....	24
2.8 Synthesis methods.....	24
2.9 Certainty of evidence grading.....	26
3 Results	31
3.1 Overview	31
3.2 Geographical distribution.....	34
3.3 Distribution of studies by health outcome	36
3.4 Summary of effect estimates	38
3.5 Maternal outcomes.....	42

3.6	Foetal and perinatal outcomes	54
3.7	Neonatal outcomes.....	67
3.8	Effect modification	88
3.9	Quality assessment.....	91
4	Discussion	92
5	Conclusion.....	100
6	References.....	101
7	Appendices.....	115
7.1	Appendix A: Search on MEDLINE (PubMed) and Web of Science.....	115
7.2	Appendix B: Summary table of all studies.....	121
7.3	Appendix C: Study references.....	169
7.4	Appendix D: Effect modification	181

List of tables

Table 1.	Distribution of studies across location, time, and outcome type	33
Table 2.	Summary of themes with at least one effect estimates by theme and environmental exposure	39
Table 3.	Adapted IPCC evidence scores	92

List of figures

Figure 1.	IPCC confidence language is based on agreement and the type, amount, quality, and consistency of evidence	27
Figure 2.	Adapted PRISMA diagram representing study selection process from 2019 and 2023 searches.....	32
Figure 3.	Number of publications per year. *Annualized for 2023.....	34

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of studies by: A region; B country, C mean temperature; D climate zone	35
Figure 5. Distribution of outcomes across different population groups.....	37
Figure 6. Number of results (vote counting) by direction of effect, per outcome category	38
Figure 7. Forest plot of the odds of gestational diabetes mellitus per 1°C temperature increase	42
Figure 8. Forest plot of odds of gestational diabetes mellitus during high versus low temperatures.....	42
Figure 9. Forest plot of odds of hypertension per 1°C temperature increase.....	44
Figure 10. Top: Meta-analysis of the odds of hypertension during high versus low temperatures. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis	47
Figure 11. Funnel plot of odds of hypertension during high versus low temperatures.....	48
Figure 12. Forest plot of the odds of maternal admissions during a heat wave ..	49
Figure 13. Forest plot for the odds of maternal infections during high versus low temperatures.....	50
Figure 14. Forest plot of odds of PROM during high versus low temperatures ...	51
Figure 15. Forest plot for odds of stillbirth during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	54
Figure 16. Top: Meta-analysis for the odds of stillbirth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure period < 4 weeks. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis.....	56
Figure 17. Top: Meta-analysis for odds of stillbirth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks . Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis.....	57
Figure 18. Funnel plot of odds of stillbirth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks.....	57

Figure 19. Forest plot for the odds of spontaneous abortion during high versus low temperatures.....	58
Figure 20. Forest plot for the odds of congenital anomalies per 1°C temperature increase.....	59
Figure 21. Top: Meta-analysis for odds of congenital anomalies during a heat wave. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis	61
Figure 22. Funnel plot for odds of congenital anomalies during a heat wave.....	62
Figure 23. Top: Meta-analysis for the odds of congenital anomalies during high versus low temperatures. Bottom: Leave one out sensitivity analysis.....	63
Figure 24. Forest plot for the odds of perinatal mortality during high versus low temperatures.....	65
Figure 25. Top: Meta-analysis of odds of preterm birth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure period < 4 weeks. Bottom: leave-one-out sensitivity analysis.....	72
Figure 26. Funnel plot for odds of preterm birth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure period < 4 weeks	73
Figure 27. Top: Meta-analysis for odds of preterm birth during a heat wave with exposure period < 4 weeks. Bottm: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis	74
Figure 28. Funnel plot for odds of preterm birth during a heat wave with exposure period < 4 week.....	75
Figure 29. Meta-analysis for odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks	76
Figure 30. Funnel plot for odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks	77
Figure 31. Forest plot of odds of preterm birth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	77
Figure 32. Meta-analysis for the odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	78

Figure 33. Funnel plot for the odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	78
Figure 34. Sub-group meta-analysis for odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks, split by Income Level	79
Figure 35. Forest plot for odds of low birth weight during a heat wave	80
Figure 36. Top: Meta-analysis for the odds of low birth weight per 1°C temperature increase. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis.....	82
Figure 37. Forest plot for change in birth weight per 1°C temperature increase	83
Figure 38. Meta-analysis for the odds of low birth weight during high versus low temperatures.....	84
Figure 39. Funnel plot for the odds of low birth weight during high versus low temperatures.....	84
Figure 40. Forest plot for the change in birth weight at high versus low temperatures.....	85
Figure 41. Forest plot for odds of being small for gestational age during high versus low temperatures	85
Figure 42. Forest plot for odds of a neonatal admission per 1°C temperature increase.....	86
Figure 43. Bar chart describing the number of studies that conduct different sub-group analyses	89
Figure 44. Illustrating the distribution of significant effect modification across various race groups	90
Figure 45. Illustrating the distribution of significant effect modification for age	91

Abstract

This systematic review aims to summarise and quantify the impacts of high temperatures on maternal, foetal, and neonatal health, while considering windows of vulnerability, subgroups at risk, and potential causal pathways.

Employing similar methodologies to Chersich et al. 2019., we systematically searched Medline and Web of Science up to September 2018. Updates were conducted in September 2019 and June 2023 in Medline, supplemented by reference list screening. Eligibility criteria included epidemiological studies on high ambient temperature exposure during pregnancy. All maternal and neonatal outcomes were included. A narrative synthesis and meta-analyses were conducted, categorising outcomes clinically and effect estimates into three temperature metric groupings.

The search identified 15,559 and 4,704 records in 2019 and 2023, ultimately with 198 included articles. The 198 articles were expanded to yield 271 outcomes. A discernible surge in studies since 2012 was observed. Sixty-six countries, with high-income countries (54,1%), predominantly in global north, represented the geographical distribution. Neonatal outcomes predominated (n=115), followed by maternal (n=52), and foetal and perinatal (n=51). Among the 20 outcome themes identified, preterm birth (n=73), low birth weight (n=48), hypertensive disorders in pregnancy (n=28), congenital anomalies (n=15), and stillbirths (n=19) were the most studied. Most outcomes had a significant number of studies with a positive direction of effect, except for low birth weight, hypertensive disorders in pregnancy and congenital anomalies, where results were heterogenous. Random effects meta-analysis revealed elevated odds of preterm birth per 1°C increase in temperature of 1.04 (95%CI 1.03, 1.05) and 1.17 (95%CI 1.10, 1.23) during heatwaves. The odds of stillbirths rose 1.14 (95%CI 0.99, 1.31) per 1°C increase in temperature and 1.08 (95%CI 0.96, 1.21) at higher versus lower temperatures.

Trends in effect modification indicated higher risk among age extremes, lower socioeconomic status, Black women, and women who smoke.

This review illustrates a growing body of evidence indicating that temperature exposure during pregnancy has an adverse impact on various maternal and neonatal outcomes. Effect modification suggests impacts may be highest in low and middle-income countries, however, there is a mismatch in research distribution. Further, there are many outcomes that have suggestive evidence for heat impacts, but more research for these is required. This review demonstrates the lack of universally accepted definitions and methodologies, providing opportunities for standardisation in future research. These findings advocate for enhanced awareness, resource allocation for adaptation and mitigation efforts, and further research to understand impacts in vulnerable populations as there is substantial evidence to demonstrate impacts of global warming on pregnant women and their babies.

PROSPERO registration CRD42019140136, CRD42018118113 and CRD42020173519

List of acronyms

Acronym	Definition
APGAR	Appearance, pulse, grimace, activity, and respiration
CI	Confidence interval
EE	Environmental exposure
GA	Gestational age
GDM	Gestational diabetes mellitus
GRADE	Grading of recommendations, assessment, development, and evaluations
HELLP	Haemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, low platelet count
HIC	High-income country
ICU	Intensive care unit
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IQR	Interquartile range
LBW	Low birth weight
LIC	Low-income county
LMIC	Low- and middle-income counties
MNH	Maternal and newborn health
OR	Odds ratio
PET	Preeclampsia
PPROM	Premature prelabour rupture of membranes
PROM	Prelabour rupture of membranes
PTB	Preterm birth
RR	Risk ratio
SD	Standard deviation
SE	Standard error
SES	Socioeconomic status
SGA	Small for gestational age
UMIC	Upper middle-income county
USA	Unites States of America
UTCI	Universal thermal climate index
WBGT	Wet bulb globe temperature
WHO	World Health Organisation

Definitions

Term	Definition*
Congenital anomalies	Congenital anomalies can be defined as structural or functional anomalies (for example, metabolic disorders) that occur during intrauterine life and can be identified prenatally, at birth, or sometimes may only be detected later in infancy, such as hearing defects. Broadly, congenital refers to the existence at or before birth. They are also known as congenital abnormalities, congenital malformations or birth defects.
Foetal	The foetal period is from conception to before birth.
Foetal growth restriction	Foetal growth restriction is defined as the failure of the foetus to meet its growth potential due to a pathological factor, most commonly placental dysfunction.
Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM)	Hyperglycaemia first detected at any time during pregnancy is defined as gestational diabetes mellitus if one or more of the following criteria are met: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fasting plasma glucose 5.1–6.9 mmol/L (92–125 mg/dL) • 1-hour plasma glucose > 10.0 mmol/L (180 mg/dL) following a 75 g oral glucose load • 2-hour plasma glucose 8.5–11.0 mmol/L (153–199 mg/dL) following a 75 g oral glucose load.
Gestational hypertension	New hypertension presenting after 20 weeks of pregnancy without significant proteinuria.
HELLP syndrome	HELLP syndrome is a condition defined by presence of haemolysis, elevated liver enzymes and low platelet count.
Low birth weight	Low birth weight is defined as weight at birth of < 2500 grams.
Neonatal	The neonatal period commences at birth and ends 28 completed days after birth.
Oligohydramnios	Reduced volume of amniotic fluid for the gestational age.
Perinatal	The perinatal period commences at 22 completed weeks (154 days) of gestation and ends seven completed days after birth.
Preeclampsia	New onset of hypertension after 20 weeks of pregnancy and the coexistence of 1 or more of the following new-onset conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • proteinuria (urine protein:creatinine ratio of 30 mg/mmol or more or albumin:creatinine ratio of 8 mg/mmol or more, or at least 1 g/litre [2+] on dipstick testing); • other maternal organ dysfunction (renal insufficiency, renal involvement, neurological complications, haematological complications); • uteroplacental dysfunction (including foetal growth restriction, abnormal umbilical artery doppler at ultrasound, stillbirth).

Term	Definition*
Prelabour rupture of membranes	Prelabour rupture of membranes is the rupture of gestational membranes prior to the onset of labour. When membrane rupture occurs before 37 weeks of gestation, it is referred to as preterm PROM (PPROM).
Preterm birth	Babies born alive before 37 weeks of pregnancy are completed.
Small-for-gestational age	Small for gestational age is defined as a birth weight of less than 10th percentile for gestational age.
Spontaneous abortion	Termination of pregnancy by the expulsion of embryo/foetus before 22 weeks of pregnancy or below 500g of weight.
Stillbirth	A baby who dies after 20 gestational weeks of pregnancy before or during birth.
*Definitions sourced from GAIA, World Health Organisation and HIGH Horizons Glossary.	

1 Introduction

Human-induced climate change poses an immediate and escalating threat to global public health (1). The rise in temperatures and intensification of extreme weather events has profound impacts, pushing both natural and human systems beyond their adaptive thresholds. In 2023, we experienced unprecedented global temperatures. July in particular, recorded as the hottest month on record, demonstrated an average temperature elevation of 1.5°C compared to the pre-industrial era (2).

Rising temperatures are part of a broader pattern of climate change, characterised by an increase in frequency, intensity, and duration of extreme weather events including hot extremes on land and in the ocean, heavy precipitation events, drought, and fire weather (3). We witnessed the record-breaking Hurricane Freddy, the longest-lasting and most accumulated energy in a tropical cyclone, that hit land twice in Mozambique in 2023 (4, 5). Heatwaves have emerged as the deadliest meteorological hazard over the past 3 decades (6).

Looking ahead, the projections are alarming. By 2070, without migration, approximately one-third of the Earth's population will reside in areas with annual average temperatures greater than 29°C, currently only experienced in less than 1% of Earth (7). We are still nowhere near the scale and pace of emissions reductions under the Paris Agreement to put us on track toward a 1.5°C world. Between 2030 and 2050, climate change is expected to cause approximately 250 000 additional deaths per year from malnutrition, malaria, diarrhoea and heat stress (8). Therefore, implementing adaptation measures, while ensuring mitigation efforts are crucial to reduce the loss of lives and burden of disease.

1.1 Heat impacts on health

The impacts of climate change on health are rapidly intensifying, manifesting through both direct and indirect pathways. Elevated temperatures contribute to an increase in climate-related food and water-borne diseases, with notable increase in vector-borne diseases such as malaria and dengue fever, and more suitable environments for aquatic pathogens like *Vibrio* (1, 9-11). The geographical expansion of disease vectors, coupled with heightened reproduction rates contributes to the increased burden. Indirect impacts extend beyond infectious diseases, encompassing soil drying, evaporation and subsequent consequences like crop failure, livestock deaths, food insecurity, and malnutrition. Additionally, heat indirectly affects health by fuelling wildfires, leaving long-term effects such as a loss of animal and plant species, direct injuries, infrastructure destruction, malnutrition, and poverty (12, 13). Many of these outcomes can consequently result in adverse mental health sequelae.

Direct health impacts of exposure to heat are pronounced, with the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) expressing high confidence in linking heat events to human mortality and morbidity across all regions (3). In many areas, ambient temperatures already exceed thresholds where physical labour becomes challenging for parts of the year, with consequential implications for health and performance of workers (14-16). While classic manifestations of heat exposure, such as heat exhaustion and stroke, remain relative rare and poorly documented, more common outcomes include increased mortality rates among the elderly and those with non-communicable diseases, (17) adverse pregnancy and birth outcomes such as preterm birth, low birth weight and stillbirths, (18) and aggression, violence and suicide (19). This leads to increased visits to emergency departments, increased hospitalisations during heatwaves

and subsequent escalation in healthcare costs and long term health consequences (20).

The mental health sequelae of acute or more prolonged periods of heat exposure encompass including generalized anxiety, depression, and the phenomenon referred to as eco-anxiety (19, 21).

Notably, patterns of temperature on health outcomes exhibit a U-shaped curve, with the base commonly found at relatively mild temperatures around 20°C in most tropical and sub-tropical areas. The curves become progressively steeper with each degree increase (for heat exposure) in temperature, emphasising the complex interplay between temperature variations and health outcomes.

1.2 Vulnerable populations

With climate change, the impacts are not borne equally by all. The ability to adapt, access healthcare, obtain necessary medications, and engage in self-care practices collectively influences the outcomes of heat-related health impacts.

Distinct populations, such as those with medical comorbidities, the elderly, children, infants, pregnant women, individuals experiencing homelessness, and those with low socioeconomic status or exposed livelihoods emerge as the most vulnerable groups (1, 18, 22, 23). Further, the IPCC highlights regional disparities in climate impacts, with more projected heat-related deaths in Africa (3).

Strikingly, these vulnerable groups and regions, often least responsible for contributing to climate change, are disproportionately affected – a stark reflection of injustices, and imbalanced power dynamics, both between and within countries (3). The most vulnerable are also the least equipped to adapt to the changing climate, accentuating the urgent need for targeted interventions.

The worsening of hot extremes, notably heatwaves, is particularly pronounced in urban areas, and disproportionately affects economically and socially

marginalised urban residents, particularly those in informal settlements, partly due to the urban heat island phenomenon (24, 25). Within cities, extreme weather events compromise infrastructure, water, sanitation, and energy systems, resulting in not only economic losses but also disruption in essential services, thereby impacting overall health (26).

Climate change is disproportionately affecting women, elevating their risk of infectious diseases, malnutrition, gender-based violence, mental illness, lack of reproductive control, and adverse obstetric outcomes (27, 28). This vulnerability is exacerbated when pregnancy overlaps with societal expectations, motivated by financial necessity and job security to work during pregnancy and postpartum periods (29). Outdoor employment, especially for women, poses very high risks (30, 31).

1.3 Pregnant women and newborns

Literature review of the associations between heat and maternal and neonatal health (MNH) indicates a broad spectrum of adverse clinical outcomes. Maternal outcomes associated with heat include hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (32-34), pre-labour rupture of membranes (35), placental abruption (36), antenatal haemorrhage (32, 33), renal disease (33), and increased rates of emergency Caesarean sections (33, 37). Heat-related adverse neonatal outcomes include preterm birth (18), stillbirth (18), low birth weight (18), and congenital anomalies (38).

The vulnerability of pregnant individuals and their foetuses to elevated temperatures during pregnancy and labour stems from physiological and anatomical changes. Heat generated by foetal metabolism, additional weight gain, fat deposits retaining heat, reduced heat-loss capacity of sweating, and the exertion of labour, collectively heighten the challenge for pregnant women to maintain a normal temperature range in warmer ambient temperatures (39-41).

Further, cardiac output and plasma volume increase by up to 50% by the third trimester, limiting capacity to compensate to higher temperatures. Recent studies underscore the difficulty of maintaining thermal homeostasis during pregnancy compared to non-pregnant states (41-43).

Several pathophysiological pathways have been suggested to explain the potential harmful impacts of heat during pregnancy. Firstly, elevated maternal body temperatures, whether due to exceeded thermoregulation capacity, heat induction during labour, fever, or other factors, can have severe consequences for both mother and foetus. Foetal temperatures are consistently 0.3-0.5°C higher than maternal core temperatures, which puts the foetus at a higher risk if maternal body temperature increases. The vulnerable period of organogenesis during the first trimester renders the foetus susceptible to temperature changes. Hyperthermia, identified as a teratogen in studies investigating hot tubs and saunas, disrupts the typical sequence of gene activity during organogenesis, potentially leading to congenital anomalies (39, 44). Additionally, higher odds of neonatal brain injuries, such as cerebral palsy were associated with maternal hyperthermia at childbirth (45).

The second major pathway linking heat with adverse outcomes involves maternal dehydration during heat events, leading to electrolyte imbalances and endocrine system activation. This adversely affects cardiovascular and renal systems during pregnancy (39). Further, dehydration reduces blood volume, altering blood flow to the placenta and concentrations of blood oxytocin, which can contribute to increased incidence of preterm contractions (44). Dehydration can manifest as severely reduced amniotic fluid during extreme heat events (46).

Thirdly, heat can disrupt hormone regulation, impacting glucose metabolism, reducing insulin sensitivity and affecting mental health through increased adrenaline and stress hormone release (19, 47-50). An increased maternal heart

rate can induce foetal tachycardia and trigger uterine contractions (51, 52). Heat can also cause secretion of ADH and oxytocin which can trigger uterine activity. Additionally, heat stress influences placental growth development, and function. Acute heat stress is associated with reductions uterine and placental blood flow, and chronic stress may result in reductions in placental volume and weight (53-55) which can trigger small-for gestational age, intrauterine growth restriction, preterm birth, or stillbirth (56).

The fourth pathway involves the upregulation of heat shock proteins, potentially implicated in adverse pregnancy outcomes. These proteins are found at higher levels in pregnancies with adverse outcomes, and their role in promoting cytokine release and tissue inflammation may contribute to premature delivery. Heat shock proteins can damage placental cells, and reduce placental efficiency, thereby decreasing oxygen and nutritional supply (39).

It is crucial to acknowledge that much of the research on the biological pathways are derived from animal or theoretical studies, and detailed human studies are notably lacking (57).

Heat impacts on women in pregnancy and childbirth involves a complex interplay of social and economic phenomena, alongside clinical and biological issues (58). Women's' experiences are shaped by various environmental factors, including socio-cultural norms, economic inequalities, health service access, and features of the built environment – all of which mediate the effects of climate change on human health.

This vulnerable population, already burdened by high prevalence of disease, faces significant long-term impacts. Several studies, including in Ethiopia (59) and Uganda(60), and a more recent review, have shown that exposure to high ambient temperatures during pregnancy affects health throughout the entire course of life (61).

Any additional risk for adverse MNH outcomes from heat exposure will have major implications for public health, long-term health, and social and cost implications for affected individuals and communities.

1.4 Current understanding and knowledge gaps

Various systematic reviews have delved into the associations between heat and maternal, neonatal, and infant outcomes. Under the same principal investigator as this review, two systematic reviews demonstrated significant heat impacts on preterm birth, stillbirth, and certain congenital abnormalities (18, 38). However, the evidence regarding low birth weight and other congenital abnormalities remains conflicting. Notably, the meta-analysis by Chersich et al., revealed a 16% higher likelihood of preterm delivery during a heatwave (18).

Other reviews, such as those by Veenema et al. and Rekha et al., echoed similar adverse heat-related outcomes such as preterm birth, birthweight reduction, small for gestational age, as well as other outcomes such as premature rupture of membranes and increased cardiovascular events during labour (44, 62). The most comprehensive review, by Dalugoda et al., examined 75 studies found that only 5% of studies were conducted in lower- middle income countries and none in low-income countries (39). Preterm birth emerged as the most common adverse neonatal outcome, while gestational diabetes was the most frequently assessed maternal outcome (39). However, the critical window period for susceptibility remained unanswered (39). For low birth weight, vulnerability appeared linked to heat exposure during the second and third trimesters, whereas for congenital anomalies, the first trimester and initial weeks were crucial (39). However, the literature showed considerable variation in susceptible windows among outcomes (39). The review identified a significant gap in exploring outcomes beyond preterm birth, low birth weight, and stillbirth (39). Literature

exploring temperature variability, acclimatisation, and biological mechanisms were minimal (39).

Crucially, quantifying the current and future burden of heat-related health conditions is imperative for understanding the escalating threat, especially to vulnerable groups. Existing studies often lack sufficient power to describe specific aspects of heat exposures and temperature thresholds' differential impact on various clinical conditions, settings, and subgroups. The existing literature almost exclusively focuses on relationships between exposure to extreme heat and common outcomes, such as preterm birth, with little known about heat exposure and rarer outcomes, or composite outcomes where several conditions are clustered together.

1.5 Purpose of review

A detailed understanding and quantification of the associations between heat and maternal and neonatal health are essential for designing effective interventions in this critical research and policy domain. Our overarching objectives are to quantify and understand the impacts of heat on maternal and neonatal health while considering vulnerable subgroups, potential causal pathways, composite outcomes, and the level of certainty of the evidence.

While existing literature predominantly reports on preterm birth, low birth weight, and stillbirth, our focus extends to encompass a broader spectrum of outcomes, aiming to cover gaps in previous reviews and provide a comprehensive understanding. We aim to explore vulnerable or high-risk subgroups, discerning both individual (e.g., age, socioeconomic status) and population level risk factors (e.g., climate zones and development index). By drawing insights from the evidence, we aim to explore possible causal pathways. By identifying specific populations, time-periods, and settings most vulnerable to the impacts of heat, alongside the possible causal pathways, our findings are poised to inform

potential interventions and the targeting of resources to those most in need. The quantification of adverse outcomes can be utilised in establishing surveillance systems to monitor the burden of heat-related morbidity, to quantify the effectiveness of interventions, and to model the future health and economic burden of climate change. Ultimately, the insights gained from this review could be used to catalyse changes in policy, clinical practice, and guidance of public health responses to climate change.

2 Methodology

We conducted a systematic review to describe and summarise the evidence of the effects of high ambient temperature exposure during pregnancy on maternal and neonatal outcomes. We used the 2020 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses to guide the conduct and reporting of this review (63). The systematic review, as part of a larger mapping, is registered in PROSPERO: registration CRD42019140136, CRD42018118113 and CRD42020173519.

2.1 Eligibility criteria

All peer-reviewed, epidemiological studies, that assessed the impact of ambient heat during pregnancy on any maternal and neonatal outcomes were included. We included all study designs apart from systematic reviews, qualitative studies, and studies that modelled potential future associations between heat and health. No date restrictions were applied, and no grey literature was included. We included studies on exposure to weather-related ambient high temperatures and not on heat sources related to saunas or hot baths, and not those that examined the impacts of low temperatures. We also included Chinese, English, German, and Italian articles.

2.2 Information sources

This search forms part of a larger systematic mapping exercise that surveyed published literature on heat-health impacts and the effectiveness of interventions to reduce these impacts (64). In the mapping review, we identified articles that assessed the effect of high temperature exposure on health. Additionally, we identified heat adaptation studies which assessed intervention outcomes aiming to reduce the impacts of heat exposure.

Further, the review draws on the results from two subsequent peer-reviewed systematic reviews that were conducted from the results of the systematic mapping (18, 38). The first systematic review investigated the impacts of high ambient temperatures on congenital abnormalities, and the second on preterm birth, low birth weight, and stillbirths (18, 38).

2.3 Search strategy

The systematic mapping search was developed and piloted in Medline (PubMed) from search strategies used in relevant reviews, by speaking to topic experts and methodologists, and by piloting the tool several times in scoping reviews. There was no date limit to the search, nor constraints on the search to specific languages. A separate exclusion for genetics and heat shock proteins were created, as these reduced the sensitivity of the search. A combination of free text keywords and subject headers (MeSH terms in PubMed) were used. The search was adapted for Web of Science, Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI_EXPANDED), Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), and Arts and Humanities Citations Index (A&HCI). Lastly, a filter was applied for excluding animal studies, from aub.edu.libguides.com and for the inclusion of certain intervention types.

The systematic mapping search was conducted in September 2018. We updated the search in September 2019 and in July 2023, using a simplified search in PubMed to identify English studies published since the date of the initial search.

Reference lists of included articles were also screened. The full search strategy is available in Appendix A.

2.4 Selection process

For the systematic mapping, using EPPI-Reviewer software (65), screening of titles and abstracts was done independently, in duplicate, with differences between reviewers reconciled through discussion, or by a third reviewer or the principal investigator (MFC). For the updated review in 2023, using a simplified search, the screening was done independently by a single reviewer. The full text was screened if eligibility could not be ascertained from the title or abstract.

2.5 Data collection process

Once studies were selected for inclusion, information from the full text articles were extracted using EPPI reviewer software, and later Microsoft Excel. Most studies were extracted in duplicate, independently, and reconciled through discussion, or by the principal investigator (MFC). Few articles were extracted by single reviewers, with expertise with data extractions in this field. No contact with authors was made to obtain additional information.

2.6 Data items

The following study characteristics were extracted: First author name and date of publication, study location, sample size, main study outcomes and positive outcomes from effect modification or subgroup analyses. Where a study was conducted across different areas/regions/countries, and provided separate effect estimates per location, this was extracted per location.

The main study outcomes included identification of patterns of association, primary analyses' results, important secondary analyses' results, and the largest effect estimates. Where absolute values of effect estimates were not provided in

the main publication and supplementary files, this was measured from graphs and other plots.

Additionally, we extracted data about the climate zone of the study location, using Koppen-Geiger climate zones, and country level data such as income level and gross domestic product from the World Bank.

2.7 Study risk of bias assessment

Risk of bias was not assessed in this systematic review. Many heat-health studies have a high risk of bias due to exposure bias, confounding bias, and various statistical approaches. Previous heat-health studies have not excluded studies based on high risk of bias. Similarly, we did not exclude any studies on this basis.

2.8 Synthesis methods

We used narrative, vote counting, and meta-analysis methodology to synthesise the information, following guidance from SWiM and the Cochrane Handbook (66, 67). We utilised various methods for synthesis due to the known challenges with heterogeneity in heat-health literature. We described the study characteristics by location, income level, population group, date of publication, and climate zone. We further grouped studies by types of outcomes, guided by the outcome groups from the WHO conceptual framework on extreme heat on maternal, newborn and child health. We further explored critical gestational periods or windows when exposure to heat might have had the largest impacts.

We conducted vote counting, guided by Cochrane Handbook, by illustrating the count of number of effects demonstrating benefit or harm per outcome group, based on the direction of effect of the highest effect estimate for each study. This was necessary as we only had direction of effect as a common data type across all studies in the review.

For the meta-analysis, we classified temperature into three metric groups as was done in Chersich et al. 2020 (18). Firstly, we grouped studies that investigated outcomes using heatwave exposure, based on the definition of heatwave that the individual study used. Heatwaves definition varied, but generally included more than one continuous day where the temperature was above a certain location-specific threshold. The second grouping was change in outcome per 1°C increase in temperature. If results were presented in Fahrenheit or per 5°C or 10°C increase in temperature, we recalculated the effect estimate to per 1°C increase. Lastly, group three included studies that dichotomised temperature effects above and below a threshold level. The reason for this grouping is due to the heterogeneity in time and lag variables, statistical analyses methods, and comparison groups that are utilised across studies. For example, high threshold levels could be temperatures above 75th, 90th and 99th centiles, or the risk when the temperature is compared to a predefined baseline temperature.

We only included studies that assessed the impact of temperature using odds, hazard, and risk ratios. Studies that presented only p values, correlation coefficients, change in absolute grams in birthweight and changes in absolute z-scores for example, were excluded from the meta-analyses. For studies that reported several significant outcomes, we selected the measure with the highest effect size. Given that the lag or temperature threshold at which the impacts are the largest is unknown and will probably vary between populations, the highest estimate might be the true highest level, rather than the result of multiple testing.

We did not take the type of temperature measurement used such as a heat index, or maximum, minimum, or mean temperatures separately into consideration when grouping exposures for meta-analysis.

Meta analyses were only conducted where the grouping was deemed clinically appropriate, and where there were at least four effect estimates. We used

random-effects meta-analysis to describe the average effect of temperature on each specified outcome. Random-effects meta-analysis was selected as the estimate of heat effects will likely differ across studies due to true differences and due to sampling variability. The decision to present the results of the meta-analysis was based on statistical heterogeneity, determined through interpretation of the I^2 value, evaluation of the difference between the common and random effects models, and leave-one-out sensitivity analysis. In addition, for outcomes with at least 9 measures, heterogeneity assessments included funnel plots and prediction intervals. No single measure determined whether a meta-analysis should be excluded. Rather, all measures were assessed in conjunction with clinical plausibility to determine whether the analysis was appropriate.

Where a meta-analysis is presented, both the random and common effect estimates, as well as sensitivity analysis is presented. For outcomes with more than 9 effect estimates, the prediction interval is presented as well.

Where meta-analysis was deemed inappropriate, we present medians, ranges and interquartile ranges (IQR) (if appropriate) to summarise the spread of effects, as per Chersich et al. (2019) (18). In addition, forest plots are presented where there are two or more estimates.

All descriptive and meta analyses were conducted using R version 4.3.1, with the meta package 6.5-0. We utilised Python to create world maps.

2.9 Certainty of evidence grading

An important step in systematic reviews and meta analyses is assessing the quality of evidence and level of confidence. In the medical field, such analyses may be used to implement medical interventions, and so it is important to understand the risks of action and inaction, and the level of confidence in each. In climate change, which largely involves a different body of literature, it is also important to understand the quality of the evidence and the level of confidence in the results

and conclusions. In climate change the purpose of this was, for a long time, simply establishing beyond doubt that climate change is real, and we can observe for example a progression over time from relative uncertainty to ‘unequivocal’ evidence in observed trends.

Several tools are used to assess the level of certainty across a body of research, the choice of which to use can depend on the type of study design: GRADE (Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation) (68) is widely used and responds to the need to know how strongly to recommend certain interventions. Several other standardized tools exist that assesses the risk of different sources of bias in both randomised and non-randomised trials.

Figure 1. IPCC confidence language is based on agreement and the type, amount, quality, and consistency of evidence

Similarly, the IPCC has been using a system of calibrated uncertainty language, to express relative levels of confidence in different kinds of climate change related evidence (from multi-model ensembles to expert judgement). Findings are graded based on the **type, quantity, quality, and consistency** of the **evidence** (evidence is then ranked as ‘limited’, ‘medium’, or ‘robust’), and based on the degree of **agreement** (‘low’, ‘medium’, or ‘high’). Together, different grading levels of evidence and agreement are then used to express levels of **confidence** (from ‘very low’ to ‘very high’), see **Error! Reference source not found.** (69). If the data allows a

statistical, probabilistic quantification of uncertainty, then a **'likelihood'** scale is used instead: 'Virtually certain' ($\geq 99\%$ probability), 'Very likely' ($\geq 90\%$), 'Likely' ($\geq 66\%$), 'About as likely as not' (33 to 66%), 'Unlikely' ($\leq 33\%$), 'Very unlikely' ($\leq 10\%$), 'Exceptionally unlikely' ($\leq 1\%$) (69).

All the evidence in this review is observational clinical data (albeit using different study designs). Observational studies tend to suffer from various biases. A quality grading system such as GRADE would result in a generally low-quality rating. Indeed, meta-analyses that have employed GRADE in review/meta-analyses of observational data, have found the quality of such evidence to be generally low. When assessing the relative confidence in results across various topics, this approach proves unhelpful. Consequently, we have adapted the IPCC approach to grade the evidence reviewed in this study.

2.9.1 Evidence

Evidence is assessed for each outcome theme individually.

Type

Different types of evidence include observational data, proxy data, model-based simulations, theoretical or mechanistic understanding of process or pathways, expert judgment, conclusive evidence, Indigenous knowledge, and local knowledge for example.

Since all the evidence in this review involves observational clinical data, the overall quality should be similar, and could be ranked 'medium', with double-blind, prospective experimental designs more deserving of a 'robust' score, while non-numerical evidence such as expert judgment might have scored 'low'.

Quantity

Quantity, in climate change assessments, covers size of datasets, number of measurements or observations, but also spatial and temporal coverage, extent and resolution, comprehensiveness, completeness, or data gaps.

We calculated quantity using the following:

1. the amount of literature (number of unique studies) reporting results under each theme;
2. the amount of data in each theme, based on individual study sample sizes and/or total number of cases/outcomes.

A decision on what constitutes 'limited', 'medium' and 'robust' evidence in terms of quantity, is subjective, and determined by the topic at hand. We assigned an evidence quantity grading (1 limited, 2 medium, 3 robust) as follows: The themes that were informed by only 3 or less separate studies, were graded as 'limited' evidence, even if they represented very large sample sizes. We assigned a rating of 'robust' to themes represented by 11 or more studies (since the I^2 index has been found to converge to within 20% of its final value in meta-analysis at 11 studies (70)). We assigned 'medium' to the rest.

We did not consider other indicators of quantity, such as spatial and/or temporal coverage and resolution, comprehensiveness and completeness.

Quality

Quality of data is determined by factors including risk of bias, data collection methods, and selection criteria. One of the biggest challenges was that data collection methods, definitions of exposure and outcome, and analytical methods used, varied considerably between studies. Rating and ranking these in terms of quality would present a major challenge and beyond the scope of this review. Different inclusion criteria are graded by the GRADE system, but as mentioned, we did not extract this information, as our review was too broad.

Consistency

Consistency poses the question: do different studies and estimates under the same theme have similar or conflicting findings? We assessed consistency in the study findings, by calculating the ratio of the number of results with a positive association to number of results with negative association for each outcome group. A value of zero means perfect consistency. Very small values mean high consistency. A value of 1 implies as many neg as positive results, and therefore complete lack of consistency. We assigned a consistency rating of 'robust' to <0.05 , 'medium' to values $0.05-0.2$, and 'limited' to values >0.2 . A value of 0.2 implies a ratio of 5 positive : 1 negative results, which casts some doubt. Where only one result was available, consistency was not calculated.

Summary evidence score

An overall evidence score was assigned based on an average of the three underlying scores, rounding up or down based on expert judgment.

2.9.2 Agreement

This is a broader concept than data 'consistency' and it refers to convergence of evidence or a shared understanding among scientists, regarding the particular phenomenon or process. In some cases, the science is so new, that a common understanding has not yet emerged, and underlying biological processes are not yet studied or understood.

The team surveyed all study authors and reviewers in the wider project, and elicit a response to the following question: "Based on your knowledge and experience in this field, beyond the literature reviewed here, would you say that there is general agreement about the effects of heat on this outcome? You may consider whether the science in this field is well established, whether processes are well understood and agreed upon, whether there is general concurrence or alignment

of results, opinions, or perspectives, whether there is a convergence of evidence or a shared understanding among scientists regarding this phenomenon, process, or relationship. Please rank agreement as 'low', 'medium', or 'high' and provide a reason for your score." Based on the feedback received, the team allocated a summary score.

2.9.3 Confidence

Based on the evidence and agreement scores, each theme was allocated a confidence statement, as per IPCC schedule.

3 Results

3.1 Overview

The search identified 15 559 and 4 704 records in databases, with an additional 106 and 27 studies identified from citation searching in 2019 and 2023 respectively, illustrated in the adapted PRISMA flow in Figure 2 (63). After duplicates were removed, and title and abstracts screened, 212 and 80 full text articles were reviewed from the 2019 and 2023 searches. A total of 198 articles are included in this review, 70 from the systematic review by Chersich et al., (18) 13 from the systematic review by Haghghi et al. (38), and an additional 42 from a review in 2019, and 73 from the updated search in 2023. A summary of findings table, along with all the study references in available in Appendix B and C.

The earliest paper dates back to 1938, and we observe a rapid recent acceleration in the number of studies over time: 94% of studies were published since 2000 (Table 1 and Figure 3).

Figure 2. Adapted PRISMA diagram representing study selection process from 2019 and 2023 searches

Table 1. Distribution of studies across location, time, and outcome type

	Categories	Number of studies	Percentage (%)
Location of Study (Continent)¹	Africa	11	5.5
	Asia	68	34.2
	Australia	12	6.0
	Europe	36	18.1
	North America	59	29.6
	South America	9	4.5
	Multiple	4	2.0
Income Level²	Low Income	6	3.1
	Lower Middle-Income	17	8.7
	Upper-Middle Income	47	24.0
	High Income	126	63.3
Year of Publication	Pre-1980	4	2.0
	1980-1999	9	4.5
	2000-2009	17	8.6
	2010-2019	96	48.5
	Post-2020	72	36.4
Population Group³	Maternal	52	23.9
	Foetal and perinatal	51	23.4
	Neonatal	115	52.8
Climate Zone⁴	A - Tropical	10	5.1
	B - Dry	19	9.6
	C - Temperate	79	40.1
	D - Continental	21	10.7
	Multiple	68	34.5

¹ N sums to 199. One paper Bakhtisityarava (2022) performs analysis separately on two different continents

² N sums to 196. One paper Bakhtisityarava (2022) included three locations (Brazil, Mexico and Chile) with two different income levels. Three papers, Dieckmann (1938), Jensen (2013) and Wells (2002) are recorded as global

³ N sums to 218, since 18 papers report two outcomes, and one paper reports three outcomes Khodadadi (2022)

⁴ N sums to 199, since one paper Qu (2021) reports estimates for two different climate zones

Figure 3. Number of publications per year. *Annualized for 2023

3.2 Geographical distribution

The included studies were conducted in 66 countries across 13 UN Sub-Regions, 5 UN Regions, and 6 continents (Figure 4). These included six (3.1%) studies conducted in low-income countries (LIC), 17 (8.7%) in lower-middle income Countries (LMIC), 47 (24.0%) in upper-middle income countries (UMIC) and 126 (63.3%) in high income countries (HIC). They included 43 Köppen-Geiger climate zones with 79 (40.1%) studies conducted exclusively in temperate climate zones, and only 10 (5.1%) studies conducted exclusively in tropical climate zones. Sixty-eight (34.5%) studies were conducted across multiple climate zone classifications, mostly in population studies in larger countries with diverse climate zones such as the United States and China. Mean annual temperatures ranged from below freezing in some areas of China, to 29.5°C in Qatar. Although this represents a broad and diverse population demographic, it is still heavily biased towards the global north, in predominantly richer and cooler areas.

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of studies by: A region; B country, C mean temperature; D climate zone

D

In total, our review identified 23 different outcomes or categories of outcomes, with an uneven distribution of coverage (Table 1). The outcomes are categorised broadly under three population groups, maternal (n=52), foetal and perinatal (n=51) and neonatal (n=115) (Table 1). The most studied outcomes are preterm birth (n=73), low birth weight (n=48), hypertensive disorders in pregnancy (n=28), congenital anomalies (n=15), and stillbirths (n=19) (Figure 5).

The majority of studies focussed on one main health outcome at a time, but 44 studies investigated two or more different outcomes, and some in more than one location, resulting in a total of 271 separate estimates. Further, we explored the direction of effect for each outcome, as illustrated by vote counting (Figure 6). Most outcomes had a significant number of studies with a positive direction of effect, except for low birth weight, hypertensive disorders in pregnancy and congenital anomalies, where results were heterogenous.

Figure 5. Distribution of outcomes across different population groups

Figure 6. Number of results (vote counting) by direction of effect, per outcome category

3.4 Summary of effect estimates

In total, 221⁵ effect estimates were extracted from 198 papers. Of these, 56 described the effect of exposure to 1°C temperature increase, 35 described the effect of exposure to heat waves and 130 described the effect of exposure to high versus low temperatures.

Table 2 summarises the results of the numeric synthesis. In total, 11 exploratory meta-analyses were conducted.

⁵ Basu (2017) excluded because it is the same data, and therefore same effect estimate reported in Avalos (2017).

Table 2. Summary of themes with at least one effect estimates by theme and environmental exposure

Theme	Number of extractions	Synthesis method	Average effect size (OR (95% CI))	I ² (%)
Maternal outcomes				
Odds of gestational diabetes per 1°C temperature increase	3	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.07 (range: 1.01, 1.54)	
Odds of gestational diabetes during high versus low temperatures	4	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.28 (IQR: 1.16-1.45; range: 1.05-1.74)	
Odds of hypertension during pregnancy per 1°C temperature increase	2	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR: 1.12 (range: 1.03-1.21)	
Odds of hypertension during pregnancy during high versus low temperatures	9	Meta-analysis	1.24 (0.98, 1.56)	85
Odds of maternal admission per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.01 (1.00-1.01)	
Odds of maternal admission during a heat wave	2	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR = 1.06 (range: 1.03-1.10)	
Odds of infections per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.01 (1.00, 1.03)	
Odds of infections during a heat wave	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.29 (1.05, 1.58)	
Odds of infections during high versus low temperatures	2	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.88 (range: 1.21-2.91)	
Odds of prelabour rupture of membranes per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.08 (1.07, 1.09)	
Odds of prelabour rupture of membranes during high versus low temperatures	2	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.63 (range: 1.23-2.16)	
Odds of mental illness during a heat wave	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.29 (0.99, 1.67)	
Odds of mental illness during high versus low temperatures	1	Summary of effect estimates	2.90 (2.10, 4.20)	
Odds of antenatal bleeding per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.16 (1.03, 1.40)	
Odds of antenatal bleeding during a heat wave	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.18 (0.98, 1.42)	
Odds of antenatal bleeding during high versus low temperatures	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.12 (1.02, 1.24)	

Theme	Number of extractions	Synthesis method	Average effect size (OR (95% CI))	I ² (%)
Odds of cardiovascular event per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.11 (1.06, 1.15)	
Foetal and perinatal outcomes				
Odds of stillbirth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure period < 4 weeks	5	Meta-analysis	1.14 (0.99, 1.32)	93
Odds of stillbirth during a heat wave with exposure period < 4 weeks	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.03 (1.01, 1.06)	
Odds of stillbirth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks	9	Meta-analysis	1.13 (0.95, 1.34)	83
Odds of stillbirth during a heat wave with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.75 (1.44, 2.12)	
Odds of stillbirth during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	6	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 2.36 (IQR: 1.38-3.36; range: 1.04-6.79)	
Odds of spontaneous abortion during a heat wave	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.05 (1.00, 1.11)	
Odds of spontaneous abortion during high versus low temperatures	6	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.31 (IQR: 1.13-1.87; range: 0.99-3.30)	
Odds of congenital anomalies per 1°C temperature increase	4	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.13 (IQR: 1.05-1.32; range:0.96-1.85)	
Odds of congenital anomalies during a heat wave	12	Meta-analysis	1.24 (0.93, 1.67)	68
Odds of congenital anomalies during high versus low temperatures	6	Meta-analysis	1.48 (1.16, 1.88)	17
Odds of non-reassuring foetal status per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.21 (1.12, 1.32)	
Odds of non-reassuring foetal status during high versus low temperatures	1	Summary of effect estimates	2.07 (1.69, 2.46)	
Odds of perinatal mortality during high versus low temperatures	2	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.57 (range: 1.53, 1.61)	
Odds of composite outcome per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.42 (1.00, 2.03)	

Theme	Number of extractions	Synthesis method	Average effect size (OR (95% CI))	I ² (%)
Neonatal outcomes				
Odds of preterm birth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure period < 4 weeks	12*	Meta-analysis	1.04 (1.03, 1.06)	85
Odds of preterm birth during a heat wave with exposure period < 4 weeks	10	Meta-analysis	1.26 (1.08, 1.47)	63
Odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks	39	Meta-analysis	1.12 (1.06, 1.18)	92
Odds of preterm birth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	8	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.15 (IQR: 1.07-1.61; range: 1.02-4.14)	
Odds of preterm birth during a heat wave with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.42 (1.29, 1.56)	
Odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy	15	Meta-analysis	1.37 (1.08, 1.74)	98
Odds of low birth weight per 1°C temperature increase	5	Meta-analysis	1.31 (0.65, 2.61)	80
Changes in birth weight per 1°C temperature increase	6	Summary of effect estimates	Mean difference -3.00g (IQR: (-4.95g)-(-0.62g); range: (-287.40) - 123.06)	
Odds of low birth weight during a heat wave	2	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.13 (IQR: 1.13-1.13; range: 1.13-1.13)	
Odds of low birth weight during high versus low temperatures	13	Meta-analysis	1.29 (1.04, 1.59)	95
Change in birth weight at high versus low temperatures	8	Summary of effect estimates	Median difference -18.85g (IQR: (-58.87g)-(-13.39g); range: (-133.40)-18.00)	
Odds of small for gestational age per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.10 (1.02, 1.18)	
Odds of small for gestational age during high versus low temperatures	4	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.04 (IQR: 1.02-1.11; range: 0.95-1.29)	

Theme	Number of extractions	Synthesis method	Average effect size (OR (95% CI))	I ² (%)
Odds of a neonatal admission per 1°C temperature increase	2	Summary of effect estimates	Median OR 1.22 (range: 1.02-1.43)	
Odds of neonatal admissions during a heat wave	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.1 (1.08, 1.12)	
Odds of neonatal morbidity per 1°C temperature increase	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.04 (1.03, 1.06)	
Odds of neonatal morbidity during a heat wave	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.01 (1.00, 1.01)	
Odds of neonatal morbidity during high versus low temperatures	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.31 (1.07, 1.60)	
Odds of neonatal mortality during high versus low temperatures	1	Summary of effect estimates	1.28 (0.94, 1.73)	

* Basu (2017) excluded due to duplication of data and effect estimate

3.5 Maternal outcomes

3.5.1 Gestational diabetes mellitus

Figure 7. Forest plot of the odds of gestational diabetes mellitus per 1°C temperature increase

Figure 8. Forest plot of odds of gestational diabetes mellitus during high versus low temperatures

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is sustained hyperglycaemia during pregnancy, diagnosed by abnormal glucose tolerance test. GDM occurs when a pregnant woman develops an inadequate insulin response to maintain a normal

blood sugar, due to decreasing insulin sensitivity (71). The diagnosis is usually made during trimester 2 and excludes a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus before pregnancy and in the first trimester. GDM can have complications for the mothers and the foetus including increased risk of caesarean section, macrosomia (baby >4000g), neonatal hypoglycaemia, and jaundice to name a few (71).

All nine relevant studies reported positive associations between GDM and temperature – mean temperature (72-76) or diurnal range (72-74, 77, 78). Various measurements of GDM were identified in the nine studies, including aspects such as the prevalence of gestational diabetes, oral glucose tolerance testing results, cord blood C-peptide and glucose levels, as well as emergency visits and admissions.

Two studies found that the 2-hour glucose levels during oral glucose-tolerance testing were higher with increased temperatures; 0.009mmol/L increase per 1°C increase in monthly mean temperature ($p < 0.001$) (75) and correlation $r=0.093$ (95%CI=0.051, 0.135; $p<0.001$) with higher temperatures (79). Conversely, negative associations were observed with fasting glucose (74, 79), HbA1c, and umbilical cord C-peptide and glucose levels (79).

There are six studies that assessed the impact of temperature exposure of the prevalence or odds of GDM diagnosis, across various locations. The largest study, with over 555 000 participants found an increased prevalence of GDM in Canada of 1.06 (95%CI=1.05, 1.07) per 10°C increase in mean temperature in the preceding 30 days (76). Similarly, in Taiwan, the odds of GDM increased by 1.54 (95%CI=1.48, 1.60) per 1°C increase in temperature, at mean temperatures of 28-30°C (73). A large proportion of these studies found associations between GDM and exposure to higher temperatures in the second trimester, around the time of screening tests and diagnosis of GDM (72, 74, 76, 77, 80).

Lastly, when assessing complications of GDM, one study of a population of nearly 2 million reported higher odds for emergency visits for GDM OR=1.17 (95%CI=1.01, 1.36) and admissions OR=1.22 (95%CI=1.08, 1.39), on the same day of extreme heat exposure in summer (78).

Overall, the median OR per 1°C temperature increase across the three studies was 1.07 (range: 1.01, 1.54) (Figure 7), while the median OR during exposure to high versus low temperatures was 1.28 (IQR: 1.16-1.45; range: 1.05-1.74) (Figure 8).

Despite varying methodologies applied across the studies, positive associations were consistently found, increasing the certainty of evidence for GDM.

3.5.2 Hypertension in pregnancy

Figure 9. Forest plot of odds of hypertension per 1°C temperature increase

Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy are a heterogeneous group, existing on a spectrum from uncomplicated chronic hypertension, and pregnancy-induced hypertension, to life-threatening organ dysfunction in the form of preeclampsia, eclampsia and HELLP syndrome. Pregnancy-induced hypertensive disorders usually develop after 20 weeks, and in the presence of organ dysfunction, as in preeclampsia, can have serious effects on both maternal and foetal health. Eclampsia, however, represents severe neurological dysfunction in the form of seizures, and HELLP syndrome represents a more generalised severe organ-dysfunction, both of which are life-threatening. Hypertensive disorders account for a large proportion of maternal mortality, and so understanding the effects of heat on this maternal outcome is critical.

The body of literature is diverse, with significant methodological and exposure-measure heterogeneity present. However, overall, a positive association of heat exposure and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was noted, with 21 of 28 studies having positive findings. Heterogeneity in this topic is particularly notable as it includes some of the oldest studies included in our review. In fact, all five pre-1990 studies discuss this particular topic, one noting that a connection had already been observed in 1895 (81). Of the reviewed studies, outcomes included admissions related to hypertensive disorders, diagnosis of hypertensive disorders across the spectrum and blood pressure levels in normal pregnancies.

A large study (82), conducted in a Chinese cohort of over 2 million pregnancies, investigated hypertension and eclampsia/preeclampsia rates in different exposure time windows. It shows consistently and significantly higher odds of hypertensive disorders with increasing heat exposure in the first and early second trimester, with a clear dose-response effect. The maximum OR=1.16 (95%CI=1.10, 1.22). Similarly, studies in Charlottesville and Johannesburg found increased odds of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy from heat exposure in within the first five weeks of pregnancy (34, 83). Additionally, Nasiri et al., (84), in an analysis of hospital records of over 20 000 live births, reported positive association of preeclampsia with temperature in the month of conception ($p<0.001$). Another study (85), found that exposure to heat during the first 4 weeks of pregnancy was associated with an increasing prevalence of preeclampsia, with a dose-response effect noted. On further analysis, however, when adjusted for seasonality the maximum OR was 0.98 (95% CI=0.88,1.08), illustrating a negative direction of effect.

Later In pregnancy was also identified as a potential window of susceptibility. A study conducted on more than 2 million births in Chengdu, China found increasing risk of both preeclampsia and gestational hypertension with increasing

heat exposure in the first 20 weeks of pregnancy (82). Shashar et al., (86) reported a significant increase in the risk of preeclampsia across all trimesters, with a maximum RR=2.91 (95%CI=1.98, 4.28) per IQR increase in heat exposure in the second and third trimesters (equal effects), when stratified by season.

Tam and colleagues conducted a study in Hong Kong, China and found increasing odds of preeclampsia in pregnancies that were conceived in the summer months compared to winter months, with OR=2.8 (95%CI=1.5-5.2) (87). Algert et al., (88) reported increased prevalence of pregnancy-induced hypertension and preeclampsia with conception during warmer months.

In a large analysis of monthly panel data for over 3000 USA counties (89), an increased case rate for pregnancy-induced hypertension and eclampsia was found with heat wave exposure. Exposure to heat waves in the second trimester significantly increased the risk of eclampsia, with a maximum increase in number of cases per 1000 live births of 0.42 (SE=0.212; P<0.05). Rates of pregnancy-induced hypertension increased by 1.47 (SE=0.615; P<0.05), with heat wave exposure in the third trimester.

Six studies reported a negative association of hypertensive conditions with temperature. In an older study from 1981 (90), based on over 80 000 deliveries, rates of eclampsia were inversely proportional to temperature in univariate analysis (p<0.001). Another pre-2000 study (91) presented a crude comparison between the monsoon and the dry season, and also does not present convincing evidence. Temperature differed by only 1.6°C between the seasons, and the significant eclampsia results were based on very small numbers (19 vs 15 in monsoon vs dry season).

Two smaller studies (92, 93) involved blood pressure outcomes, one in 101 home-based blood pressure measures, the other in repeat measures on 1500 women during antenatal visits, without complications. In fact, Metoki et al., excluded

women who developed gestational hypertension from the analysis (93). Both found blood pressure to decrease at higher temperatures, in keeping with acute physiological responses to heat. A South African study (94) found risk of eclampsia, preeclampsia, or HELLP syndrome to be significantly higher in winter than summer. Importantly, the analysis did not examine the temperature at conception, and did not include other variables, such as gestational age and pre-existing hypertension. A Brazilian study (95) showed a clear inverse relationship (5051 hypertensive complications out of 26125 pregnancy-related admissions in a referral hospital). However, the analysis was based on temperatures at the time of delivery, with no consideration of gestational age. Moreover, in this tropical environment the average monthly temperatures ranged only from 24 to 26°C.

Figure 10. Top: Meta-analysis of the odds of hypertension during high versus low temperatures. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Overall, the median OR per 1°C temperature increase was 1.12 (range: 1.03-1.21) (Figure 9). Meta-analysis assessing high versus low temperature exposure on the odds of hypertension found an average OR of 1.24 (95%CI=0.98, 1.56) across nine studies in China, Iran, South Africa, Turkey and the United States of America (Figure 10). However, this estimate should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies:

- I^2 value of 85%, with common effects estimate of 1.03 (95% CI= 1.02, 1.04)
- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis results in point estimates ranging from 1.12 to 1.29
- The asymmetrical funnel plot of effect estimates by standard error reveals evidence of inflated effects in smaller studies (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Funnel plot of odds of hypertension during high versus low temperatures

Therefore, further research is needed to quantify the relationship between heat exposure and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

In conclusion, the body of evidence for the harmful effects of heat exposure on hypertensive disorders of pregnancy is substantive, importantly with several recent studies with modern methodologies providing strong supporting evidence.

Studies showing a negative association were often methodologically flawed and contribute little contradictory evidence.

3.5.3 Maternal admissions

Figure 12. Forest plot of the odds of maternal admissions during a heat wave

This outcome category represents studies that investigated all-cause hospital visits or admissions and temperature. When specific causes of admissions were investigated, the studies are discussed in those specific outcomes. Complications that require hospital admission during pregnancy could include anything from unrelated illness in the mother (e.g., pneumonia) to complications related to the foetus or pregnancy (e.g., baby is not moving and needs intensive observation).

Five studies investigated the effect of heat on all-cause maternal admissions. Unique to this outcome category is the study of heat waves as the main exposure, and large sample sizes. A regression analysis (96) of hospitalisation during pregnancy found significant association with cumulative exposure to extreme heat during the 40 weeks prior to delivery for some outcomes, but not all, which are discussed under relevant topical headings. Qu et al. (78), using a case-crossover design, analysed emergency department visits and admissions due to various pregnancy complications, looking at possible lags of up to 7 days. Hospital admissions were significantly higher after heat exposure in early summer (May lag0d, OR=1.06, 95%CI=1.02, 1.09) but not in mid- or late-summer. The odds of emergency visits and admissions tended to be higher after 3 days of heatwave, than 1 or 2 days.

The other three studies investigated general population admissions, which included maternal and perinatal diagnoses. In national admissions data from Brazil (97), a linear relationship was found between mean temperature, maternal admissions, and certain conditions originating in the perinatal period. When the same admissions data was analysed against various definitions of heat waves (98), perinatal conditions showed the strongest association with extreme heat, while maternal admissions, though significantly positive, were low compared to most other causes. An incremental effect was also found; admissions rates were more strongly associated with more extreme and longer-lasting heat over the preceding 7 days.

Davis (99), in a case-crossover design, analysed admission rate for 21 general population diagnostic categories, and found a marginally significant increase in mean difference of admissions for 'complications of pregnancy, childbirth, and the puerperium', with no lag, during heatwave period 0.4 (95%CI=0.0, 0.8; p=0.034).

For the two studies which reported effect estimates for the odds of maternal admissions during a heat wave, the median OR was 1.06 (range: 1.03-1.10) (Figure 12).

3.5.4 Infections

Figure 13. Forest plot for the odds of maternal infections during high versus low temperatures

There is some evidence for a heat association with bacterial and parasitic infections. An analysis of a cohort of 7976 full-term births (100), found higher risk of vagino-rectal group B streptococci colonisation during screening at week 36

with increased temperature. The association was most pronounced for recent heat exposure (week 32-36), OR=1.01 (95% CI=1.00, 1.03). In fact, a dose-response was observed, with higher risk in quartile 4 OR=1.21 (95% CI=1.02-1.45; p=0.031) than quartile 3 OR=1.18 (95%CI=0.99, 1.40, p=0.068), when compared with the 1st quartile.

Likewise, a study of 270 cases of bacteriuria (based on midstream clean catch urine) out of 1271 screened (101), found that prevalence was positively correlated with average monthly temperature ($r=0.677$, $p=0.003$); prevalence was significantly higher in months with temperatures $\geq 35^{\circ}\text{C}$ (11.3%), versus below (3.6% ; $p < 0.001$).

A case cross-over analysis of nearly 2 million emergency department visits and over 800000 admissions, for multiple pregnancy complications (78), found significant association between extreme heat exposure and emergency visits for infectious and parasitic diseases (9473 cases) in May (OR=1.29, 95%CI=1.05, 1.58), but not in June-Aug and September when case numbers were much higher, and no significant association with admissions. Results for infections of genitourinary tract were also non-significant.

Another analysis (102) found no significant correlation between monthly rates of pyelonephritis (kidney infection), and monthly averaged daily temperature.

Overall, two studies reported increased odds of infections during high versus low temperatures, with a median OR of 1.88 (range: 1.21-2.91) (Figure 13).

3.5.5 Prelabour rupture of membranes

Figure 14. Forest plot of odds of PROM during high versus low temperatures

Prelabour rupture of membranes (PROM), defined as the rupture of foetal membranes outside the context of labour (103), can occur preterm or at term. A total of five studies assessed the impacts of heat on PROM. All five studies consistently found an association between heat and both term and preterm PROM. These studies span diverse climate zones, from China, cities in the USA, and the desert in Israel.

One study provided evidence for an increased risk at higher temperatures, with $RR=1.61$ (95%CI=1.01, 2.57) at 29°C, and $RR=2.16$ (95%CI=1.24, 3.76) at 32°C when compared to the median (104). Notably, no studies were identified that specifically investigated the association between heatwaves and PROM. Additionally, two studies assessed the impact of diurnal temperature variation and found significant associations, indicating that increased changes in temperature were associated with a risk of PROM, reaching up to 23% $RR=1.23$ (95%CI 1.03, 1.47) with a diurnal temperature variation of 17°C (105, 106). Minimal lagged effects were observed, with higher effect estimates demonstrated at short lag periods of 0, 1, and 2 days (104, 105, 107, 108). For the two studies which reported on the odds of PROM during high versus low temperatures, the median OR was 1.63 (range: 1.23-2.16) (Figure 14).

3.5.6 Mental illness

For maternal mental health, two studies assessed the impact of temperature (109) and heat events (78) during pregnancy. A study done in Shanghai, China, utilised the Global Severity Index Scale to evaluate emotional stress and revealed a U-shaped association with temperature, with the nadir of the U-shape at 20-25°C (109). Additionally, an increased odds of emotional stress was demonstrated at a lag1d ($OR=2.9$, 95%CI=1.9, 4.60) and lag2d ($OR=2.9$, 95%CI=1.9, 4.6) when temperature at the 95th percentile was compared to the median percentile (109). Diurnal temperature range was also found to be associated with emotional stress.

The study by Qu et al., conducted in New York State, found a positive direction of effect with extreme heat event and admission for mental illness, however, the association was not statistically significant OR=1.29 (95%CI=0.99, 1.67) (78).

3.5.7 Antenatal bleeding

Also referred to as antepartum haemorrhage, antenatal bleeding is a syndrome characterised by bleeding in second or third trimester and encompasses many causes, such as placenta praevia, vasa praevia, uterine rupture, and placental abruption (110). Antenatal bleeding can have catastrophic consequences for the mother and foetus.

There are five studies that assessed the impact of temperature on antenatal bleeding. Four of the five studies found a positive association with temperature and one study from 1991 that reported no effect estimate (111). Two of the five studies assessed placental abruption specifically; Rammah et al., found almost double the odds of placental abruption per 10°F increase in apparent temperature at a 1-day lag OR=1.93 (95%CI 1.15, 3.23), however only amongst 87 cases (112). Similarly, He et al. found an increased odds of 1.12 (95%CI=1.02, 1.24) with weekly temperature of $\geq 30^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to 15°C (113).

A study by Cil et al. found a modest increase in additional cases of uterine bleeding when pregnant women were exposed to a heat wave in trimester one (114). The large study by Qu et al, on approximately 2 million admissions in the USA, found a non-significant increased odds of hospital visit OR=1.15 (95%CI=0.99, 1.33) and admissions OR=1.18 (95%CI=0.98, 1.42) for antepartum haemorrhage when exposed to a heat event on the same day (78).

Two studies allude to a shorter lag period, with effects on the same day (33), a 1-day lag (112), or in the same week as the exposure (113). Conversely, one study points to exposure during trimester one as the vulnerable period (114).

3.5.8 Caesarean section

There is one study, in the Andean region, that assessed the impact of temperature on delivery via caesarean section, which found a 0.7% increase for one standard deviation above the historical mean temperature, however, this was not statistically significant (115).

3.5.9 Cardiovascular event

One study, in 12 sites in the USA, with 228 000 pregnant women, assessed the association between temperature and a cardiovascular event. Over the study period, 680 cardiovascular events were observed (116). The study found an increased risk of a cardiovascular event on the day of the outcome, and in the week preceding delivery (116). For every 1°C increase in mean temperature, OR=1.11 (95%CI=1.06, 1.15) on the day of delivery and OR=1.07 (95%CI=1.03, 1.12) in the week preceding delivery (116).

3.6 Foetal and perinatal outcomes

3.6.1 Stillbirths

Figure 15. Forest plot for odds of stillbirth during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy

Stillbirths are generally defined as death after 20 gestational weeks. The reviewed studies provide clear evidence that exposure to high temperatures affects the survival of the foetus. All 19 included effect estimates reported positive effect on stillbirths. In two studies the results were not significant (117, 118), but several studies reported a strong effect: one multi-centre retrospective cohort study (119) reported an odds ratio of stillbirths in the >90th centile heat exposure (versus 10-

90 centile group) of 3.71 (95%CI=3.07, 4.47). Several other studies (120-123) reported odds ratios between exposed versus unexposed groups of >2, though with fairly wide confidence intervals. Collectively, the 19 studies include over 10 million stillbirths, and all have large sample sizes indicating a robust body of evidence.

For the four studies that reported significant increases in the odds of stillbirths during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy, the median OR was 2.97 (range: 1.04-6.79) (Figure 15). Five studies (112, 123-127) reported significant increase in the odds of stillbirths per 1°C of heat exposure – from 5% OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.0-1.1) up to 32% OR=1.32 (95%CI=1.20-1.49) per degree.

Over half of the 20 studies investigated a possible lag effect. The evidence seems to point to a short-term effect of heat on stillbirths (of a week or less) though not all studies investigated longer lags. Ranjbaran (128) reported clearly higher risk at 0 and 1 day lags, as opposed to longer lags in daily intervals up to 21 days.

Meta-analysis assessing the change in the odds of stillbirth per one degree increase found an average estimate of 1.14 (95%CI=0.99, 1.32) across five studies, all conducted in USA (Figure 16). However, this should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies:

- I² value of 93%
- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis, the point estimates ranged from 1.10 to 1.17, and the I² value remained relatively stable, suggesting no single study is responsible for the heterogeneity observed (Figure 16)
- The common effect model point estimate and CI differs substantially from the random effects point estimate and CI.

Figure 16. Top: Meta-analysis for the odds of stillbirth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure period < 4 weeks. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Meta-analysis assessing high versus low temperature exposure on the odds of stillbirth found an average estimate of 1.13 (95%CI=0.95, 1.34) across nine studies (Figure 17). However, this should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies:

- I^2 value of 83%
- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis, the point estimates range from 1.09 to 1.16, with little fluctuation in I^2 values, suggesting that no one study is driving the heterogeneity (Figure 17)
- Strand (2012) found a protective effect of heat, with a point estimate of 0.82 (95% CI: 0.64, 1.02)
- Substantial difference between the common and random effects meta-analysis
- The asymmetrical funnel plot of effect estimates by standard error reveals evidence of inflated effects in smaller studies (Figure 18).

Figure 17. Top: Meta-analysis for odds of stillbirth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks . Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Figure 18. Funnel plot of odds of stillbirth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks

Further research is needed to assess the extent of the relationship between short-term heat exposure and still births.

3.6.2 Spontaneous abortion

Figure 19. Forest plot for the odds of spontaneous abortion during high versus low temperatures

Spontaneous abortion, defined by the World Health Organisation as the “termination of pregnancy by expulsion of embryo/foetus before 22 weeks of pregnancy or below 500g of weight” (129). The definition, however, varies across countries. The primary cause is often an abnormal chromosome number (129).

Seven studies investigated the association between temperature and spontaneous abortion. While six studies indicated a positive direction of effect, the findings were heterogenous, with some studies reporting no statistically significant association. Two Iranian studies, encompassing approximately 15 000 pregnant women, examined heat indices (UTCI and PET) and found no statistically significant impact on spontaneous abortion UTCI RR=1.23 (95%CI=0.86, 1.77); PET index OR=1.10 (95%CI=0.89, 1.36) (130, 131). Similarly, a study in New York, involving around 830 000 cases, showed no significant effect with exposure to an extreme heat event in summer OR=1.02 (95%CI=0.99, 1.05) (78).

Notably, a study in China revealed an inverse U-shaped temperature association, with significant effects at the 50th centile in the preceding one and two months before admission, and throughout pregnancy, but found no significant association at higher temperatures (132).

Conversely, in Switzerland, an association was found with threatened abortion (bleeding with a closer cervical opening), but not spontaneous abortion (133). Similarly, in Turkey, among 6053 cases, no association was found (134).

Only one study, in Nanjing, China, among 1000 cases, found a significant association between high and low temperatures(135). At maximum temperature, compared to the mean, the odds of spontaneous abortion more than doubled OR=2.07 (95%CI=1.36, 3.16) at lag1d (135).

For the six studies which reported an effect estimate for the odds of spontaneous abortion during high versus low temperatures, the median OR was 1.31 (IQR: 1.13-1.87; range: 0.99-3.30) (Figure 19).

Despite most studies indicating a positive direction of effect, the evidence lacks consistency across locations, with many studies yielding no association for spontaneous abortion or statistically insignificant results. The observed inverse U-shaped association adds complexity to the overall understanding of the temperature association with spontaneous abortion.

3.6.3 Congenital anomalies

Figure 20. Forest plot for the odds of congenital anomalies per 1°C temperature increase

Congenital anomalies, also known as birth defects or congenital anomalies refers to conditions that are of prenatal origin, that may impact the health of the foetus/newborn, their development, and survival (136). There are many different functional and structural congenital anomalies, and some that commonly occur together, such as in Down's syndrome for example. For the review, we group all

the different congenital anomalies together, and consider risk of any congenital anomaly in association with heat.

There are 15 studies and 22 effect estimates that assess the impact of heat on any congenital anomaly. Of the 22 effect estimates, 16 have a positive direction of effect, five with a negative direction or protective effect, and one study where the direction of effect is not reported.

Congenital anomalies were considered across various levels of groupings across the studies, from specific defects like atrial septal defect and congenital hypothyroidism, to broader categories such as congenital cardiac malformations and neural tube defects, to categories as broad as any lethal malformation or total anomalies.

The study with the largest sample size of over 2 million women and 29 000 anomalies conducted in the USA, found an effect of moderate heat (85th percentile) OR=1.25 (95%CI=1.18, 1.32) and extreme heat (95th percentile) OR=1.29 (95%CI=1.21, 1.38) on total anomalies (137).

Vulnerable exposure windows and the inclusion of lags in the analysis is an important consideration, as temperature impacts are likely to occur during organogenesis early on in the gestational period. Most studies find impacts in the first few weeks of pregnancy; week 5 (138), weeks 4-7 but not to week 10 (139) and weeks 2 and 8 (140). However, one study found a significant impact on congenital heart defect during weeks 8-14, 20-26, and 28-32 weeks (141). Further, one study that examined temperature in the whole first trimester, found no association (142).

Overall, for the four studies which reported an effect estimate for the odds of congenital anomalies per 1°C temperature increase, the median OR 1.13 (IQR: 1.05, 1.32; range:0.96, 1.85) (Figure 20).

Meta-analysis assessing the impact of heat wave exposure on the odds of any congenital anomaly found an average OR of 1.24 (95%CI=0.93, 1.67) across five studies, with 12 distinct effect estimates in Israel and USA (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Top: Meta-analysis for odds of congenital anomalies during a heat wave. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

However, this should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies and limited geographical coverage:

- I^2 value of 68%
- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis, the point estimates range from 1.19 to 1.34, with little fluctuation in I^2 values, suggesting that no one study is driving the heterogeneity.

- There are multiple effect estimates that were found heat to be protective against congenital anomalies
- Wide prediction interval
- Encouragingly, the funnel plot suggests that these findings do not suffer from non-reporting bias (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Funnel plot for odds of congenital anomalies during a heat wave

Meta-analysis assessing the impact of high versus low temperature exposure on the odds of any congenital anomaly found an average estimate of 1.48 (95%CI=1.16, 1.88) across six studies in China, Israel, Mexico, Türkiye and USA (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Top: Meta-analysis for the odds of congenital anomalies during high versus low temperatures. Bottom: Leave one out sensitivity analysis

There is evidence to suggest that this estimate is robust against heterogeneity between the studies:

- I^2 value of 17%
- Small differences between the effect found in the common and random effects models
- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis, the point estimates range from 1.39 to 1.57. Excluding Xu (2023) results in a substantial decrease in I^2 to 0%, indicating this study may be substantially different from the rest. Doing this, the point estimate shifts to 1.39 (95% CI: 1.21, 1.61), slightly decreasing the magnitude but still statistically significant in the positive direction.

However, given the small number of studies, further research to assess the extent of the relationship between exposure to high versus low temperatures and congenital anomalies is needed.

3.6.4 Oligohydramnios

Oligohydramnios refers a reduced volume of amniotic fluid for the gestational age and is usually diagnosed on ultrasound examination. Oligohydramnios is associated with various maternal, foetal, and placental conditions. In the systematic review, two studies investigated an association between temperature and oligohydramnios. A study in Baltimore, United States, found a significant negative correlation between amniotic fluid index and higher mean temperatures in the preceding 2, 3 and 4 days (143). The second study in Paris, France, found a significantly higher proportion in cases in 2003 when there was a heatwave, as compared to 2002 (144). Both studies had very small samples sizes.

3.6.5 Non-reassuring foetal status

Non-reassuring foetal status is used as a term to describe suspected foetal hypoxia and indicates changes in foetal heart patterns, reduced foetal movement and/or foetal growth restriction (145). These changes are usually diagnosed with heart rate monitoring and ultrasound. Non-reassuring foetal status is an indicator of an underlying condition resulting in temporary or permanent oxygen deprivation, which can lead to adverse outcomes (145).

There are five studies that assessed the impact of temperature on the foetal status, all of which found a positive direction of effect (56, 146-149).

Two studies by Bonell, conducted on subsistence farmers in The Gambia, found a significant increase in foetal heart rate associated with heat strain measured using UTCI and WBGT; for every 10°C UTCI and 10°C WBGT increase, foetal heart rate increased by 10.7 (95%CI=7.5,13.8) and 13.4 (95%CI=9.5,17.3) beats per minute

respectively (150). The risk of a higher heart rate was OR=1.45 (95%CI=1.26, 1.64) with increased UCTI, and OR=2.07 (95%CI=1.69, 2.46) with increased WBGT (56). Increased foetal strain (heart rate great than 160 beat per minute and increased umbilical artery resistance) was associated with each 1°C increase UTCTI OR=1.12 (95%CI=1.03, 1.21) and WBGT OR=1.08 (95%CI=0.97, 1.21) (56).

There is some evidence of a threshold for an increased umbilical artery resistance. The resistance decreases, up until 30°C heat strain measured using WBGT, where it then begins to increase (150). This pattern is noted in The Gambia which has a tropical savanna climate. Yuzen et al., describes a decrease in the umbilical peripheral artery resistance for four consecutive days of heat exposure in Germany, a temperate climate (146).

The last two studies measured foetal growth restriction in association with heat. In Pakistan, a study among 459 women found reduced gestational age-appropriate length, height, and head circumference with high exposures in the first and second trimester (148). However, exposure to heat in the third trimester was associated with an increase in gestational appropriate length (148). Similarly, in a larger study in Boston, among 9000 participants, a reduction in age-appropriate head circumference, and femur length was demonstrated with exposure from weeks 16-32, while abdominal circumference decreased with exposures from weeks 16-31 and 32-40 (149).

3.6.6 Perinatal mortality

Figure 24. Forest plot for the odds of perinatal mortality during high versus low temperatures

In our search results, two studies explored the association between exposure to higher temperatures in utero and perinatal mortality (151, 152). In Spain, on the same day as exposure to temperatures >95th percentile, the risk of a perinatal death increased by 53% RR=1.53 (95%CI=1.16, 2.02) (151). The second study, which examined data from old Parish records in 1800's in Sweden, found a reduction the odds of perinatal mortality when temperature >90th centile in the month of birth in non-Sami population, and no association in the Sami (indigenous) population (152). Temperatures in this region were very low, with the median temperature below 0°C for many months (152). For the two studies with effect estimates for high versus low temperature exposure on the odds of perinatal mortality, the median OR was 1.57 (range: 1.53, 1.61) (Figure 24).

3.6.7 Placental outcome

One study assessed the impact of temperature on placental weight, volume, and placental weight to birth ratio, in Guangzhou, China (153). High temperature exposure during the late third trimester was association with a -6.03g (95%CI=-11.28, -0.78) decrease in weight and -16.51cm³ (95%CI=-26.24, -6.07) decrease in volume (153).

3.6.8 Composite outcome

There is one study that grouped two outcomes, namely stillbirth and miscarriage together, to present an odds ratio of experiencing either outcome. This study, conducted in Ghana, assessed the additional increase in odds of stillbirth or miscarriage with an increase in the mean yearly WBGT and monthly WBGT (154). The study found no significant increase in odds of miscarriage or stillbirth with yearly OR =1.15 (95%CI=0.92, 1.39) or monthly WBGT OR=1.03 (95%CI=0.84, 1.27) (154). However, when the study selected 4 regions to analyse, based on similar heat exposure characteristics, an increase in the odds of miscarriage or stillbirth was found for every 1°C increase in yearly WBGT OR=1.42 (95%CI=1.00, 2.13) (154).

3.7 Neonatal outcomes

3.7.1 Preterm birth

Preterm birth, commonly defined as birth before 37 completed weeks of gestation, is a major global health burden, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, contributing significantly to neonatal and child mortality (155). This outcome is prone to measurement error, given challenges in accurately calculating gestational age without ultrasound resources and a known last menstrual period.

The literature extensively explores PTB, with 72 unique studies and 84 effect estimates. Of these, 78 outcomes reported a positive direction of effect, indicating an increased PTB risk. The largest study, analysing 56 million USA births, noted accelerated deliveries on and after extreme heat days, estimating an annual loss of 150 000 gestation days and 25 000 infants born earlier (156).

When exploring windows of susceptibility, we see varying evidence across the literature, possibly suggesting more than one vulnerable exposure window may be present for an increased risk of PTB.

Wang et al. discovered that less intense heatwaves were linked to a higher risk of PTB at weeks 35-36, contrasting with only higher intensity heatwaves exposure during weeks 28-34 (157). Similarly, studies found that short term lags of between 0 and 13 days heeded the strongest PTB risk in California, Spain, Iran. and Italy (158-161). In the meta-analysis (Figure 25), the odds of a preterm birth increased by an average of 1.04 (95%CI=1.03, 1.06) per 1°C degree increase in temperature across all the study locations with an exposure lag of less than one month. While there is significant heterogeneity across the studies, all the effect estimates have a positive direction of effect. The pooled estimate should be interpreted with caution however, due to unexplained variability. The prediction interval indicates that if a study were to be conducted in a similar setting and study population, the

odds of preterm birth per 1°C increase in temperature would fall between 1.00 and 1.08. Similarly, in the short term with a heatwave exposure, on average, the odds of preterm birth increase by 1.26 (95%CI=1.08, 1.47) (Figure 27). Lastly, when comparing high temperature versus low temperature, the mean odds of preterm birth across all studies is 12% higher OR=1.12 (95%CI=1.06, 1.18) (Figure 29). There is significant heterogeneity in this estimate, with two studies that have a negative direction of effect; this estimate should be interpreted with caution.

On the contrary, there are studies that found that an earlier exposure to higher temperatures increased the risk of PTB. In Australia, a study with a quarter million births, observed the highest PTB risk when women were exposed to a heat wave in the first 1-6 months of pregnancy, compared to the 7th month (162). Similarly, a study in Lima, Peru found the highest risk with exposure in the second trimester, and the entire pregnancy, but not for the third trimester (163). In Changsha, China, a cross-country study in Europe and a study by Wang et al, all found that exposure to high temperatures in the first trimester incited the highest PTB risk as compared to the second and third trimesters and the whole pregnancy (157, 164, 165). In the meta-analysis for a long exposure period, the odds of preterm birth, on average, across all the studies was OR=1.37 (95%CI=1.08, 1.74) with a higher temperature as compared to lower temperature (Figure 32). This effect estimate is larger than that reported for a short-term lag of OR=1.12 and warrants further investigation.

A compelling body of evidence across diverse geographical locations and populations establishes a dose-response relationship between ambient temperatures and the risk of PTB (146, 153, 166-169). Numerous studies consistently demonstrate that as ambient temperatures rise or heatwave intensity or duration increases, so does the risk of PTB. In a heat wave study conducted in China by Wang et al., the hazard ratios for PTB exhibited a gradient,

ranging from 1.10 (95%CI=1.01, 1.20) to 1.92 (95%CI=1.39, 2.64) , with higher risks associated with more intense heat wave exposure (157). Similarly, a study by Yuzen et al. in Germany, observed a 59% (RR=1.59 (95%CI=1.01, 2.43)) increase in the risk of PTB when exposed to a heat event at the 98th percentile for a minimum of 3 days, compared to a 20% increased risk with 90th percentile exposure for 5 days, and 45% increased risk with 99th percentile temperature exposure for two days (146).

Similarly, a study by Wang et al., found that a heatwave, when defined using the 98th percentile for 4 days compared to other definitions using the 90 and 95th percentiles at different durations, yielded the highest hazard ratio (169). Similarly, a study in Alabama, with a substantial study population of 500 000, observed a positive correlation between the duration of heatwave and the magnitude of the association with PTB (170).

Conversely, there are two examples where in Iran, and in Stockholm, the higher odds of PTB were at the 75th percentile compared to the 99th percentile (161)(158). A proposed mechanism for this is that people may seek measures to cool down when temperatures are extremely hot.

There are similar shapes of association reported across study locations. In Sweden and Taiwan, we find example of J-shaped and U-shaped associations, indicating risks from cold and hot temperatures (121, 171). It is noteworthy that the bottom of the U or J shape, or inflection point may differ, with temperatures as low as 7.5°C reported in Sweden, 19.5°C in Brisbane, and 23.5°C in Taiwan (121, 171, 172).

In addition to association with temperature, some studies investigated the impact of diurnal temperature variation and day-to-day temperature variation and found significant impacts across locations in Israel and China (106, 173).

Some studies explored type of preterm (early or late for example), location, or by season which sheds further interesting information on the nature of the association between temperature and preterm birth. A study in Germany found an increased risk for late preterm, as compared to all preterm births $RR=2.00$ (95%CI=1.21, 3.21) versus $RR=1.59$ (95%CI=1.01, 2.43) (146). Similarly, and additional two studies found an increase in risk of late PTB as compared to early PTB (108, 174). On the contrary, estimates were higher for PTB <32 weeks as compared to 32-36 weeks in a study in Belgium (175).

Studies that are conducted in diverse locations provide valuable insights. A Puerto Rican study showed regional variations in risk of PTB, with the capital city having no risk, while Ponce, the warmest region, exhibited a significant association (176). A study by Guo et al., in China, demonstrated varied associations across climate areas, significant in hot regions, and non-significant, or even protective in colder areas (177).

When seasons were explored, a study conducted in Australia found that the transition season had higher risk compared to winter and summer (178). The short-term exposure risk was 4% in the transition season, 2% in summer, and a 1% reduction in risk with higher temperatures in winter (178). Similarly, a study by Avalos et al., found a higher effect estimate with increased temperature in warm season of 11.6% compared to 6.2% in the cold season among 14 000 preterm births in California (179).

There are few studies that reported protective benefit or no association with temperature and preterm birth. A study in Iran found no significant association with universal thermal climate index (UTCI) and risk of PTB at short lags 0-21 days (130). However, they did identify a positive direction of effect for a longer lag duration (130). Similarly, a study in Shenzhen, China, involving a substantial sample size of one million mothers, reported no association of mean temperature

from lag 10 days to 30 days (180). However, a study in the same region, with a similarly large sample size, found a significant impact of diurnal temperature range and day-to-day temperature variation on PTB risk (181).

Additionally, an older study, conducted by Porter et al., found no change in mean gestation length in Chicago with increase in temperature, but no direction of effect was reported (182). Moreover, a large study in the UK, involving 482 000 women reported no significant impact of high temperature exposure for 0-6 days before birth (183). Similarly, a recent study by de Bont, did not yield any significant findings of an association between temperature and preterm birth in Sweden (184).

In addition to studies presenting odds or risk, several have quantified the number of preterm births associated with heat, attributed preterm births to temperature and climate change, and quantified the economic burden. In Australia, an excess of 11 (95%CI=9, 13) per 10,000 liveborn are preterm due to immediate heat stress and 36 (95%CI=29, 43) excess preterm births due to cumulative (lag0 to 6 days) heat stress in Australia (178). Further, another study reported that an additional day during pregnancy with average temperature of 90°F leads to additional 0.013 very preterm, and 0.014 extremely preterm births per 1 000 births (185). One attribution study and economic evaluation in China found that heatwave associated PTBs amounted to annual average of 13 262 (95%CI= 6 962, 18 802) cases (186). Further, heatwave related PTBs, induced by anthropogenic climate change, gave an average of 4609 (95%CI=711, 6110) cases annually (95%CI=17.1%, 34.5%) (186). The total economic costs of human capital losses caused by anthropogenic climate change on preterm birth are expected to exceed \$1billion annually in China (186).

In subgroup analysis, we explored country income level and how that modifies the risk of PTB (Figure 34). At high versus low temperatures, the odds of PTB were

highest in low-income countries, with an OR=1.61 (95%CI=1.39, 1.86) compared to high-income countries OR=1.11 (1.06, 1.15), and upper-middle income countries 1.10 (95%CI=1.06, 1.15). Despite there being very few studies in the low-income country group, the findings suggest that the odds of PTB when exposed to high versus low temperatures are higher in low-income countries as compared to upper-middle- and high-income countries.

3.7.1.1 Meta-analysis

A. Exposure period <4 weeks

i. 1°C temperature increase

Figure 25. Top: Meta-analysis of odds of preterm birth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure period < 4 weeks. Bottom: leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

*Basu (2017) excluded from meta-analysis due to the same effect estimate in Avalos (2017)

The meta-analysis assessing the impact of an additional 1°C exposure on the odds of preterm birth found an average estimate of 1.04 (95%CI=1.03, 1.05) across 12 studies, with 13 effect estimates, in China, Israel, Italy, Spain and USA (Figure 25). There is strong evidence to suggest that this estimate is robust against heterogeneity between the studies, despite an I^2 value of 85%:

- Small differences between the effect found in the common and random effects models
- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis, the point estimates range from 1.04 to 1.05, but the CIs are identical, with slight variations in I^2
- Prediction interval of [1.00, 1.08]
- Limited evidence of asymmetry in the funnel plot (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Funnel plot for odds of preterm birth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure period < 4 weeks

ii. Heat Wave

The meta-analysis assessing the impact of exposure to a heat wave on the odds of preterm birth found an average estimate of 1.26 (95%CI=1.08, 1.47) across 10 studies across North America, Europe, and Asia (Figure 27). However, this should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies:

- I^2 value of 63%

- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis, the point estimates ranged from 1.20 to 1.29, and the I^2 value remained relatively stable, indicating no one study may be driving this heterogeneity.
- The common effect model point estimate and CI differs substantially from the random effects point estimate and CI,
- Despite both the common and random effects models producing statistically significant point estimates and CIs, the prediction interval is wide and not statistically significant [0.80, 1.98], suggesting the substantial heterogeneity
- The asymmetrical funnel plot of effect estimates by standard error reveals evidence of inflated effects in smaller studies (Figure 28).

Figure 27. Top: Meta-analysis for odds of preterm birth during a heat wave with exposure period < 4 weeks. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

Figure 28. Funnel plot for odds of preterm birth during a heat wave with exposure period < 4 week

Therefore, further research is needed to assess the extent of the relationship between exposures to heat waves and preterm births.

iii. High vs Low

The meta-analysis assessing the impact of exposure to high versus low temperatures on the odds of preterm birth found an average estimate of 1.12 (95%CI=1.06, 1.18) across 30 countries excluding South America (Figure 29). However, this should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies:

- I^2 value of 92%
- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis was not useful, given the large number of studies with relatively tight CIs
- Point estimates < 1.00, indicating protective effects of heat in some studies
- The common effect model point estimate and CI differs substantially from the random effects point estimate and CI, despite both being statistically significant
- The prediction interval is wide and not statistically significant [0.84, 1.50], suggesting the substantial heterogeneity

- Some evidence of non-reporting bias, with smaller studies reporting higher effect estimates (Figure 30).

Figure 29. Meta-analysis for odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks

Figure 30. Funnel plot for odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks

B. Exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy

i. Per 1°C increase

Figure 31. Forest plot of odds of preterm birth per 1°C temperature increase with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy

For the eight studies that reported on the effect of 1°C temperature increase on preterm birth with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy, the median OR was 1.15 (IQR: 1.07-1.61; range: 1.02-4.14) (Figure 31).

ii. High vs Low

The meta-analysis assessing the long-term exposure to high versus low temperatures on the odds of preterm birth found an average estimate of 1.37 (95%CI=1.08, 1.74) across 14 studies (Figure 32). However, this estimate should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies:

- I^2 value of 98%, with a substantially different common effects estimate of 1.01 (95% CI= 1.00, 1.01)
- One study (Liang (2016)) with an effect estimate < 1.00, indicating a protective effect of heat
- Prediction interval of [0.55, 3.41]
- Evidence of funnel plot asymmetry, potentially indicating non-reporting bias, with smaller studies reporting higher effect estimates (Figure 32)

Figure 32. Meta-analysis for the odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy

Figure 33. Funnel plot for the odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure over a trimester or all of pregnancy

3.7.1.2 Subgroup analysis

High, low, country income level

Figure 34. Sub-group meta-analysis for odds of preterm birth during high versus low temperatures with exposure period < 4 weeks, split by Income Level

3.7.2 Low birth weight

Figure 35. Forest plot for odds of low birth weight during a heat wave

Approximately a quarter of all the 198 papers included in this review fall in the low birth weight group. Out of 51 separate results from 48 studies, 42 found evidence of lower birth weight with exposure to higher temperatures during pregnancy, 35 of them significantly so. Of these, 11 were very large studies with sample sizes exceeding 1 million. Another 10 studies had sample sizes >100 000. Geographical coverage is good, with multiple studies from all the main world regions, despite the inevitable concentration of northern literature.

The largest study was based on 34.7 million national birth data (2009 to 2018) from across the USA (185), analysed against daily maximum and minimum temperature data over the 9 months prior to birth, and aggregated by county of residence at the time of delivery. This study found that every additional day with mean temperature between 26.7-32.2°C, increased very low birth weight by 0.008 per 1000 (0.1% of mean, $p < 0.5$), particularly among Black and Hispanic mothers.

In a similarly sized study that utilised USA birth data from 1989 to 2002, average daily temperature over the entire pregnancy in the 80-90th and 90-100th centile were associated with lower birth weight, respectively lower by -11g (95%CI=-12, -9) and -15g (95%CI=-17, -13), compared to the 40-50th centile (187).

In data from 15 million births in 265 cities in Brazil, Mexico, Chile (188), cumulative exposure to average temperature in 95th centile (compared to a reference temperature of 19°C) was associated with reductions in birth weight: -36.99g (95% CI=-45.50,-28.49) in Brazil, and -8.55g (95% CI=-16.43,-0.68) in Mexico (Chile non-significant).

While these and other studies provide statistical evidence that exposure to extreme heat can be associated with reduced birth weight at any time during pregnancy (189, 190), many analyses disaggregated exposure by trimester, month or gestational week – sometimes only for part of the pregnancy – to determine possible time window(s) during which effects are accentuated. The results have not been entirely consistent.

When disaggregated by trimester, significant positive associations were observed only in the 1st trimester (190-192), maximum effect in 2nd trimester (193-195), or in 3rd trimester (163, 196-199), or both 2nd and 3rd trimester (187), or reversed in 3rd trimester (191, 195).

Analysing the effect of by month of gestation, lower birth weights were reported after exposure to higher temperatures in month 1, with a reversed effect in month 4 (200). On the other hand, (188) one study found an effect later in pregnancy (variously for months 2-3, 6-9) but not in month 1. Analysis by gestational week, covering the entire pregnancy, provides a more accurate picture, than more aggregated analysis, but the results are also variable, with evidence for significantly lower birth weights after exposure to higher temperatures, during weeks 6-20 (201), weeks 10-29 (202), or weeks 0-16 and 29-37(203).

Among the studies were the effect of heat on low birthweight was non-significant, Khododadi (a study on multiple birth outcomes) included heat exposure only during the 21 days prior to birth, which based on other evidence is not necessarily the critical window affecting birth weight (130).

Is there strong evidence to the contrary, showing significant increase of birth weight with temperature, that might need to be explained? In this section, the earliest evidence (204) comes from Irish birth data from 1971-86, which found that with every 1°C increase in mean daily maximum temperature during the second semester, mean female birth weight rose by 3.5g (SE=0.88; p<0.001) but this was

nonsignificant in males (1.02g; SE=0.88; p=0.25). The authors did not look for or find evidence on the effect of extreme heat, but rather concluded that cold temperatures in winter reduce birth weight. A clear seasonal pattern in birthweight disappeared when temperature was controlled for.

For the two studies that reported an effect estimate for the odds of low birth weight during a heat wave, they both reported the point estimate OR of 1.13 (Figure 35).

Meta-analysis assessing the increase of one-degree Celsius exposure on the odds of low birth weight found an average estimate of 1.31 (95%CI=0.65, 2.61) across five studies in Brazil, Israel, Peru, Spain and USA (Figure 36).

Figure 36. Top: Meta-analysis for the odds of low birth weight per 1°C temperature increase. Bottom: Leave-one-out sensitivity analysis

However, this estimate should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies:

- I^2 value of 80%, with substantially different common effects estimate of 1.04 (95% CI= 1.03, 1.05)
- Performing a leave-one-out sensitivity analysis results in point estimates ranging from 1.04 to 1.41. Excluding Chodick (2007) results in the lowest I^2 and a statistically significant random effects estimate of 1.04 (95% CI: 1.02, 1.07). This suggests that Chodick (2007) is substantially different from the other studies and contributing to the heterogeneity.

However, given the small number of studies, caution must be taken when interpreting this more conservative estimate. Further research is needed to assess the extent of the relationship between exposure to one additional degree Celsius of heat and low birth weight.

For the six studies that reported an absolute change in grams of birthweight per 1°C temperature increase, the median of the mean difference in weight was -3.00g (IQR=-4.95g, -0.62g); range: (-287.40), -123.06) (Figure 37).

Figure 37. Forest plot for change in birth weight per 1°C temperature increase

Meta-analysis assessing the impact of high versus low temperature exposure on the odds of low birth weight found an average estimate of 1.29 (95%CI=1.04, 1.59) across 12 studies (Figure 38).

Figure 38. Meta-analysis for the odds of low birth weight during high versus low temperatures

However, this estimate should be interpreted with caution, given the significant heterogeneity in the studies:

- I^2 value of 95%, with substantially different common effects estimate of 1.11 (95% CI= 1.09, 1.13)
- A prediction interval of [0.63, 2.64]
- Asymmetrical funnel plot (Figure 39).

Figure 39. Funnel plot for the odds of low birth weight during high versus low temperatures

Change in Grams

For the six studies that reported an absolute change in grams of birthweight during high versus low temperatures, the median of the mean difference in weight was -18.85g (IQR=-58.87g,-13.39g); range: (-133.40, -18.00) (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Forest plot for the change in birth weight at high versus low temperatures

3.7.3 Small for gestational age

Figure 41. Forest plot for odds of being small for gestational age during high versus low temperatures

Small for gestational age (SGA) foetuses or newborns are those smaller in size than normal for their gestational age, most commonly defined as weight below the 10th percentile for the gestational age (205). A related term is low birth weight, defined as a birth weight less than 2500g, regardless of gestational age at the time of birth. However, SGA is not a synonym for low birth weight as approximately only one third of LBW babies weighing less than 2500g are SGA. SGA is associated with increased perinatal mortality and morbidity.

There are six studies that assessed the association between temperature and SGA, with five of the six finding a positive association with temperature (190, 197,

202, 206, 207). Of these, four studied the effect of exposure to high versus low temperatures on the odds of SGA, of which three found a positive association (Figure 41), with a median OR of 1.04 (IQR: 1.02-1.11; range: 0.95-1.29). There is poor geographical representation with 50% of the studies conducted in the USA, and the other three in Israel, China and the Andean region.

The study with the largest sample size of 29 million term births across 403 counties in the USA, found that temperature in the 80-90th percentile OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.02, 1.04) and above the 90th percentile OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.03, 1.05) as compared to 40-50th percentile were associated with SGA in term births (207). Similar findings were found for preterm births and the highest effect estimates were in marine and cold/very cold climates (207).

When exploring windows of susceptibility, studies found that exposure during the second and third trimesters and the whole pregnancy were significantly associated with SGA (197, 202, 206, 207).

The study by Kloog et al. found a protective benefit of temperature exposure above the 75th percentile during exposure in the whole pregnancy, and the first and second trimesters in Israel (208).

3.7.4 Neonatal admissions

Figure 42. Forest plot for odds of a neonatal admission per 1°C temperature increase

There are four studies that assessed the impact of high ambient temperature exposure during pregnancy on neonatal admissions, all with a positive direction of effect (185, 209). Two studies in Brazil, amongst the same population, observed

a 7% increase in hospitalisations for each 5°C increase in daily mean temperature, and similarly an increase in hospitalisation by between 5-33% using 12 definitions of heatwaves (97, 98).

In 34 million births in the USA, an additional 0.153 per 1000 neonatal ICU admissions were found with an additional day with the mean temperature above 90°F (32°C) (185). Further, in high exposure pregnancies, where there is greater exposure to summer months during gestation, an additional day when the temperature is 2-3 standard deviations above the mean, there is an additional 0.295 admissions per 1000 births (185). Lastly, a study conducted in Ahmedabad found a 43% increase in heat-related neonatal admissions with each 1°C increase in daily temperature above 42°C (209). This is the only study that investigated the impact of an intervention; it found a 64% reduction in heat-related admissions when the labour ward was moved from the top floor to the bottom floor of the hospital (209).

For the two studies that reported on the odds of neonatal admissions per 1°C temperature increase, the median OR was 1.22 (range=1.02-1.43) (Figure 42).

3.7.5 Neonatal morbidity

There are six studies that assessed temperature association with morbidity in the neonate, all of which demonstrated a positive direction of effect. Three of the six studies assessed Apgar score at time of birth (189, 210, 211), 2 studies jaundice (212, 213), and 1 study assessed respiratory distress syndrome (114).

Three studies found a significant association between a lower Apgar score and exposure to high ambient temperatures in China and Colombia. One study in China found increased odds of a lower Apgar score with exposure to extreme heat (>90th centile) on the same day OR=1.31, with a week's lag OR=1.26, and with a lag of 1 month OR=1.24 (210). Another study in China found that the total Apgar score decreased by 0.03% when duration of extreme temperatures increases by a day

(211). Lastly, a study in Colombia found a lower likelihood of 0.2-0.6% of having a normal Apgar during a heatwave (189).

The two studies that assessed neonatal jaundice found a 4% increase in referral for jaundice when assessed visually by community health workers in Pakistan for every 1°C increase in the minimum temperature (213), while the second study found a decrease in total serum bilirubin in a neonate with increase in the mean temperature (212). Lastly, a study in the USA among half a million births, found a positive association between heatwave exposure in all three trimesters individually and any adverse neonatal outcome at birth (foetal distress, assisted breathing with a ventilator, meconium aspiration syndrome) (114).

3.7.6 Neonatal mortality

Only one study explored the impact of neonatal mortality and temperature in 2 million births in Taiwan (214). Compared to a temperature of 21.5-23.4°C, the risk of neonatal mortality increased, non-significantly, by 28% (95%CI=0.94, 1.73) with exposure to temperatures between 25.5°C-27.4°C (214). Similarly, there was an increased risk, but statistically not significant, for exposure to higher temperatures up to 30.8°C (214).

3.8 Effect modification

There is a small proportion of studies that assess effect modification, or subgroup analysis to identify high-risk groups. Across the studies that do assess subgroups, the division of groups is heterogenous, for example, age could be divided into binary or in 3-4 categories. Furthermore, very few studies conduct analyses to detect statically significant differences between subgroups. Appendix C in the supplementary file provides summary estimates for the studies that investigated effect modification.

Figure 43 describes the number of studies that found a difference in effect estimates across the sub-group outcomes. The differences were not always statistically significant. Race was the most studied individual risk factor, with 31 studies finding a difference by race in maternal/foetal/neonatal outcomes. This was followed by age (n=28), sex (n=24), education (n=17), and socioeconomic status (n=16). Notably, only one study assessed air conditioning’s modification on the adverse risk of high temperatures. Additional built environment variables that were assessed were urbanicity which included population density and normalised difference vegetation index.

Figure 43. Bar chart describing the number of studies that conduct different sub-group analyses

There appears to be a trend toward Black, followed by Hispanic groups that were found to have a higher risk of any adverse foetal/neonatal outcome across the literature (Figure 44). This is evident by the higher number of ‘red squares,’ i.e. a study that observed a higher risk in that population, in the Black and Hispanic columns.

Figure 44. Illustrating the distribution of significant effect modification across various race groups

1 st author (year)	Black	Hispanic	Indigenous	Non-indigenous	White
Foetal/neonatal					
Wang (2013)					
Mathew (2017)					
Porter (1999)					
Sun (2019)					
Carmichael, (2014)					
Basu (2010)					
Basu (2017)					
Ngo (2016)					
Smith (2022)					
Cil (2022)					
Requia (2022)					
Nyadanu (2022)					
MacVicar (2017)					
Ngo (2016)					
Basu (2018)					
Cil (2022)					
Yitshak-Shade (2021)					
Rammah (2019)					
Basu (2016)					
Savitz (2021)					
MacVicar (2017)					
Richards (2022)					
Mathew (2017)					
Barreca (2020)					
Schumann (2019)					
Zhang (2023)					
Van Zutphen					
Maternal					
Shashar (2020)					
Ha (2017)					
Rammah (2019)					
He (2018)					
Gat (2021)					
Lin (2017)					
Kim (2021)					

When age was mapped across the literature, we can observe a pattern where most studies that found an effect modification, identified this in the extreme maternal ages. We can observe that most of the 'red boxes' lie on either age extremes (Figure 45). Notably, there are some studies that found women in the ages that fall in the middle of the diagram (24-35 years old) at higher risk, but it may represent how the age groups were categorised than actual risk.

Figure 45. Illustrating the distribution of significant effect modification for age

Preterm births																									
Zhong (2018)																									
Wu (2019)																									
Wang (2013)																									
Son (2019)																									
Liang (2016)																									
Cox (2016)																									
Schifano (2013)																									
Asta (2019)*																									
Sun (2019)																									
Basu (2010)																									
Basu (2017)																									
Ngo (2016)																									
Nyadanu (2022)																									
Li (2021)																									
Cheng (2020)																									
Gronlund (2020)																									
Gong (2021)																									
Low birth weight																									
Andalon (2016)																									
Ngo (2016)																									
Basu (2018)																									
Leung (2023)																									
Zhang (2021)																									
Stillbirth																									
Basu (2016)																									
	≤17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	28	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	≥41

3.9 Quality assessment

Using an adapted approach to the IPCC confidence assessment, the evidence scores of type, quantity, quality, and consistency across reported outcomes are shown in Table 3.

All studies are observational and are consequently given the same scoring for type of study. Quality or risk of bias was not assessed in this study. For quantity, the outcomes that have the most evidence are for stillbirths, congenital anomalies, preterm birth, low birth weight, and hypertension in pregnancy. In terms of consistency, most studies have coherent results, apart from the body of evidence on congenital anomalies and hypertension in pregnancy that score poorly.

The certainty grading is on ongoing process. We are currently reaching out to study authors to use the evidence gathered for the review, their existing knowledge in this field, and thoughts about biological plausibility to grade the evidence. We will collate these findings and present them in future.

Table 3. Adapted IPCC evidence scores

MATERNAL OUTCOMES			
Gestational diabetes mellitus	2	2	3
Hypertension in pregnancy	2	3	1
Maternal admissions	2	2	3
Infections	2	2	3
Prelabour rupture of membranes	2	2	3
Mental health	2	1	3
Antenatal bleeding	2	2	3
Caesarean section	2	1	-
Cardiovascular event	2	1	-
FOETAL AND NEONATAL OUTCOMES			
Stillbirths	2	3	2
Spontaneous abortion	2	2	2
Congenital anomalies	2	3	1
Oligohydramnios	2	1	3
Non-reassuring foetal status	2	2	3
Perinatal mortality	2	1	3
Placental outcome	2	1	-
Composite outcome	2	1	-
NEONATAL OUTCOMES			
Preterm birth	2	3	2
Low birth weight	2	3	2
Small for gestational age	2	2	2
Neonatal admissions	2	2	3
Neonatal morbidity	2	2	3
Neonatal mortality	2	1	-

4 Discussion

There is an extensive body of literature on the impacts of high ambient temperature exposure on adverse maternal, foetal, and neonatal outcomes. We identified just under 200 studies, with approximately half of the studies assessing neonatal outcomes, and the rest split between maternal and foetal outcomes.

The evidence was skewed towards certain outcomes, with five topics (preterm births, low birth weight, hypertension in pregnancy, congenital abnormalities and stillbirths) accounting for 75% of the evidence (200 out of 271 individual results).

Ten topics were represented by only one or two results, which points to a need for further investigations in this emerging field. Furthermore, there was a mismatch between disease burden and research efforts, both from a social equity perspective and regarding the major causes of maternal morbidity and mortality. When assessing the body of literature on **maternal outcomes**, there is compelling evidence that high temperatures increase the risk of hypertension in pregnancy, gestational diabetes mellitus, and all-cause admissions with a large number of studies in each category, consistently finding a positive direction of effect. While fewer studies assessed prelabour rupture of membranes, antenatal bleeding, mental illness, caesarean section, and cardiovascular events, the evidence was consistently in support of an impact of temperature on these adverse outcomes. Worldwide, the top five causes of maternal mortality are severe bleeding, infections, hypertension in pregnancy, complications from delivery, and unsafe abortion (215). There is a mismatch in research on temperature effects when compared to the top causes of maternal mortality. The literature has only five studies on antenatal bleeding and no studies on post-partum haemorrhage, which accounts for a large burden of all maternal mortality from bleeding. Further, there are very few studies on pregnancy related infections, and no studies on non-pregnancy related infections like malaria, only one study on complications from delivery (caesarean section). Lastly, all maternal outcomes only account for a quarter of the body of literature and as a population are under-represented in heat-health research.

Foetal and perinatal outcomes account for another quarter of the overall body of literature, with the most studied outcomes being congenital anomalies and stillbirths. The literature provides convincing evidence of an impact of temperature on any congenital anomaly, stillbirths, and non-reassuring foetal status. The odds of any congenital anomaly when the temperature is high

compared to low, increase on average across the literature by 1.48 (95%CI=1.16, 1.88) and by 1.24 (95%CI=0.96, 1.85) during a heatwave. For stillbirths, the odds of stillbirth were on average 1.14 (95%CI=0.99, 1.32) per 1°C increase in temperature and 1.13 (95%CI=0.95, 1.34) at high versus low temperatures for short lag period. These results were similar to those in Chersich et al. (18), but have slightly larger confidence intervals, likely due to increased heterogeneity when more studies are included in the meta-analysis. There is less evidence for oligohydramnios, perinatal mortality, and placental outcomes with two or less studies for each.

The literature was skewed toward **neonatal outcomes** with the greatest number of studies on evidence of an association between preterm birth and high ambient temperature. The number of studies in preterm birth allowed for further exploration, with evidence suggesting two periods of susceptibility to heat during the gestational period, evidence of a dose-response relationship, evidence of effect of diurnal temperature range and day-to-day temperature variation effects, and progress in the field to quantify the impacts and attribute those to anthropogenic-induced climate change. The other outcomes were low birth weight, where there was more heterogeneity in the direction of effect, but with some large studies suggestive of a decrease in weight. However, small-for-gestational age, which can be associated with low birth weight, had significant evidence of association with temperature, and may potentially be a better indicator of heat stress. Neonatal admissions were significantly associated with temperature in the literature. Lastly, there were few studies that assess Apgar scores, jaundice, and neonatal mortality to draw meaningful conclusions, but the early evidence suggests impacts on all these outcomes. As with maternal outcomes, there is a mismatch between the main global causes of neonatal morbidity and mortality and the prioritisation of those outcomes in the body of literature on heat-health associations.

Overall, this review has presented the emerging and growing evidence on the harmful effect of heat on maternal, foetal, and neonatal outcomes, though the evidence is unevenly distributed geographically (Table 1), with a distinct concentration in high-income countries. The dearth of research from low-income countries (3%), and from tropical (5%) climate zones, points to an important knowledge gap in these areas. Poor **geographical representation** is in keeping with other systematic reviews in this field (18, 216).

Evidence from this review suggests that pregnant women and neonates that live in low-and-middle income countries are at a higher risk of adverse impacts of temperature. There is well established evidence that the most **vulnerable** populations are in low-and-middle income countries, already experiencing the highest burden of maternal and neonatal mortality (3). There is an obvious mismatch between vulnerability to temperature effects and research effort, which needs to be addressed in future work.

The studies varied considerably with regard to **study design and methodologies**, as is common in heat-health literature reviews. In keeping with the purpose of our review, we retained all studies, despite the heterogeneity in study designs and potential risk of bias. The heterogeneity was present clinically, methodologically, and ultimately resulted in statistical heterogeneity, represented by high I^2 results in the meta-analysis.

Clinically, **definitions of outcomes**, or what constitutes a 'case', including how or when it is detected or measured, even for the same type of outcome varied (e.g., identified actively through routine testing or passively through emergency visits). This is also reflective of the maternal and neonatal health field, where there is country or region-specific definitions for some outcomes such as stillbirth which may vary based on local definitions of foetal viability. Some types of outcomes are presented on a continuum (e.g. blood sugar levels with gestational diabetes in the

extreme case, or blood pressure levels with preeclampsia and eclampsia on the extreme high end) while other outcomes have binary definitions (e.g. stillbirth). Additionally, enrolment methods or participant inclusion criteria differed widely, including (near-) all-of-population scenarios (e.g., all registered live births in a geographical area), to convenient selection criteria (e.g., emergencies at a health facility), to some kind of recruitment procedure (e.g., recruited from participants in another study).

Definitions of **heat exposure classification** varied considerably, with regard to the temperature measurement that was used (temperature mean, minimum, maximum, range, with or without considering humidity, and heat indices), which could differ by source (weather station data, climate models), by aggregation period and timing (annual / trimester / calendar month / calendar week / gestational week / daily / degree-days / shifting periods / moving averages), or with varying definitions of extreme heat exposure and heatwaves (different absolute temperature thresholds, different relative thresholds such as centiles). The World Meteorological Organisation's definition of heat waves, "understood to be periods of unusually hot and dry or hot and humid weather that have a subtle onset and cessation, a duration of at least 2 to 3 days, usually with a discernible impact on human and natural systems." However, there is no universally accepted definition for excessive heat, extreme heat, heat waves, extreme heat events, heat exposure and high ambient temperatures which is reflected in the heterogeneity in exposure classification found in the literature.

Heterogeneity is also found in the **study designs**, with simple linear regression designs, to case-control, to the newer case-crossover and time-series analyses. Confounding is controlled for differently, varying lag periods are measured, there is an array of results that are reported (e.g., odds ratio, risk ratio, prevalence ratio, cumulative relative risk ratio, absolute change in grams, number of gestation days

lost, Pearson's correlation coefficient, regression coefficient), and these results are reported for differing exposure measurements (per 1°C increase, per 10°C increase, per 10°F increase, per SD above mean, at a high percentile compared to a lower percentile, a higher IQR compared to a lower IQR).

This field may benefit from an attempt at **standardisation** of exposure classification, dealing with confounding, and analytical approaches. Distributed lag analysis has emerged as a useful method to investigate the contribution of heat exposure during any single week or day towards the final health outcome, and thus make it possible to determine possible vulnerable windows of exposure. Linear and non-linear distributed lag models allow flexible modelling of exposure-response functions and can therefore identify and describe delayed effects.

While there seems to be strong evidence for a positive link between heat exposure and various adverse maternal, foetal, and neonatal outcomes, there were also many **negative results**, even other results within studies for which we have extracted positive results. The biophysical pathways must be diverse and complex, easily confounded or modified by many other factors, depending on context and mean conditions. Further, windows of susceptibility during the gestational period and lag periods may also result in negative results, if these are missed in the analysis. This review is too broad to delve into this level of detail.

In some instances authors found a **U-shaped relationship**, where a negative outcome was more likely in very low and very high temperatures, for example in preterm births (164, 217) with the nadir of the U-shape at 25°C and 17-19°C respectively, or Apgar scores (210) relative to 12.5°C, or birth weight (196, 218) relative to 13-18°C and the 41-50th centile respectively, or emotional stress (109), relative to 20-25°C. Inverse U-shaped associations were also observed, e.g. on preterm births (132), or odds of miscarriage(132). Careful reanalysis or new research, including prospective studies that measure any relevant variables

comprehensively and in a disaggregated manner, would help unravel these complexities.

There are only a small proportion of studies that investigate individual risk factors through **effect modification or subgroup analysis**. Trends in the evidence suggest that Black and Hispanic mums are at higher risk, as well as mums at the age extremes. Additionally, women with lower levels of education and socioeconomic status appear to be at higher risk. Further investigation into subgroups, for factors such as air conditioning, access to healthcare, and type of housing for example are important next steps. Assessing subgroups will not only assist in better understanding heterogeneity observed across study populations, but are also important for adaptation interventions, which can be targeted to those populations that are at highest risk.

There is one study in the evidence that calculated the number of preterm births that can be attributable to anthropogenic induced climate change. There is limited evidence of these attribution type studies in the heat-health literature. **Attribution studies**, a subset of impact studies, attempt to define the extent to which a given (health) outcome can be attributed to climate change, i.e. with what (statistical) level of confidence can climate change be blamed, or what fraction of the health outcome can be attributed to climate change as opposed to other causes. Attribution studies are becoming increasingly important in the light of the concept of Loss and Damage, especially now that a Loss and Damage Fund has been established to pay out money to relieve actual losses attributable to climate change. In this highly politicised and monetized international context, confidence in evidence takes on a new meaning. Given the lack of research on attribution, and the importance of this type of evidence, more research is recommended.

Limitations

The systematic review is not without its limitations, and consideration of these is important when interpreting the findings. Firstly, the search strategy, while initially conducted in numerous databases, was only updated in PubMed, which may exclude studies published in specialised environmental journals. We did attempt to address this through extensive citation searching, but there may still be some missing research papers.

A notable limitation is the absence of assessment of the quality of studies and risk of bias. Previous systematic reviews in this field suggest that most studies score poorly on quality assessments and have a high risk of bias. Based on our knowledge of limited literature on many outcomes, we wanted to ensure our review incorporated all studies, so we did not exclude based on quality. Furthermore, with the large number of studies in the review, it was not within the scope to assess quality. Additionally, if there were any data discrepancies, we did not reach out to data providers, due to the large number of studies.

Each one of the studies included in this review might have contained several results (some report over 50 effect estimates), for example for different models, or different time periods. We focussed on the most significant results reported, thereby potentially losing details. Studies with highly significant results might also have reported non-significant results – or even trend reversals – based on different timing or definitions of exposure, different measures of the outcome variable or different analytical approaches. With 198 studies included, and around 20 subtopics, we were not able to do justice to the full details of the various analyses. To get a complete picture of current evidence under each subtopic, a more detailed analysis would be required.

Each synthesis method has limitations. Vote counting does not consider the relative sizes of the studies and differences in sizes of effect. This was partially

addressed by presenting direction of effect and not statistical significance. The meta-analysis only accounts for studies that reported an effect estimate that could be compared across 3 or more studies for the outcome exposure, so is not inclusive of all studies in the field. It also uses the biggest effect estimate extracted from the study which likely introduces further heterogeneity. Lastly, the thematic synthesis best attempts to group similar studies, but some outcomes may be relevant for maternal or foetal or neonatal populations, for example, oligohydramnios may be maternal or foetal outcome. By combining and triangulating results across these synthesis methods, we hope to reduce the limitations incurred by each.

Our outcomes and effect estimations are based on observational studies, which are prone to bias and make the assessment of causality challenging. However, observational data is often the only available data in this field, and despite its limitations, can be used to provide evidence for some hypotheses, can suggest avenues for future exploration, and have more credibility when supported by theoretical and empirical evidence.

5 Conclusion

This review presents a growing evidence base on the effect of heat on a list of pregnancy and birth outcomes. Despite the high degree of variability in study methods, it is noteworthy to find consistent (and significant) impacts of heat. Temperature-related increases in the odds of negative outcomes, range from <5%, to 30% and higher, to over 200%. These risks are not negligible by far. An increase of 10 or 20 or even 30% in any *one* of these different outcomes must significantly increase the risk and health burden on already vulnerable pregnant women and their babies. There is an urgent need to mitigate the impacts of heat on pregnant women and the babies.

The review highlights clearly the outcomes that have relatively more evidence, while others, which also contribute significantly to the burden of maternal and neonatal mortality are less studied. Each theme warrants its own more detailed follow-up review, especially as evidence accumulates, geographical gaps are attended to, and biophysical pathways are explored. With only one study investigating attribution to climate change, the maternal and child health community have some way to go to access loss and damage funds incurred from the rapidly increasing heat.

6 References

1. Romanello M, Napoli CD, Green C, Kennard H, Lampard P, Scamman D, et al. The 2023 report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: the imperative for a health-centred response in a world facing irreversible harms. *Lancet*. 2023.
2. NASA. NASA Clocks July 2023 as Hottest Month on Record Ever Since 1880 2023 [Available from: <https://www.nasa.gov/news-release/nasa-clocks-july-2023-as-hottest-month-on-record-ever-since-1880/>].
3. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [H.-O. Pörtner DCR, M. Tignor, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lössche, V. Möller, A. Okem, B. Rama (eds.)]. IPCC, 2022: Summary for Policymakers [H.-O. Pörtner, D.C. Roberts, E.S. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, M. Tignor, A. Alegría, M. Craig, S. Langsdorf, S. Lössche, V. Möller, A. Okem (eds.)] In: *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability*. . UK and New York, NY, USA: Cambridge University Press; 2022. p. pp. 3-33.
4. Liu HY, Satoh M, Gu JF, Lei L, Tang J, Tan ZM, et al. Predictability of the Most Long-Lived Tropical Cyclone Freddy (2023) During Its Westward Journey Through the Southern Tropical Indian Ocean. *Geophysical Research Letters*. 2023;50(20).
5. NASA. NASA Tracks Freddy, Longest-lived Tropical Cyclone on Record 2023 [Available from: <https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/14312>].
6. World Meteorological Organization. *The Global Climate in 2015-2019*. Geneva, Switzerland; 2019.
7. Xu C, Kohler TA, Lenton TM, Svenning JC, Scheffer M. Future of the human climate niche. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2020;117(21):11350-5.
8. World Health Organisation. *Climate change and health 2023* [Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/climate-change-and-health>].
9. Attaway D, Jacobsen K, Falconer A, Manca G, Waters NR. Risk analysis for dengue suitability in Africa using the ArcGIS predictive analysis tools (PA tools). *Acta Tropica* 2016;158:248-57.

10. Ebi K, Nealon J. Dengue in a changing climate. *Environmental Research*. 2016;151:115-23.
11. Ebi K. Adaptation costs for climate change-related cases of diarrhoeal disease, malnutrition, and malaria in 2030. *Global Health*. 2008;4(9).
12. Xu R, Yu P, Abramson M, Johnston F. Wildfires, Global Climate Change, and Human Health. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2020.
13. Zhang Y, Beggs P, McGushin A, Bambrick H. The 2020 special report of the MJA-Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: lessons learnt from Australia's "Black Summer". *Medical Journal of Australia*. 2020.
14. Engelbrecht F, Adegoke J, Bopape M, Naidoo M. Projections of rapidly rising surface temperatures over Africa under low mitigation. *Environmental Research Letters* 2015;10(8).
15. Global Commission on Adaptation. *Adapt now: a global call for leadership on climate resilience 2019* [Available from: <https://reliefwebint/report/world/adapt-now-global-call-leadership-climate-resilience>]
16. International Labour Organization. *Working on a warmer planet: The effect of heat stress on productivity and decent work 2019* [Available from: https://www.ilo.org/global/publications/books/WCMS_711919/lang--en/index.htm].
17. Gasparrini A, Guo Y, Hashizume M, Lavigne E. Mortality risk attributable to high and low ambient temperature: a multicountry observational study. *Lancet*. 2015;386(9991):369-75.
18. Chersich MF, Pham MD, Areal A, Haghghi MM, Manyuchi A, Swift CP, et al. Associations between high temperatures in pregnancy and risk of preterm birth, low birth weight, and stillbirths: systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ*. 2020;371:m3811.
19. Chersich M, Swift C, Edelstein I, Breetzke G. Violence in hot weather: Will climate change exacerbate rates of violence in South Africa? . *South African Medical Journal*. 2019;109(7):447-9.
20. Ebi K, Hess J, Watkiss P, Mock C, Nugent R, Kobusingye O. Health Risks and Costs of Climate Variability and Change. In: Bank TIBfRaDTW, editor. *Injury Prevention and Environmental Health*. 3rd edition ed. Washington (DC): The World Bank; 2017.
21. Watts N, Amann M, Arnell N, Ayeb-Karlsson S, Beagley J, Belesova K, et al. The 2020 report of The Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: responding to converging crises. *Lancet*. 2020.
22. Helldén D, Andersson C, Nilsson M, Ebi KL, Friberg P, Alfvén T. Climate change and child health: a scoping review and an expanded conceptual framework. *The Lancet Planetary Health*. 2021;5(3):e164-e75.
23. Hajat S, Sarran CE, Bezgrebelna M, Kidd SA. Ambient Temperature and Emergency Hospital Admissions in People Experiencing Homelessness: London, United Kingdom, 2011-2019. *Am J Public Health*. 2023;113(9):981-4.
24. Souverijns N, De Ridder K, Veldeman N, Lefebvre F, Kusambiza-Kiingi F, Memela W, et al. Urban heat in Johannesburg and Ekurhuleni, South Africa: A meter-scale assessment and vulnerability analysis. *Urban Clim*. 2022;46:101331.
25. UCCRN. *The Future We Do'nt Want: How Climate Change Could Impact the World's Greatest Cities*. 2018.

26. Ebi KL, Vanos J, Baldwin JW, Bell JE, Hondula DM, Errett NA, et al. Extreme Weather and Climate Change: Population Health and Health System Implications. *Annu Rev Public Health*. 2021;42:293-315.
27. The American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. Addressing Climate Change: Position Statement 2021 [Available from: <https://www.acog.org/clinical-information/policy-and-position-statements/position-statements/2021/addressing-climate-change>].
28. World Health Organization. *Gender, Climate Change and Health*. Geneva, Switzerland; 2014.
29. Palmer KT, Bonzini M, Harris EC, Linaker C, Bonde JP. Work activities and risk of prematurity, low birth weight and preeclampsia: an updated review with meta-analysis. *Occup Environ Med*. 2013;70(4):213-22.
30. <BONELL~3.PDF>.
31. Bonell A, Sonko B, Badjie J, Samateh T, Saïdy T, Sosseh F, et al. Environmental heat stress on maternal physiology and fetal blood flow in pregnant subsistence farmers in The Gambia, west Africa: an observational cohort study. *The Lancet Planetary health*. 2022;6(12):e968-e76.
32. Cil G, Cameron T. Potential Climate Change Health Risks from Increases in Heat Waves: Abnormal Birth Outcomes and Adverse Maternal Health Conditions. *Risk analysis : an official publication of the Society for Risk Analysis*. 2017;37(11):2066-79.
33. Qu Y, Zhang W, Ryan I, Deng X, Dong G, Liu X, et al. Ambient extreme heat exposure in summer and transitional months and emergency department visits and hospital admissions due to pregnancy complications. *Sci Total Environ*. 2021;777:146134.
34. Part C, le Roux J, Chersich M, Sawry S, Filippi V, Roos N, et al. Ambient temperature during pregnancy and risk of maternal hypertensive disorders: A time-to-event study in Johannesburg, South Africa. *Environ Res*. 2022;212(Pt D):113596.
35. Gat R, Kachko E, Kloog I, Erez O, Yitshak-Sade M, Novack V, et al. Differences in environmental factors contributing to preterm labor and PPRM - Population based study. *Environ Res*. 2021;196:110894.
36. Rammah A, Whitworth K, Han I, Chan W, Hess J, Symanski E. Temperature, placental abruption and stillbirth. *Environ Int*. 2019;131:105067.
37. Frölich M, Esame A, Zhang K, Wu J, Owen J. What factors affect intrapartum maternal temperature? A prospective cohort study: maternal intrapartum temperature. *Anesthesiology*. 2012;117(2):302-8.
38. Haghighi MM, Wright CY, Ayer J, Urban MF, Pham MD, Boeckmann M, et al. Impacts of High Environmental Temperatures on Congenital Anomalies: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(9).
39. Dalugoda Y, Kuppa J, Phung H, Rutherford S, Phung D. Effect of Elevated Ambient Temperature on Maternal, Foetal, and Neonatal Outcomes: A Scoping Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022;19(3).
40. Hall ME, George EM, Granger JP. The heart during pregnancy. *Rev Esp Cardiol*. 2011;64(11):1045-50.
41. Samuels L, Nakstad B, Roos N, Bonell A, Chersich M, Havenith G, et al. Physiological mechanisms of the impact of heat during pregnancy and the clinical implications: review of the evidence from an expert group meeting. *International Journal of Biometeorology*. 2022;66:1-9.

42. W. SJ, Puhenthirar A, Casasola W, Inoue DS, Chaseling GK, Ravanelli N, et al. Thermoregulation During Pregnancy: a Controlled Trial Investigating the Risk of Maternal Hyperthermia During Exercise in the Heat. *Sports medicine (Auckland, NZ)*. 2021;51(12).
43. Dervis S, Dobson KL, Nagpal TS, Geurts C, Haman F, Adamo KB. Heat loss responses at rest and during exercise in pregnancy: A scoping review. *J Therm Biol*. 2021;99:103011.
44. Rekha S, Nalini SJ, Bhuvana S, Kanmani S, Vidhya V. A Comprehensive Review on Hot Ambient Temperature and its Impacts on Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes. *J Mother Child*. 2023;27(1):10-20.
45. Morton S, Kua J, Mullington C. Epidural analgesia, intrapartum hyperthermia, and neonatal brain injury: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2021;125(2):500-15.
46. Luton D, Alran S, Fourchette V, Sibony O, Oury J. Paris heat wave and oligohydramnios. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 2004;191(6):2103-5.
47. Kanninen T, Sisti G, Witkin S. Induction of the 70 kDa heat shock protein stress response inhibits autophagy: possible consequences for pregnancy outcome. *Journal of maternal-fetal & neonatal medicine*. 2016;29(1):159-62.
48. MacPhee D, Miskiewicz E. The Potential Functions of Small Heat Shock Proteins in the Uterine Musculature during Pregnancy. *Advances in anatomy, embryology, and cell biology* 2017;222:95-116.
49. Molina-Vega M, Gutiérrez-Repiso C, Muñoz-Garach A, Lima-Rubio F, Morcillo S, Tinahones F, et al. Relationship between environmental temperature and the diagnosis and treatment of gestational diabetes mellitus: An observational retrospective study. *Sci Total Environ*. 2020;744:140994.
50. Lin Y, Hu W, Xu J, Luo Z, Ye X, Yan C, et al. Association between temperature and maternal stress during pregnancy. *Environ Res*. 2017;158:421-30.
51. Khamis Y, Shaala S, Damarawy H, Romia A, Topozada M. Effect of heat on uterine contractions during normal labor. *International Journal of Gynaecology and Obstetrics the official organ of the International Federation of Gynaecology and Obstetrics*. 1983;21(6):491-3.
52. Morishima H, Glaser B, Niemann W, James L. Increased uterine activity and fetal deterioration during maternal hyperthermia. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 1975;121(4):531-8.
53. Wang J, Liu X, Dong M, Sun X, Xiao J, Zeng W, et al. Associations of maternal ambient temperature exposures during pregnancy with the placental weight, volume and PFR: A birth cohort study in Guangzhou, China. *Environ Int*. 2020;2020(139):105682.
54. Limesand S, Camacho L, Kelly A, Antolic A. Impact of thermal stress on placental function and fetal physiology *Animal Reproduction*. 2018;15(1):886-98.
55. Pirhonen J, Vähä-Eskeli K, Seppänen A, Vuorinen J, Erkkola R. Does thermal stress decrease uterine blood flow in hypertensive pregnancies? *American Journal of Perinatology*. 1994;11(5):313-6.
56. Bonell A, Sonko B, Badjie J, Samateh T, Saidy T, Sosseh F, et al. Environmental heat stress on maternal physiology and fetal blood flow in pregnant subsistence farmers in The Gambia, west Africa: an observational cohort study. *Lancet Planet Health*. 2022;6(12):e968-e76.

57. Bonell A, Part C, Okomo U, Cole R, Hajat S, Kovats S, et al. An expert review of environmental heat exposure and stillbirth in the face of climate change: Clinical implications and priority issues. *BJOG*. 2023.
58. Filippi V, Chou D, Barreix M, Say L, Group tWMMW. A new conceptual framework for maternal morbidity. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*. 2018;141(S1):4-9.
59. Randell H, Gray C, Grace K. Stunted from the start: Early life weather conditions and child undernutrition in Ethiopia. . *Social Science & Medicine*. 1982;261:113234.
60. Duchoslav J. Prenatal Temperature Shocks Reduce Cooperation: Evidence from Public Goods Games in Uganda. . *Frontiers in Behavioural Neuroscience*.11:249.
61. Chersich M, Kovats S, Part C, Samuels L, Hajat S, Solarin I. Systematic review of the effect of ambient heat on maternal health outcomes. In: 2021 ISfEEI, Conference 2021., editors. *International Society for Environmental Epidemiology*,2021.
62. Veenema RJ, Hoepner LA, Geer LA. Climate Change-Related Environmental Exposures and Perinatal and Maternal Health Outcomes in the U.S. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2023;20(3).
63. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Syst Rev*. 2021;10(1):89.
64. Albert Manyuchi Edgar., Ashtyn Areal., Bianca Wernecke., Barend Erasmus, Chongying Wang, Caradee Wright, et al. The impacts of heat on health and effectiveness of interventions to reduce these impacts: a systematic review in the era of climate change.: PROSEPRO; 2018 [Available from: https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospéro/display_record.php?ID=CRD42018118113].
65. Thomas J, Graziosi, S., Brunton, J., Ghouze, Z., O'Driscoll, P., & Bond, M. Koryakina A. EPPI-Reviewer: advanced software for systematic reviews, maps and evidence synthesis. EPPI-Centre, UCL Social Research Institute, University College London. 2022.
66. Campbell M, McKenzie JE, Sowden A, Katikireddi SV, Brennan SE, Ellis S, et al. Synthesis without meta-analysis (SWiM) in systematic reviews: reporting guideline. *BMJ*. 2020;368:l6890.
67. Higgins JPT, Thomas J CJ, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, (editors). *WV. Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions 2023*. Available from: www.training.cochrane.org/handbook.
68. Guyatt GH, Oxman AD, Kunz R, Vist GE, Falck-Ytter Y, Schünemann HJ. What is "quality of evidence" and why is it important to clinicians? *Bmj*. 2008;336(7651):995-8.
69. Mastrandrea MD, Field CB, Stocker TF, Edenhofer O, Ebi KL, Frame DJ, et al. Guidance Note for Lead Authors of the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report on Consistent Treatment of Uncertainties. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC); 2010.
70. Thorlund K, Imberger G, Johnston B, Walsh M, Awad T, Thabane L, et al. Evolution of heterogeneity (I²) estimates and their 95% confidence intervals in large meta-analyses. *PLoS one*. 2012;7(7).
71. Kachikis A, Eckert LO, Walker C, Oteng-Ntim E, Guggilla R, Gupta M, et al. Gestational diabetes mellitus: Case definition & guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine*. 2017;35(48 Pt A):6555-62.

72. Zhang H, Wang Q, Benmarhnia T, Jalaludin B, Shen X, Yu Z, et al. Assessing the effects of non-optimal temperature on risk of gestational diabetes mellitus in a cohort of pregnant women in Guangzhou, China. *Environ Int.* 2021;152:106457.
73. Su WL, Lu CL, Martini S, Hsu YH, Li CY. A population-based study on the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus in association with temperature in Taiwan. *Sci Total Environ.* 2020;714:136747.
74. Molina-Vega M, Gutierrez-Repiso C, Munoz-Garach A, Lima-Rubio F, Morcillo S, Tinahones FJ, et al. Relationship between environmental temperature and the diagnosis and treatment of gestational diabetes mellitus: An observational retrospective study. *Sci Total Environ.* 2020;744:140994.
75. Katsarou A, Claesson R, Ignell C, Shaat N, Berntorp K. Seasonal Pattern in the Diagnosis of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus in Southern Sweden. *J Diabetes Res.* 2016;2016:8905474.
76. Booth GL, Luo J, Park AL, Feig DS, Moineddin R, Ray JG. Influence of environmental temperature on risk of gestational diabetes. *CMAJ.* 2017;189(19):E682-E9.
77. Retnakaran R, Ye C, Kramer CK, Hanley AJ, Connelly PW, Sermer M, et al. Impact of daily incremental change in environmental temperature on beta cell function and the risk of gestational diabetes in pregnant women. *Diabetologia.* 2018;61(12):2633-42.
78. Qu Y, Zhang W, Ryan I, Deng X, Dong G, Liu X, et al. Ambient extreme heat exposure in summer and transitional months and emergency department visits and hospital admissions due to pregnancy complications. *Sci Total Environ.* 2021;777:146134.
79. Shen EX, Moses RG, Oats JJN, Lowe J, McIntyre HD. Seasonality, temperature and pregnancy oral glucose tolerance test results in Australia. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2019;19(1):263.
80. Teyton A, Sun Y, Molitor J, Chen JC, Sacks D, Avila C, et al. Examining the Relationship Between Extreme Temperature, Microclimate Indicators, and Gestational Diabetes Mellitus in Pregnant Women Living in Southern California. *Environ Epidemiol.* 2023;7(3):e252.
81. Dieckmann WJ. The geographic distribution and effect of climate on eclampsia, toxemia of pregnancy, hyperemesis gravidarum, and abruptio placentae. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology.* 1938;36(4):623-31.
82. Xiong T, Chen P, Mu Y, Li X, Di B, Li J, et al. Association between ambient temperature and hypertensive disorders in pregnancy in China. *Nat Commun.* 2020;11(1):2925.
83. Tran TC, Boumendil A, Bussieres L, Lebreton E, Ropers J, Rozenberg P, et al. Are Meteorological Conditions within the First Trimester of Pregnancy Associated with the Risk of Severe Preeclampsia? *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol.* 2015;29(4):261-70.
84. Nasiri R, Ahmadi Shadmehri A, Khajeh Ghiassi P, Sarafraz Yazdi M, Mazloum Farsi Baf M. Association of meteorological factors and seasonality with preeclampsia: a 5-year study in northeast of Iran. *Clin Exp Hypertens.* 2014;36(8):586-9.
85. Auger N, Siemiatycki J, Bilodeau-Bertrand M, Healy-Profitos J, Kosatsky T. Ambient Temperature and Risk of Preeclampsia: Biased Association? *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol.* 2017;31(4):267-71.
86. Shashar S, Kloog I, Erez O, Shtein A, Yitshak-Sade M, Sarov B, et al. Temperature and preeclampsia: Epidemiological evidence that perturbation in maternal heat homeostasis affects pregnancy outcome. *PLoS One.* 2020;15(5):e0232877.

87. Tam WH, Sahota DS, Lau TK, Li CY, Fung TY. Seasonal variation in pre-eclamptic rate and its association with the ambient temperature and humidity in early pregnancy. *Gynecol Obstet Invest.* 2008;66(1):22-6.
88. Algert CS, Roberts CL, Shand AW, Morris JM, Ford JB. Seasonal variation in pregnancy hypertension is correlated with sunlight intensity. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2010;203(3):215 e1-5.
89. Cil G, Cameron TA. Potential Climate Change Health Risks from Increases in Heat Waves: Abnormal Birth Outcomes and Adverse Maternal Health Conditions. *Risk Anal.* 2017;37(11):2066-79.
90. Agobe JT, Good W, Hancock KW. Meteorological relations of eclampsia in Lagos, Nigeria. *Br J Obstet Gynaecol.* 1981;88(7):706-10.
91. Neela J, Raman L. Seasonal trends in the occurrence of eclampsia. *Natl Med J India.* 1993;6(1):17-8.
92. Hampel R, Lepeule J, Schneider A, Bottagisi S, Charles MA, Ducimetière P, et al. Short-term impact of ambient air pollution and air temperature on blood pressure among pregnant women. *Epidemiology.* 2011;22(5):671-9.
93. Metoki H, Ohkubo T, Watanabe Y, Nishimura M, Sato Y, Kawaguchi M, et al. Seasonal trends of blood pressure during pregnancy in Japan: the babies and their parents' longitudinal observation in Suzuki Memorial Hospital in Intrauterine Period study. *J Hypertens.* 2008;26(12):2406-13.
94. Immink A, Scherjon S, Wolterbeek R, Steyn DW. Seasonal influence on the admittance of preeclampsia patients in Tygerberg Hospital. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand.* 2008;87(1):36-42.
95. Melo B, Amorim M, Katz L, Coutinho I, Figueiroa JN. Hypertension, pregnancy and weather: is seasonality involved? *Rev Assoc Med Bras (1992).* 2014;60(2):105-10.
96. Kim J, Lee A, Rossin-Slater M. What to Expect When it Gets Hotter: The Impacts of Prenatal Exposure to Extreme Temperature on Maternal Health. *American Journal of Health Economics.* 2021;7(3):249-360.
97. Zhao Q, Li S, Coelho M, Saldiva PHN, Hu K, Abramson MJ, et al. Assessment of Intraseasonal Variation in Hospitalization Associated With Heat Exposure in Brazil. *JAMA network open.* 2019;2(2):e187901.
98. Zhao Q, Li S, Coelho M, Saldiva PHN, Hu K, Huxley RR, et al. The association between heatwaves and risk of hospitalization in Brazil: A nationwide time series study between 2000 and 2015. *PLoS medicine.* 2019;16(2):e1002753.
99. Davis RE, Novicoff WM. The Impact of Heat Waves on Emergency Department Admissions in Charlottesville, Virginia, U.S.A. *International journal of environmental research and public health.* 2018;15(7).
100. Dadvand P, Basagana X, Figueras F, Sunyer J, Nieuwenhuijsen MJ. Climate and group B streptococci colonisation during pregnancy: present implications and future concerns. *Bjog.* 2011;118(11):1396-400.
101. Minisha F, Mohamed M, Abdulmunem D, El Awad S, Zidan M, Abreo M, et al. Bacteriuria in pregnancy varies with the ambiance: a retrospective observational study at a tertiary hospital in Doha, Qatar. *J Perinat Med.* 2019;48(1):46-52.
102. Busowski JD, Chez RA. Climatic factors and the incidence of pyelonephritis during pregnancy. *Infect Dis Obstet Gynecol.* 1995;3(6):226-8.

103. Harrison MS, Eckert LO, Cutland C, Gravett M, Harper DM, McClure EM, et al. Pathways to preterm birth: Case definition and guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine*. 2016;34(49):6093-101.
104. Song J, Lu J, Wang E, Lu M, An Z, Liu Y, et al. Short-term effects of ambient temperature on the risk of premature rupture of membranes in Xinxiang, China: A time-series analysis. *Sci Total Environ*. 2019;689:1329-35.
105. Yang D, Chen L, Yang Y, Shi J, Xu J, Li C, et al. Influence of ambient temperature and diurnal temperature variation on the premature rupture of membranes in East China: A distributed lag nonlinear time series analysis. *Environ Res*. 2021;202:111145.
106. Yackerson N, Piura B, Sheiner E. The influence of meteorological factors on the emergence of preterm delivery and preterm premature rupture of membrane. *J Perinatol*. 2008;28(10):707-11.
107. Ha S, Liu D, Zhu Y, Sherman S, Mendola P. Acute Associations Between Outdoor Temperature and Premature Rupture of Membranes. *Epidemiology*. 2018;29(2):175-82.
108. Gat R, Kachko E, Kloog I, Erez O, Yitshak-Sade M, Novack V, et al. Differences in environmental factors contributing to preterm labor and PPRM - Population based study. *Environ Res*. 2021;196:110894.
109. Lin Y, Hu W, Xu J, Luo Z, Ye X, Yan C, et al. Association between temperature and maternal stress during pregnancy. *Environmental research*. 2017;158.
110. Prabhu M, Eckert LO, Belfort M, Babarinsa I, Ananth CV, Silver RM, et al. Antenatal bleeding: Case definition and guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine*. 2017;35(48 Pt A):6529-37.
111. Bider D, Sivan E, Seidman DS, Dulitzky M, Mashiach S, Serr DM, et al. Meteorological factors in hypertensive disorders, vaginal bleeding and premature rupture of membranes during pregnancy. *Gynecol Obstet Invest*. 1991;32(2):88-90.
112. Rammah A, Whitworth KW, Han I, Chan W, Hess JW, Symanski E. Temperature, placental abruption and stillbirth. *Environment international*. 2019;131.
113. He S, Kosatsky T, Smargiassi A, Bilodeau-Bertrand M, Auger N. Heat and pregnancy-related emergencies: Risk of placental abruption during hot weather. *Environment international*. 2018;111.
114. Cil G, Cameron TA. Potential Climate Change Health Risks from Increases in Heat Waves: Abnormal Birth Outcomes and Adverse Maternal Health Conditions. *Risk Analysis*. 2017;37(11):2066-79.
115. Molina S. The Perils of Climate Change: In Utero Exposure to Temperature Variability and Birth Outcomes in the Andean Region. 2017.
116. Ha S, Nguyen K, Liu D, Männistö T, Nobles C, Sherman S, et al. Ambient temperature and risk of cardiovascular events at labor and delivery: A case-crossover study. *Environmental research*. 2017;159.
117. Ranjbaran M, Mohammadi R, Yaseri M, Kamari M, Habibelahi A, Yazdani K. Effect of ambient air pollution and temperature on the risk of stillbirth: a distributed lag nonlinear time series analysis. *J Environ Health Sci Eng*. 2020;18(2):1289-99.
118. Strand L, Barnett A, Tong S. Maternal exposure to ambient temperature and the risks of preterm birth and stillbirth in Brisbane, Australia. *American journal of epidemiology*. 2012;175(2).
119. Ha S, Liu D, Zhu Y, Kim SS, Sherman S, Grantz KL, et al. Ambient Temperature and Stillbirth: A Multi-Center Retrospective Cohort Study. 2017.

120. Khodadadi N, Dastoorpoor M, Khanjani N, Ghasemi A. Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) and adverse pregnancy outcomes in Ahvaz, Iran. *Reproductive health*. 2022;19(1).
121. Li S, Chen G, Jaakkola J, Williams G, Guo Y. Temporal change in the impacts of ambient temperature on preterm birth and stillbirth: Brisbane, 1994-2013. *The Science of the total environment*. 2018;634.
122. McElroy S, Ilango S, Dimitrova A, Gershunov A, Benmarhnia T. Extreme heat, preterm birth, and stillbirth: A global analysis across 14 lower-middle income countries. *Environment international*. 2022;158:106902.
123. Savitz DA, Hu H. Ambient heat and stillbirth in Northern and Central Florida. *Environ Res*. 2021;199:111262.
124. Asamoah BK, T; Östergren, PO;. Is ambient heat exposure levels associated with miscarriage or stillbirths in hot regions? A cross-sectional study using survey data from the Ghana Maternal Health Survey 2007. *International Journal of Biometeorology*. 2023;62(3):319-30.
125. Basu R, Sarovar V, Malig B. Association Between High Ambient Temperature and Risk of Stillbirth in California. *American journal of epidemiology*. 2016;183(10).
126. Kanner J, Williams A, Nobles C, Ha S, Ouidir M, Sherman S, et al. Ambient temperature and stillbirth: Risks associated with chronic extreme temperature and acute temperature change. *Environmental research*. 2020;189.
127. Richards M, Huang M, Strickland MJ, Newman AJ, Warren JL, D'Souza R, et al. Acute association between heatwaves and stillbirth in six US states. *Environmental health : a global access science source*. 2022;21(1):59.
128. Ranjbaran M, Mohammadi R, Yaseri M, Kamari M, Habibelahi A, Yazdani K. Effect of ambient air pollution and temperature on the risk of stillbirth: a distributed lag nonlinear time series analysis. *Journal of environmental health science & engineering*. 2020;18(2).
129. Rouse CE, Eckert LO, Babarinsa I, Fay E, Gupta M, Harrison MS, et al. Spontaneous abortion and ectopic pregnancy: Case definition & guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of maternal immunization safety data. *Vaccine*. 2017;35(48 Pt A):6563-74.
130. Khodadadi N, Dastoorpoor M, Khanjani N, Ghasemi A. Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) and adverse pregnancy outcomes in Ahvaz, Iran. *Reprod Health*. 2022;19(1):33.
131. Dastoorpoor M, Khanjani N, Khodadadi N. Association between Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET) with adverse pregnancy outcomes in Ahvaz, southwest of Iran. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2021;21(1):415.
132. Sun X, Luo X, Cao G, Zhao C, Xiao J, Liu X, et al. Associations of ambient temperature exposure during pregnancy with the risk of miscarriage and the modification effects of greenness in Guangdong, China. *Sci Total Environ*. 2020;702:134988.
133. Bianchi-Demicheli F, Lüdicke F, Spinedi F, Major AL, Kulier R, Campana A, et al. Association between weather conditions and the incidence of emergency gynecological consultations. *Gynecologic and obstetric investigation*. 2001;51(1).
134. Bogan M, Al B, Kul S, Zengin S, Oktay M, Sabak M, et al. The effects of desert dust storms, air pollution, and temperature on morbidity due to spontaneous abortions and toxemia of pregnancy: 5-year analysis. *Int J Biometeorol*. 2021;65(10):1733-9.

135. Zhao S, Xu J, Li W, Lu Y, Huang L, Xu H, et al. High-temperature exposure and risk of spontaneous abortion during early pregnancy: a case-control study in Nanjing, China. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*. 2023;30(11):29807-13.
136. DeSilva M, Munoz FM, McMillan M, Kawai AT, Marshall H, Macartney KK, et al. Congenital anomalies: Case definition and guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine*. 2016;34(49):6015-26.
137. Zhang Y, Sun F, Yuan K, Du Y, Wu L, Ge Y, et al. Ambient temperature and major structural anomalies: A retrospective study of over 2 million newborns. *Sci Total Environ*. 2023;882:163613.
138. Davies BR. The seasonal conception of lethal congenital malformations. *Archives of medical research*. 2000;31(6):589-91.
139. Van Zutphen AR, Lin S, Fletcher BA, Hwang SA. A population-based case-control study of extreme summer temperature and birth defects. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2012;120(10):1443-9.
140. Auger N, Siemiatycki J, Bilodeau-Bertrand M, Healy-Profitos J, Kosatsky T. Ambient Temperature and Risk of Preeclampsia: Biased Association? *Paediatric and Perinatal Epidemiology*. 2017;31(4):267-71.
141. Xu W, Li D, Shao Z, You Y, Pan F, Lou H, et al. The prenatal weekly temperature exposure and neonatal congenital heart disease: a large population-based observational study in China. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*. 2023;30(13):38282-91.
142. Tikkanen J, Heinonen OP. Maternal hyperthermia during pregnancy and cardiovascular malformations in the offspring. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 1991;7(6):628-35.
143. Sciscione AC, Costigan KA, Johnson TR. Increase in ambient temperature may explain decrease in amniotic fluid index. *Am J Perinatol*. 1997;14(5):249-51.
144. Luton D, Alran S, Fourchette V, Sibony O, Oury JF. Paris heat wave and oligohydramnios. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2004;191(6):2103-5.
145. Gravett C, Eckert LO, Gravett MG, Dudley DJ, Stringer EM, Mujobu TB, et al. Non-reassuring fetal status: Case definition & guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine*. 2016;34(49):6084-92.
146. Yüzen D, Graf I, Tallarek AC, Hollwitz B, Wiessner C, Schleussner E, et al. Increased late preterm birth risk and altered uterine blood flow upon exposure to heat stress. *EBioMedicine*. 2023;93:104651.
147. Bonell A, Vannevel V, Sonko B, Mohammed N, Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Haines A, et al. A feasibility study of the use of UmbiFlow™ to assess the impact of heat stress on fetoplacental blood flow in field studies. *International journal of gynaecology and obstetrics: the official organ of the International Federation of Gynaecology and Obstetrics*. 2022.
148. Shankar K, Ali SA, Ruebel ML, Jessani S, Borengasser SJ, Gilley SP, et al. Maternal nutritional status modifies heat-associated growth restriction in women with chronic malnutrition. *PNAS Nexus*. 2023;2(1):pgac309.
149. Leung M, Laden F, Coull BA, Modest AM, Hacker MR, Wylie BJ, et al. Ambient temperature during pregnancy and fetal growth in Eastern Massachusetts, USA. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2023;52(3):749-60.
150. Bonell A, Vannevel V, Sonko B, Mohammed N, Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Haines A, et al. A feasibility study of the use of UmbiFlow™ to assess the impact of heat stress on fetoplacental blood flow in field studies. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*. 2023;160(2):430-6.

151. Basagaña X, Sartini C, Barrera-Gómez J, Dadvand P, Cunillera J, Ostro B, et al. Heat waves and cause-specific mortality at all ages. *Epidemiology*. 2011;22(6):765-72.
152. Schumann B, Häggström Lundevaller E, Karlsson L. Weather extremes and perinatal mortality - Seasonal and ethnic differences in northern Sweden, 1800-1895. *PLoS One*. 2019;14(10):e0223538.
153. Wang J, Liu X, Dong M, Sun X, Xiao J, Zeng W, et al. Associations of maternal ambient temperature exposures during pregnancy with the placental weight, volume and PFR: A birth cohort study in Guangzhou, China. *Environ Int*. 2020;139:105682.
154. Asamoah B, Kjellstrom T, Östergren P. Is ambient heat exposure levels associated with miscarriage or stillbirths in hot regions? A cross-sectional study using survey data from the Ghana Maternal Health Survey 2007. *International Journal of Biometeorology*. 2023;62(3):319-30.
155. Quinn JA, Munoz FM, Gonik B, Frau L, Cutland C, Mallett-Moore T, et al. Preterm birth: Case definition & guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunisation safety data. *Vaccine*. 2016;34(49):6047-56.
156. Barreca A, Schaller J. The impact of high ambient temperatures on delivery timing and gestational lengths. *Nature Climate Change*. 2019;10(1):77-82.
157. Wang YY, Li Q, Guo Y, Zhou H, Wang QM, Shen HP, et al. Ambient temperature and the risk of preterm birth: A national birth cohort study in the mainland China. *Environ Int*. 2020;142:105851.
158. Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Olsson D, Forsberg B. Exposure to Seasonal Temperatures during the Last Month of Gestation and the Risk of Preterm Birth in Stockholm. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2015;12(4):3962-78.
159. Basu R, Malig B, Ostro B. High ambient temperature and the risk of preterm delivery. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2010;172(10):1108-17.
160. Schifano P, Lallo A, Asta F, De Sario M, Davoli M, Michelozzi P. Effect of ambient temperature and air pollutants on the risk of preterm birth, Rome 2001-2010. *Environ Int*. 2013;61:77-87.
161. Mohammadi D, Naghshineh E, Sarsangi A, Zare Sakhvidi MJ. Environmental extreme temperature and daily preterm birth in Sabzevar, Iran: a time-series analysis. *Environ Health Prev Med*. 2019;24(1):5.
162. Wang J, Tong S, Williams G, Pan X. Exposure to Heat Wave During Pregnancy and Adverse Birth Outcomes: An Exploration of Susceptible Windows. *Epidemiology*. 2019;30:S115-S21.
163. Tapia VL, Vasquez-Apestegui BV, Alcantara-Zapata D, Vu B, Steenland K, Gonzales GF. Association between maximum temperature and PM(2.5) with pregnancy outcomes in Lima, Peru. *Environ Epidemiol*. 2021;5(6):e179.
164. Zheng X, Zhang W, Lu C, Norbäck D, Deng Q. An epidemiological assessment of the effect of ambient temperature on the incidence of preterm births: Identifying windows of susceptibility during pregnancy. *J Therm Biol*. 2018;74:201-7.
165. Giorgis-Allemand L, Pedersen M, Bernard C, Aguilera I, Beelen RM, Chatzi L, et al. The Influence of Meteorological Factors and Atmospheric Pollutants on the Risk of Preterm Birth. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2017;185(4):247-58.
166. Liu X, Xiao J, Sun X, Chen Q, Yao Z, Feng B, et al. Associations of maternal ambient temperature exposures during pregnancy with the risk of preterm birth and the effect

- modification of birth order during the new baby boom: A birth cohort study in Guangzhou, China. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2020;225:113481.
167. Dadvand P, Basagaña X, Sartini C, Figueras F, Vrijheid M, de Nazelle A, et al. Climate extremes and the length of gestation. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2011;119(10):1449-53.
168. Wang Q, Yin L, Wu H, Ren Z, He S, Huang A, et al. Effects of gestational ambient extreme temperature exposures on the risk of preterm birth in China: A sibling-matched study based on a multi-center prospective cohort. *Sci Total Environ*. 2023;887:164135.
169. Wang J, Williams G, Guo Y, Pan X, Tong S. Maternal exposure to heatwave and preterm birth in Brisbane, Australia. *BJOG : an international journal of obstetrics and gynaecology*. 2013;120(13):1631-41.
170. Kent ST, McClure LA, Zaitchik BF, Smith TT, Gohlke JM. Heat waves and health outcomes in Alabama (USA): the importance of heat wave definition. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2014;122(2):151-8.
171. Bruckner TA, Modin B, Vågerö D. Cold ambient temperature in utero and birth outcomes in Uppsala, Sweden, 1915-1929. *Ann Epidemiol*. 2014;24(2):116-21.
172. Weng YH, Yang CY, Chiu YW. Adverse neonatal outcomes in relation to ambient temperatures at birth: A nationwide survey in Taiwan. *Archives of environmental & occupational health*. 2018;73(1):48-55.
173. Wu M, Song L, Zheng X, Zhang L, Liu B, Wang L, et al. Prenatal exposure of diurnal temperature range and preterm birth: Findings from a birth cohort study in China. *Sci Total Environ*. 2019;656:1102-7.
174. Walfisch A, Kabakov E, Friger M, Sheiner E. Trends, seasonality and effect of ambient temperature on preterm delivery. 2016.
175. Cox B, Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Gasparrini A, Roels HA, Martens E, Vangronsveld J, et al. Ambient temperature as a trigger of preterm delivery in a temperate climate. *J Epidemiol Community Health*. 2016;70(12):1191-9.
176. Yu X, Feric Z, Cordero JF, Meeker JD, Alshawabkeh A. Potential influence of temperature and precipitation on preterm birth rate in Puerto Rico. *Sci Rep*. 2018;8(1):16106.
177. Guo T, Wang Y, Zhang H, Zhang Y, Zhao J, Wang Y, et al. The association between ambient temperature and the risk of preterm birth in China. *Sci Total Environ*. 2018;613-614:439-46.
178. Nyadanu SD, Tessema GA, Mullins B, Pereira G. Prenatal acute thermophysiological stress and spontaneous preterm birth in Western Australia, 2000-2015: A space-time-stratified case-crossover analysis. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*. 2022;245:114029.
179. Avalos LA, Chen H, Li DK, Basu R. The impact of high apparent temperature on spontaneous preterm delivery: a case-crossover study. *Environ Health*. 2017;16(1):5.
180. Liang Z, Lin Y, Ma Y, Zhang L, Zhang X, Li L, et al. The association between ambient temperature and preterm birth in Shenzhen, China: a distributed lag non-linear time series analysis. *Environ Health*. 2016;15(1):84.
181. Li C, Bloom MS, Lin S, Ren M, Hajat S, Wang Q, et al. Temperature variation and preterm birth among live singleton deliveries in Shenzhen, China: A time-to-event analysis. *Environ Res*. 2021;195:110834.
182. Porter KR, Thomas SD, Whitman S. The relation of gestation length to short-term heat stress. *Am J Public Health*. 1999;89(7):1090-2.

183. Lee SJ, Hajat S, Steer PJ, Filippi V. A time-series analysis of any short-term effects of meteorological and air pollution factors on preterm births in London, UK. *Environ Res.* 2008;106(2):185-94.
184. de Bont J, Stafoggia M, Nakstad B, Hajat S, Kovats S, Part C, et al. Associations between ambient temperature and risk of preterm birth in Sweden: A comparison of analytical approaches. *Environ Res.* 2022;213:113586.
185. Cil G, Kim J. Extreme temperatures during pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes: Evidence from 2009 to 2018 U.S. national birth data. *Health Econ.* 2022;31(9):1993-2024.
186. Zhang Y, Hajat S, Zhao L, Chen H, Cheng L, Ren M, et al. The burden of heatwave-related preterm births and associated human capital losses in China. *Nature communications.* 2022;13(1):7565.
187. Sun S, Spangler KR, Weinberger KR, Yanosky JD, Braun JM, Wellenius GA. Ambient Temperature and Markers of Fetal Growth: A Retrospective Observational Study of 29 Million U.S. Singleton Births. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2019;127(6):67005.
188. Bakhtsiyarava M, Ortigoza A, Sánchez BN, Braverman-Bronstein A, Kephart JL, Rodríguez López S, et al. Ambient temperature and term birthweight in Latin American cities. *Environ Int.* 2022;167:107412.
189. Andalón M, Azevedo JP, Rodríguez-Castelán C, Sanfelice V, Valderrama-González D. Weather Shocks and Health at Birth in Colombia. *World Development.* 2016;82:69-82.
190. Molina O, Saldarriaga V. The perils of climate change: In utero exposure to temperature variability and birth outcomes in the Andean region. *Economics & Human Biology.* 2017;24(C):111-24.
191. Lawlor DA, Leon DA, Davey Smith G. The association of ambient outdoor temperature throughout pregnancy and offspring birthweight: findings from the Aberdeen Children of the 1950s cohort. *Bjog.* 2005;112(5):647-57.
192. Lawrence WR, Soim A, Zhang W, Lin Z, Lu Y, Lipton EA, et al. A population-based case-control study of the association between weather-related extreme heat events and low birthweight. *J Dev Orig Health Dis.* 2021;12(2):335-42.
193. Poeran J, Birnie E, Steegers EA, Bonsel GJ. The Impact of Extremes in Outdoor Temperature and Sunshine Exposure on Birth Weight. *J Environ Health.* 2016;78(6):92-100.
194. Requia WJ, Koutrakis P, Papatheodorou S. The association of maternal exposure to ambient temperature with low birth weight in term pregnancies varies by location: In Brazil, positive associations may occur only in the Amazon region. *Environ Res.* 2022;214(Pt 2):113923.
195. Zhang JX, Yang M, Ji PH, Li QY, Chai J, Sun PP, et al. The Association between Outdoor Ambient Temperature and the Risk of Low Birth Weight: A Population-Based Cohort Study in Rural Henan, China. *Biomed Environ Sci.* 2021;34(11):905-9.
196. Basagaña X, Michael Y, Lensky IM, Rubin L, Grotto I, Vadislavsky E, et al. Low and High Ambient Temperatures during Pregnancy and Birth Weight among 624,940 Singleton Term Births in Israel (2010-2014): An Investigation of Potential Windows of Susceptibility. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2021;129(10):107001.
197. Ha S, Zhu Y, Liu D, Sherman S, Mendola P. Ambient temperature and air quality in relation to small for gestational age and term low birthweight. *Environ Res.* 2017;155:394-400.

198. Kloog I, Melly SJ, Coull BA, Nordio F, Schwartz JD. Using Satellite-Based Spatiotemporal Resolved Air Temperature Exposure to Study the Association between Ambient Air Temperature and Birth Outcomes in Massachusetts. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2015;123(10):1053-8.
199. Yitshak-Sade M, Novack L, Landau D, Kloog I, Sarov B, Hershkovitz R, et al. Relationship of ambient air pollutants and hazardous household factors with birth weight among Bedouin-Arabs. *Chemosphere.* 2016;160:314-22.
200. Chodick G, Shalev V, Goren I, Inskip PD. Seasonality in birth weight in Israel: new evidence suggests several global patterns and different etiologies. *Ann Epidemiol.* 2007;17(6):440-6.
201. Jakpor O, Chevrier C, Kloog I, Benmerad M, Giorgis-Allemand L, Cordier S, et al. Term birthweight and critical windows of prenatal exposure to average meteorological conditions and meteorological variability. *Environ Int.* 2020;142:105847.
202. Carlson JM, Zanobetti A, Ettinger de Cuba S, Poblacion AP, Fabian PM, Carnes F, et al. Critical windows of susceptibility for the effects of prenatal exposure to heat and heat variability on gestational growth. *Environ Res.* 2023;216(Pt 2):114607.
203. Yitshak-Sade M, Kloog I, Schwartz JD, Novack V, Erez O, Just AC. The effect of prenatal temperature and PM(2.5) exposure on birthweight: Weekly windows of exposure throughout the pregnancy. *Environ Int.* 2021;155:106588.
204. Murray LJ, O'Reilly DP, Betts N, Patterson CC, Davey Smith G, Evans AE. Season and outdoor ambient temperature: effects on birth weight. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2000;96(5 Pt 1):689-95.
205. Schlaudecker EP, Munoz FM, Bardaji A, Boghossian NS, Khalil A, Mousa H, et al. Small for gestational age: Case definition & guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of maternal immunisation safety data. *Vaccine.* 2017;35(48 Pt A):6518-28.
206. Li X, Ma J, Cheng Y, Feng L, Wang S, Dong G. The relationship between extreme ambient temperature and small for gestational age: A cohort study of 1,436,480 singleton term births in China. *Environ Res.* 2023;232:116412.
207. Sun S, Spangler KR, Weinberger KR, Yanosky JD, Braun JM, Wellenius GA. Ambient Temperature and Markers of Fetal Growth: A Retrospective Observational Study of 29 Million US Singleton Births. *Environmental health perspectives.* 2019;127(6):067005.
208. Kloog I, Novack L, Erez O, Just AC, Raz R. Associations between ambient air temperature, low birth weight and small for gestational age in term neonates in southern Israel. *Environ Health.* 2018;17(1):76.
209. Kakkad K, Barzaga ML, Wallenstein S, Azhar GS, Sheffield PE. Neonates in Ahmedabad, India, during the 2010 heat wave: a climate change adaptation study. *J Environ Public Health.* 2014;2014:946875.
210. Tang Z, Wu M, Song G, Yang R, Wang Y. Impact of ambient temperature exposure on newborns with low Apgar scores in northwest China. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int.* 2021;28(27):36367-74.
211. Chen F, Liu M, Yang C, Hao X, Chen Z. Effect on the health of newborns caused by extreme temperature in Guangzhou. *Journal of environmental management.* 2022;311:114842.
212. Iijima S, Baba T, Kondo M, Fujita T, Ohishi A. Effects of Season of Birth and Meteorological Parameters on Serum Bilirubin Levels during the Early Neonatal Period: A Retrospective Chart Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021;18(5).

213. Scrafford CG, Mullany LC, Katz J, Khattry SK, LeClerq SC, Darmstadt GL, et al. Incidence of and risk factors for neonatal jaundice among newborns in southern Nepal. *Trop Med Int Health*. 2013;18(11):1317-28.
214. Weng Y, Yang C, Chiu Y. Adverse neonatal outcomes in relation to ambient temperatures at birth: A nationwide survey in Taiwan. *Archives of environmental & occupational health*. 2018;73(1).
215. World Health Organization. Maternal mortality 2019 [Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/maternal-mortality>].
216. Sexton J, Andrews C, Carruthers S, Kumar S, Flenady V, Lieske S. Systematic review of ambient temperature exposure during pregnancy and stillbirth: Methods and evidence. *Environ Res*. 2021;197:111037.
217. He JR, Liu Y, Xia XY, Ma WJ, Lin HL, Kan HD, et al. Ambient Temperature and the Risk of Preterm Birth in Guangzhou, China (2001-2011). *Environ Health Perspect*. 2016;124(7):1100-6.
218. Basu R, Rau R, Pearson D, Malig B. Temperature and Term Low Birth Weight in California. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2018;187(11):2306-14.

7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix A: Search on MEDLINE (PubMed) and Web of Science

7.1.1 PubMed search

Search covers terms for:

1. The **population** (those affected by heat: no 1 below) AND
2. **Intervention** (No. 2a: climate change OR 2b Media OR 2c cooling OR 2d Health promotion)
3. **NOT 3** (genetics)

1. Search for the Population (those with heat-related conditions)

((("ambient temperature"[title/abstract] OR "heat strain"[title/abstract] OR "heat exposure"[title/abstract] OR "heat stress"[title/abstract] OR Heating[mesh] OR "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH] OR "hot temperature*" [title/abstract] OR "extreme heat"[MESH] OR "Heat stroke"[MESH] OR "heatstroke"[title/abstract] OR "heat index"[title/abstract] OR "heat episode"[title/abstract] OR "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH] OR "heat event"[title/abstract] OR "Body temperature"[Mesh:noexp] OR "extreme temperature*" [title/abstract] OR "summer temperature*" [title/abstract] OR "Heat Exhaustion"[mesh] OR "summer weather"[title/abstract] OR "summer

temperature*[title/abstract] OR "heat wave"[title/abstract] OR
"heatwave"[title/abstract] OR "indoor temperature"[title/abstract] OR "global
temperature*[title/abstract])) NOT (((("Animals"[Mesh] NOT ("Animals"[Mesh] AND
"Humans"[Mesh]))) NOT ("Chemicals and Drugs Category"[MeSH]) NOT
(((("Plants"[Mesh] NOT ("Plants"[Mesh] AND "Humans"[Mesh])))))

AND

2. Search strategy for interventions

a. locating Climate change articles in PubMed

((("global warming"[Title/Abstract] OR "global warming"[MESH] OR
climatic*[Title/Abstract] OR "climate change"[Title/Abstract] OR "climate change"[MESH]
OR "Desert Climate"[mesh] OR "El Nino-Southern Oscillation"[Mesh] OR
Microclimate[mesh] OR "Tropical Climate"[mesh]))

b. Search for media (a validated search for social media)

media[title/abstract] OR communication*[title/abstract] OR audiovisual[title/abstract]
OR helpline*[title/abstract] OR hotline*[title/abstract] OR
telecommunication*[title/abstract] OR educat*[title/abstract] OR radio[title/abstract] OR
television[title/abstract] OR TV[title/abstract] OR internet[title/abstract] OR
campaign*[title/abstract] OR advert*[title/abstract] OR print*[title/abstract] OR
"information campaign"[title/abstract] OR telemedicine[title/abstract] OR
telehealth[title/abstract] OR telepharmac* OR e-health[title/abstract] OR
ehealth[title/abstract] OR e-pharmac*[title/abstract] OR "social media"[mesh] OR "social
media"[title/abstract] OR "social network*[title/abstract] OR Twitter[title/abstract] OR
Facebook[title/abstract] OR LinkedIn[title/abstract] OR Pinterest[title/abstract] OR
YouTube[title/abstract] OR "daily motion"[title/abstract] OR Yelp[title/abstract] OR
Foursquare[title/abstract] OR "Google Circles"[title/abstract] OR Qype[title/abstract] OR
Ello[title/abstract] OR Instagram[title/abstract] OR "Pip.io"[title/abstract] OR "Google
Buzz"[title/abstract] OR Orkut[title/abstract] OR Tumblr[title/abstract] OR
onesocialweb[title/abstract] OR asmallworld[title/abstract] OR bebo[title/abstract] OR
myspace[title/abstract] OR folkdirect[title/abstract] OR virb[title/abstract] OR
Friendster[title/abstract] OR storyofmylife[title/abstract]

c. Search for cooling

cooling[title/abstract] OR "Air condition*[title/abstract] OR "Air-
condition*[title/abstract] OR climatization[title/abstract] OR climatization[title/abstract]
OR ventilation[title/abstract] OR Fan[title/abstract] OR fans[title/abstract]

d. Search for health promotion and risk

adaptation[title/abstract] OR adapting[title/abstract] OR response[title/abstract] OR
alert[title/abstract] OR implement*[title/abstract] OR awareness[title/abstract] OR
strategy*[title/abstract] OR strategies[title/abstract] OR "risk
management"[title/abstract] OR "risk management"[mesh] OR "emergency
management"[title/abstract] OR "preparedness"[title/abstract] OR "disaster
management"[title/abstract] OR warning*[title/abstract] OR "health promotion"[MeSH]

OR "Health education"[MeSH] OR "communication campaign*"[Title/abstract] OR guideline*[Title/Abstract] OR recommendation*[Title/Abstract] OR "Health Services for the Aged"[mesh] OR "health facility planning"[MESH] OR "Public health surveillance"[MeSH] OR "home intervention"[title/abstract] OR "home care"[title/abstract] OR homecare[title/abstract] OR "home care services"[MESH] OR "patient care planning"[MESH] OR "Comprehensive Health Care"[mesh] OR outreach[title/abstract] OR "Patient care team"[MESH] OR multidisciplinary[title/abstract] OR "home visit"[title/abstract] OR "home assessment"[title/abstract] OR "patient management"[title/abstract] OR "social support"[MESH] OR shelter[title/abstract]

3. Not genetics

NOT (Genetic Phenomena[MeSH] OR DNA[title/abstract] OR RNA[title/abstract])

Full search:

(((((adaptation[title/abstract] OR adapting[title/abstract] OR response[title/abstract] OR alert[title/abstract] OR implement*[title/abstract] OR awareness[title/abstract] OR strategy*[title/abstract] OR strategies[title/abstract] OR "risk management"[title/abstract] OR "risk management"[mesh] OR "emergency management"[title/abstract] OR "preparedness"[title/abstract] OR "disaster management"[title/abstract] OR warning*[title/abstract] OR "health promotion"[MeSH] OR "Health education"[MeSH] OR "communication campaign*"[Title/abstract] OR guideline*[Title/Abstract] OR recommendation*[Title/Abstract] OR "Health Services for the Aged"[mesh] OR "health facility planning"[MESH] OR "Public health surveillance"[MeSH] OR "home intervention"[title/abstract] OR "home care"[title/abstract] OR homecare[title/abstract] OR "home care services"[MESH] OR "patient care planning"[MESH] OR "Comprehensive Health Care"[mesh] OR outreach[title/abstract] OR "Patient care team"[MESH] OR multidisciplinary[title/abstract] OR "home visit"[title/abstract] OR "home assessment"[title/abstract] OR "patient management"[title/abstract] OR "social support"[MESH] OR shelter[title/abstract])) OR (cooling[title/abstract] OR "Air condition*"[title/abstract] OR "Air-condition*"[title/abstract] OR climatization[title/abstract] OR climatisation[title/abstract] OR ventilation[title/abstract] OR Fan[title/abstract] OR fans[title/abstract])) OR (media[title/abstract] OR communication*[title/abstract] OR audiovisual[title/abstract] OR helpline*[title/abstract] OR hotline*[title/abstract] OR telecommunication*[title/abstract] OR educat*[title/abstract] OR radio[title/abstract] OR television[title/abstract] OR TV[title/abstract] OR internet[title/abstract] OR campaign*[title/abstract] OR advert*[title/abstract] OR print*[title/abstract] OR "information campaign"[title/abstract] OR telemedicine[title/abstract] OR telehealth[title/abstract] OR telepharmac* OR e-health[title/abstract] OR ehealth[title/abstract] OR e-pharmac*[title/abstract] OR "social media"[mesh] OR "social media"[title/abstract] OR "social network*"[title/abstract] OR Twitter[title/abstract] OR Facebook[title/abstract] OR LinkedIn[title/abstract] OR Pinterest[title/abstract] OR YouTube[title/abstract] OR "daily motion"[title/abstract] OR

Yelp[title/abstract] OR Foursquare[title/abstract] OR "Google Circles"[title/abstract] OR Qype[title/abstract] OR Ello[title/abstract] OR Instagram[title/abstract] OR "Pip.io"[title/abstract] OR "Google Buzz"[title/abstract] OR Orkut[title/abstract] OR Tumblr[title/abstract] OR onesocialweb[title/abstract] OR asmallworld[title/abstract] OR bebo[title/abstract] OR myspace[title/abstract] OR folkdirect[title/abstract] OR virb[title/abstract] OR Friendster[title/abstract] OR storyofmylife[title/abstract])) OR (((("global warming"[Title/Abstract] OR "global warming"[MESH] OR climatic*[Title/Abstract] OR "climate change"[Title/Abstract] OR "climate change"[MESH] OR "Desert Climate"[mesh] OR "El Nino-Southern Oscillation"[Mesh] OR Microclimate[mesh] OR "Tropical Climate"[mesh]))) NOT ((Genetic Phenomena[MeSH] OR DNA[title/abstract] OR RNA[title/abstract]))) AND (((("ambient temperature"[title/abstract] OR "heat strain"[title/abstract] OR "heat exposure"[title/abstract] OR "heat stress"[title/abstract] OR Heating[mesh] OR "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH] OR "hot temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "extreme heat"[MESH] OR "Heat stroke"[MESH] OR "heatstroke"[title/abstract] OR "heat index"[title/abstract] OR "heat episode"[title/abstract] OR "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH] OR "heat event"[title/abstract] OR "Body temperature"[Mesh:noexp] OR "extreme temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "summer temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "Heat Exhaustion"[mesh] OR "summer weather"[title/abstract] OR "summer temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "heat wave"[title/abstract] OR "heatwave"[title/abstract] OR "indoor temperature"[title/abstract] OR "global temperature*"[title/abstract]))) NOT (((("Animals"[Mesh] NOT ("Animals"[Mesh] AND "Humans"[Mesh]))) NOT ("Chemicals and Drugs Category"[MeSH]) NOT (((("Plants"[Mesh] NOT ("Plants"[Mesh] AND "Humans"[Mesh]))))))

7.1.2 Web of Science search

Terms for heat and interventions:

(TS=(ambient temperature OR heat strain OR heat exposure OR heat stress OR extreme heat OR Heat stroke OR heatstroke OR heat index OR heat episode OR heat event OR extreme temperature OR heat exhaustion OR heat wave OR heatwave OR hot temperature OR global temperature OR summer temperature OR summer weather OR outdoor temperature OR "Air conditioner*" OR "air conditioning")) **OR**

(TI=(ambient temperature OR heat strain OR heat exposure OR heat stress OR extreme heat OR Heat stroke OR heatstroke OR heat index OR heat episode OR heat event OR extreme temperature OR heat exhaustion OR heat wave OR heatwave OR hot temperature OR global temperature OR summer temperature OR summer weather OR outdoor temperature OR "air conditioner*" OR "air conditioning"))

AND LANGUAGE: (English OR Chinese OR German) **AND DOCUMENT TYPES:** (Article)

WC/SU

(WC=(Medicine, Research & Experimental OR Public, Environmental & Occupational Health OR Health Care Sciences & Services OR Primary Health Care OR Film, Radio,

Television OR urban studies OR Behavioral Sciences OR communication OR Infectious Diseases OR Planning & Development)) OR

(SU=(Communication OR Biomedical Social Sciences OR Health Policy & Services OR Public, Environmental & Occupational Health OR Urban Studies OR Research & Experimental Medicine OR Infectious Diseases OR Health Care Sciences & Services OR Behavioral OR Film, Radio & Television))

NOT

NOT TS=(wildlife OR animal OR fish OR flora OR conservation OR soil OR "heat shock protein" OR "heat shock proteins" OR genetic OR "DNA" OR "RNA")

Indexes:

Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED) --1945-present

Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) --1945-present

Arts & Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI) --1975-present

Web extra

Supplement 1

Updated search

Preterm birth

Date of search 2019/09/11 Medline(PubMed) 1094 records located. 12 eligible on screening of title or abstract

((preterm) OR Obstetric Labor, Premature[MeSH Terms]) AND ((((((weather) OR temperature) OR meteoro*)) OR (((climate) OR (((("ambient temperature"[title/abstract] OR "heat strain"[title/abstract] OR "heat exposure"[title/abstract] OR "heat stress"[title/abstract] OR Heating[mesh] OR "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH] OR "hot temperature*" [title/abstract] OR "extreme heat"[MESH] OR "Heat stroke"[MESH] OR "heatstroke"[title/abstract] OR "heat index"[title/abstract] OR "heat episode"[title/abstract] OR "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH] OR "heat event"[title/abstract] OR "Body temperature"[Mesh:noexp] OR "extreme temperature*" [title/abstract] OR "summer temperature*" [title/abstract] OR "Heat Exhaustion"[mesh] OR "summer weather"[title/abstract] OR "summer temperature*" [title/abstract] OR "heat wave"[title/abstract] OR "heatwave"[title/abstract] OR "indoor temperature"[title/abstract] OR "global temperature*" [title/abstract]))) NOT (((("Animals"[Mesh] NOT ("Animals"[Mesh] AND "Humans"[Mesh]))) NOT ("Chemicals and Drugs Category"[MeSH]) NOT (((("Plants"[Mesh] NOT ("Plants"[Mesh] AND "Humans"[Mesh])))))))) AND Obstetric Labor, Premature[MeSH Terms]))

Birth weight

Date of search 2019/09/07 Medline(Pubmed) 1758 records located. 8 eligible on screening of title or abstract

((birth) AND weight) AND (((((((weather) OR temperature) OR meteoro*)) OR
 (((climate) OR (((("ambient temperature"[title/abstract] OR "heat strain"[title/abstract]
 OR "heat exposure"[title/abstract] OR "heat stress"[title/abstract] OR Heating[mesh] OR
 "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH] OR "hot temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "extreme
 heat"[MESH] OR "Heat stroke"[MESH] OR "heatstroke"[title/abstract] OR "heat
 index"[title/abstract] OR "heat episode"[title/abstract] OR "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH]
 OR "heat event"[title/abstract] OR "Body temperature"[Mesh:noexp] OR "extreme
 temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "summer temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "Heat
 Exhaustion"[mesh] OR "summer weather"[title/abstract] OR "summer
 temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "heat wave"[title/abstract] OR
 "heatwave"[title/abstract] OR "indoor temperature"[title/abstract] OR "global
 temperature*"[title/abstract]))) NOT (((("Animals"[Mesh] NOT ("Animals"[Mesh] AND
 "Humans"[Mesh]))) NOT ("Chemicals and Drugs Category"[MeSH]) NOT
 (((("Plants"[Mesh] NOT ("Plants"[Mesh] AND "Humans"[Mesh])))))))) AND Obstetric Labor,
 Premature[MeSH Terms])))

Stillbirth

Date of search 2019/09/12 Medline(Pubmed). 83 records located. 1 eligible on screening of title or abstract.

(stillbirth) AND (((((((weather) OR temperature) OR meteoro*)) OR (((climate) OR
 (((("ambient temperature"[title/abstract] OR "heat strain"[title/abstract] OR "heat
 exposure"[title/abstract] OR "heat stress"[title/abstract] OR Heating[mesh] OR "Heat
 Stress Disorders"[MESH] OR "hot temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "extreme
 heat"[MESH] OR "Heat stroke"[MESH] OR "heatstroke"[title/abstract] OR "heat
 index"[title/abstract] OR "heat episode"[title/abstract] OR "Heat Stress Disorders"[MESH]
 OR "heat event"[title/abstract] OR "Body temperature"[Mesh:noexp] OR "extreme
 temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "summer temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "Heat
 Exhaustion"[mesh] OR "summer weather"[title/abstract] OR "summer
 temperature*"[title/abstract] OR "heat wave"[title/abstract] OR
 "heatwave"[title/abstract] OR "indoor temperature"[title/abstract] OR "global
 temperature*"[title/abstract]))) NOT (((("Animals"[Mesh] NOT ("Animals"[Mesh] AND
 "Humans"[Mesh]))) NOT ("Chemicals and Drugs Category"[MeSH]) NOT
 (((("Plants"[Mesh] NOT ("Plants"[Mesh] AND "Humans"[Mesh])))))))) AND Obstetric Labor,
 Premature[MeSH Terms]

7.2 Appendix B: Summary table of all studies

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
Maternal				
Antenatal bleeding				
1.	Bider (1991)	Tel Aviv region, Israel	N=349 hospitalisations due to vaginal bleeding	No monthly/seasonal pattern observed with antepartum haemorrhage
2.	Cil (2017)	3000 counties across USA	N=570 000	HW (temperature and relative humidity > threshold). Association between exposure ≥ 1 HW in a trimester (or 3 months before conception) and any clinically significant uterine bleeding. 1st trimester 0.837 additional cases/1000 births (SE=0.367; $p < 0.05$)
3.	He (2018)	Quebec, Canada	N=17 172. N preterm=5 294. N term=11 878	Weekly Tmax $\geq 30^\circ\text{C}$ compared to 15°C associated with term abruption OR=1.12 (95%CI=1.02, 1.24). No association with preterm abruption.
4.	Rammah (2019)	Harris county, Texas, USA	N=87 placental abruptions	OR=1.93 (95%CI=1.15, 3.23) per 10°F increase in apparent temperature at lag1d. Lag1_6d NS, but in direction of effect.
5.	Qu (2021)	New York State, USA	N= 1 934 918. N=835 465 emergency department visit for antepartum haemorrhage	EHE (>90th centile) by month in transition season and summer. Lag0d. Antepartum haemorrhage, abruption placentae and placenta previa May visit OR=1.15 (95%CI=0.99, 1.33), admission OR=1.18 (95%CI=0.98, 1.42)
Caesarean section				
6.	Molina (2017)	Andean region, Bolivia, Colombia and Peru	N=86 021	Outcome is change in absolute percent with 1 SD above historical Tmean in location for entire pregnancy. C-section increase 0.7% NS
Cardiovascular event				
7.	Ha (2017)	12 sites in USA	N=228 438. N=680 cardiovascular events	In warm season, OR=1.07 (95%CI=1.03, 1.12) of cardiovascular event per 1°C increase in Tmean during week before childbirth. Highest lag0d OR=1.11 (95%CI=1.06, 1.15) per 1°C increase in temperature

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
Gestational diabetes mellitus				
8.	Katsarou (2016)	Skane, Sweden	N=11 538. N=487 GDM cases	2-h glucose level increased 0.009 mmol/L per 1°C increase in monthly Tmean (p<0.001)
9.	Booth (2017)	Toronto, Canada	N=555 911. N=35 879 GDM cases	Prevalence of GDM at Tmean ≤-10°C in 30d before test=4.6% (95%CI=3.5%, 5.3%) vs prevalence at ≥24°C=7.7% (95%CI=7.2%, 8.2%). OR of positive test=1.06 (95%CI=1.05, 1.07) per 10°C increase in Tmean in past 30d.
10.	Retnakaran (2018)	Toronto, Canada	N=1 464. N=318 GDM cases	Odds of GDM higher for increased temperature change in preceding 7, 14, 21 and 28d (only in Feb-July): preceding 7d OR=1.16 (95%CI=1.04, 1.29; P<0.01); preceding 14d OR=1.20 (95%CI=1.05, 1.37; P<0.01); preceding 21d OR=1.16 (95%CI=1.01, 1.33; P<0.05); preceding 28d OR=1.20 (95%CI=1.03, 1.39; P<0.05)
11.	Shen (2019)	Newcastle, Brisbane, Australia	N=2 120	Monthly Tmean at time of OGTT. Lower levels at higher temperature of fasting plasma glucose r=-0.145 (95%CI=-0.187, -0.103; P<0.001) and glycated haemoglobin A1c r=-0.069 (-0.113, -0.025; P=0.002). At higher temperatures increased 1-h plasma glucose r=0.079 (95%CI=0.036, 0.120; P<0.001); 2-h plasma glucose r=0.093 (95%CI=0.051, 0.135; P<0.001). Monthly Tmean at birth. Lower levels at high temperature: umbilical cord C-peptide r=-0.153 (95%CI=-0.199, -0.107; P<0.001) and umbilical cord glucose r=-0.126 (95%CI=-0.172, -0.079; P<0.001)
12.	Molina-Vega (2020)	Malaga, Spain	N=2 374. N=473 GDM cases	Higher odds of GDM with higher Tmean on day of OGTT OR=1.049 (95%CI=1.028, 1.070; P<0.05), preceding 14d OR=1.024 (95%CI=1.005, 1.044; P<0.05), preceding 28d OR=1.048 (95%CI=1.027, 1.069; P<0.05). Higher temperature change in 14 and 28d before OGTT test associated with GDM
13.	Su (2020)	Taiwan	N=371 131	Odds of GDM higher per 1°C increase in daily Tmean overall OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.04, 1.04), daily Tmean 14-27°C OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.02, 1.03), and daily Tmean 28-30°C OR=1.54 (95%CI=1.48, 1.60). Reduced odds GDM for each 1°C increase in mean within-day temperature difference OR=0.90 (95%CI=0.87, 0.92)
14.	Zhang (2021)	Guangzhou, China	N=5 165. N=604 GDM cases	Odds of GDM diagnosis at 24-28 weeks. Compared with the Tmedian of Tmax (30.4°C): 99th centile (35.5°C), week 21 gestation OR=1.66 (95%CI=1.01, 2.74), week 22 OR=1.74 (95%CI=1.06, 2.87). 95th and 97th centile similar to 99th. Per 1°C increase in diurnal temperature range: week 21 OR=1.03

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				(95%CI=1.002, 1.06), week 22 OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.01, 1.08), week 23 OR=1.06 (95%CI=1.02, 1.09), week 24 OR=1.07 (95%CI=1.03, 1.12)
15.	Qu (2021)	New York State, USA	N=1 934 918. N admitted= 835 465	EHE (>90th centile). Lag0d. Diabetes mellitus visits May OR=1.17 (95%CI=1.01, 1.36). Admissions May OR=1.22 (95%CI=1.08, 1.39)
16.	Teyton (2022)	Southern California, USA	N=395 927	At 97th percentile, bell-shaped curve for Tmax across gestational weeks; negative or null estimated for the first trimester and late second trimester and positive estimates for weeks 13-14. Shape of the 99th temperature percentile similar to 97th percentile, although more pronounced. Odds of GDM increased with Tmax at 99th percentile for week 13, OR=1.36 (95%CI=1.07, 1.75) and week 14, OR=1.36 (95%CI=1.06, 1.72). Odds of GDM increased with Tmax at 97th percentile for Tmax at week 14 OR=1.28 (95%CI=1.11, 1.61).
Hypertension in pregnancy				
17.	Dieckmann (1938)	Multiple cities, worldwide	N not reported	Significant association between Tmean and eclampsia, $r=0.33 \pm 0.07$. Poor exposure data: annual Tmean used for some cities. No significant association between temperature range and eclampsia.
18.	Griswold (1965)	Miami, Florida	22 650 deliveries (40 eclampsia)	Positive association between eclampsia and weather. Eclampsia attack rate=3.1 per 1000 during Aug, Sept and Oct, 1.2 per 1000 for other months. Presence of lag60d between beginning of summer and increased attack rate
19.	Ylostalo (1972)	Oulu, Finland	N=1 152	Temperature on admission (when >0°C) positively correlated with hypertension in pregnancy, preeclampsia or eclampsia, $r=0.855$ ($p<0.001$)
20.	Neutra (1974)	Cali, Colombia	N=621. N=156 eclampsia cases	Eclampsia rates decreases as Tmax increases on day of admissions and 3 days prior to admissions (chi squared test= $p<0.05$). Rates of eclampsia on the cooler days are 1.6 to 1.9 times greater than on moderate days. Tmin and temperature range not associated with rates of eclampsia.
21.	Agobe (1981)	Lagos, Nigeria	N=80 129. N=821 eclampsia cases	Eclampsia rate (per 1000 hospital deliveries) inversely proportional to temperature, $r=-0.51$; $P<0.001$.
22.	Bider (1991)	Tel Aviv region, Israel	N=276 hypertension and toxemia	Increased rates of preeclampsia in winter.

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
23.	Neela (1993)	Hyderabad, India	N=34 cases preeclampsia	Higher Tmean for month of childbirth, lower eclampsia. Correlation coefficient=-0.77 (p<0.01), but based on very small numbers (19 vs 15) in monsoon vs dry season, with no significant difference between seasons in preeclampsia (941/22216 vs 331/7346)
24.	Jamelle (1998)	Karachi, Rawalpindi, Peshawar, Quetta, Pakistan	N=18 483. N=395 eclampsia cases	Eclampsia increased with temperature (r=0.74; P<0.01) in Rawalpindi, Punjab. Other provinces NS
25.	Yackerson (2007)	Negev, Israel	N=11 979. N=109 preeclampsia	Increased preeclampsia with increased temperature difference (Tmax-Tmin about 20°C; p=0.003; lag3d)
26.	Tam (2008)	Hong Kong, China	N=15 157. N=245 preeclampsia and eclampsia cases	Significant association between season of conception and rate of preeclampsia (logistic regression Wald Chi-Square=9.2, p=0.03). Conceptions during summer had a higher risk of preeclampsia than those during autumn; OR=1.7 (95%CI=1.2, 2.5). Women who conceived in June had highest risk of developing preeclampsia OR=2.8 (95%CI=1.5-5.2) while women who conceived in October had the lowest.
27.	Imminki (2008)	Cape Town, South Africa	N=1 329. N=93 HELLP syndrome. N=157 eclampsia	Decrease in preeclampsia with increase in monthly Tmin in month of childbirth (p<0.001). Baseline Tmin <8.5°C OR=1.0. Tmin 8.5-10.5°C OR=0.90 (95%CI=0.76, 1.068). Tmin 10.5-12.5°C OR=0.96 (95%CI=0.81, 1.14). Tmin 12.5-14.5°C OR=0.90 (95%CI=0.71, 1.12). Tmin 14.5-16.5°C OR=0.62 (95%CI=0.53-0.72)
28.	Metoki (2008)	Sendai City, Miyagi Prefecture, Japan	N=101	Home BP measurement week 20 gestation to 1 month postpartum. 10°C increase in daily Tmin reduced BP by 2.5 mmHg for SBP (95%CI=2.3, 2.6 mmHg) and 2.5 mmHg for DBP (95%CI=2.4, 2.7 mmHg). Similar findings with daily Tmax and Tmean. (Excludes women who developed gestational hypertension)
29.	Algert (2010)	New South Wales, Australia	N=424 732. N=34 828 hypertension in pregnancy cases	High temperature month 8 decreased pregnancy hypertension (r=-0.69). High temperature at conception=increased pregnancy hypertension and preeclampsia prevalence (data not provided)
30.	Hampel (2011)	Nancy, and Poitiers, France	N=1 500	Per 10°C decrease in temperature, 0.5% increase in SBP (95%CI=0.1, 1.0%), corresponds to 0.6 mmHg increase in SBP (95%CI=0.1, 1.1 mmHg)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
31.	Melo (2014)	Recife, Brazil	N=26 125. N=5 051 hypertensive disorders of pregnancy	Monthly Tmean in month of childbirth negatively correlated with percent of patients with hypertension; r=-0.26; P=0.046
32.	Nasiri (2014)	Mashhad, Khorasan, Razavi province, Iran	N=20 520. N=262 preeclampsia	Monthly Tmean positively associated with preeclampsia prevalence in conception month (p<0.001).
33.	Tran (2015)	Charlottesville, USA	N=63 633. N=526 severe preeclampsia.	Daily Tmax: 1st trimester per 1 SD OR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.03). Month 1 per 1 SD OR=1.12 (95%CI=1.03, 1.22). Month 1 per 1°C OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.01, 1.04). Month 1 Tmin 1st quartile ($\leq 2.3^{\circ}\text{C}$) vs 4th quartile Tmin $\geq 9.7^{\circ}\text{C}$ OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.02, 1.07)
34.	Cho (2017)	South Korea	N=2 495 383. N=48 275 preeclampsia cases	No association between monthly temperature and preeclampsia r=0.49 (SE=0.39, p=0.22) [moderate positive association]
35.	Auger (2017)	Quebec, Canada	N=1 890 711. N 65 273 preeclampsia cases	Preeclampsia prevalence highest with Tmean in week 1-4 of pregnancy $\geq 15.0^{\circ}\text{C}$; (95th centile)=3.69% (95%CI=3.63, 3.74); 5.0-14.9°C(95th-50th)=3.58% (95%CI=3.53-3.64); -5-4.9°C (50th-5th)=3.42% (95%CI=3.36-3.48); $< -5^{\circ}\text{C}$ (5th)=3.36% (95%CI=3.31-3.42). Last 4w pregnancy, lower prevalence in 95th centile: $\geq 15.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ =3.25% (95%CI=3.21-3.30); 5.0-14.9°C=3.53% (95%CI=3.48-3.58); -5-5°C=3.64% (95%CI=3.58-3.70); $< 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ =3.61% (95%CI=3.55-3.67). Maximum OR of 0.98(95% CI=0.88,1.08), when adjusted for season for exposure in first four weeks of pregnancy and preeclampsia(visual estimate from graph)
36.	Cil (2017)	3000 counties across USA	N=570 000	HW (temperature and relative humidity>threshold). Exposure ≥ 1 HW in trimester (or 3m before conception) and additional cases per 1,000 births. Pregnancy-associated hypertension in 2nd trimester increased by 1.04 cases per 1000 births (SE=0.625; p<0.1). 3rd trimester increased 1.47 (SE=0.615; p<0.05). Eclampsia 2nd trimester increased 0.417 (SE=0.212; p<0.05). 3rd trimester increased 0.30 (SE=0.171; p<0.1).
37.	Shashar (2020)	Beersheba, Israel	N=88 476	Positive association between averaged trimester temperature and preeclampsia during warm pregnancies (>50% gestation during spring-summer). RR=2.38 (95%CI=1.50, 3.80) eclampsia with 1 IQR elevation in 1st

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				trimester, RR=2.91 (95%CI=1.98, 4.28) in 2nd trimester and RR=2.91 (95%CI=1.98, 4.28) in 3rd trimester. No association in cold pregnancies.
38.	Xiong (2020)	Chengdu, China	N=2 043 182. N=69 263 hypertensive disorder of pregnancy cases	During first 20w pregnancy, moderately hot and very hot temperatures associated with increased odds of preeclampsia OR=1.13 (95%CI=1.07, 1.19) or eclampsia OR=1.16 (95%CI=1.10, 1.22). Gestational hypertension similar trends
39.	Dastoorpoor (2021)	Ahvaz, Khuzestan province, Iran	N=150 766	Temperature 99th vs 75th centile. Preeclampsia at lag0_6d RR=1.15 (95%CI=0.82, 1.62); lag0_21d RR=1.67 (95%CI=0.90, 3.08). Gestational hypertension lag0_6d RR=0.84 (95%CI=0.58, 1.22); lag0_21d RR=0.87 (95%CI=0.45, 1.69)
40.	Bogan (2019)	Gaziant Turkey	N=6 410 admissions. N=357 toxemia cases	No significant association between Tmax increase and toxemia for outpatients OR=1.01 (95%CI=0.99, 1.02) and in-patients OR=0.99 (95%CI=0.97, 1.01)
41.	Qu (2021)	New York State, USA	N=1 934 918. N admitted= 835 465	EHE (>90th centile) by month in transition season and summer. Lag0d. Hypertension complication visits Sept OR=1.13 (95%CI=1.02, 1.25)
42.	Kim (2021)	Arizona, New York and Washington, USA	N=2 240 000 mothers	When exposed to temperatures above 3SD, increase in hospitalisations is driven by hypertension (r=0.013, SE0.006, p<0.05).
43.	Khodadi (2022)	Ahvaz, Iran	N=150 766 women. N=4 357 preeclampsia cases. N=4 030 gestational hypertension cases	Hot thermal stress (UTCI) not associated with cumulative relative risk of preeclampsia and gestational hypertension at lag0d, 0_2d, 0_6d, 0_13d and 0_21d. Preeclampsia at lag0d and lag 0_21d, cumulative relative risk=1.09 (95%CI=0.76, 1.56) and 1.52 (95%CI=0.76, 3.08). Gestational hypertension at lag0d. cumulative relative risk=0.98 (95%CI=0.66, 1.46) [Highest effect estimate: Preeclampsia, high-low analysis, Lag0_13, CRR= 1.385 (0.529–3.629), Gestational Hypertension, high-low analysis, lag0_6, CRR= 1.544 (0.775–3.079)]
44.	Part (2022)	Johannesburg, South Africa	N=7 986. N=844 hypertensive disorder of pregnancy	Weekly Tmean exposure of 23°C versus 18°C during weeks 3-5 of pregnancy associated with increased risk of preeclampsia, eclampsia, severe preeclampsia, imminent eclampsia, or HELLP syndrome: week 3 HR=1.76 (95%CI=1.12, 2.78) and week 4 HR=1.79 (95% CI=1.19, 2.71). Women with PEH

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				more likely to deliver at later gestational age if exposed to heatwave (heatwave95: p=0.002 and heatwave99: p <0.001)
Infections				
45.	Busowski (1995)	Tampa, Florida	N births=26 880. N pyelonephritis cases=499	NS correlation between daily Tmean, Tmin or Tmax in month of admission and pyelonephritis rate
46.	Dadvand (2011)	Barcelona, Spain	N=7 976. N positive GBS culture=1 359.	Temperature in last 4w of pregnancy increased risk of GBS colonisation per degree above Tmean OR=1.014 (95%CI=1.003, 1.025). Increase in GBS colonisation from >15.4°C. Stepwise increase in quartile 3 and 4 temperature vs quartile 1 (<12.0°C). Quartile 3 (15.4-21.8°C), OR=1.18 (95%CI=0.99-1.40; p=0.068). Quartile 4 (>21.8°C) OR=1.21 (95%CI=1.02-1.45, p=0.031)
47.	Minisha (2019)	Doha, Qatar	N=1 588. N bacteriuria cases=270 N=143 significant bacteriuria	Bacteriuria versus average monthly temperature r=0.677 (p=0.003). Percentage of samples with bacteriuria in months with temperatures ≥35°C=11.3%(179 cases/1408 non-cases) vs. 3.6%(57 cases/1531 non-cases) when <25°C (p< 0.001). Same patterns with Group B Streptococcus and E. Coli
48.	Qu (2021)	New York State, USA	N=1 934 918. N admitted= 835 465.	EHE (>90th centile) by month in transition season and summer. Lag0d. Infectious and parasitic diseases visits May OR=1.29 (95%CI=1.05, 1.58)
Maternal admissions				
49.	Davis (2018)	Charlottesville, USA	N admissions=14 400	HW >35°C for 3d. Admissions for complications of pregnancy, childbirth and the puerperium. Lag0d. Mean difference higher during HW periods 0.4 (95%CI=0.0, 0.8; p=0.034)
50.	Zhao (2019)	1814 cities across Brazil	N=58 400 682 total admissions. N maternal admissions not reported	Maternal admissions (ICD-10 O00-O99) 1-3% higher during HW for all 12 HW definitions. Maximum effect estimate at 97.5th percentile at lag4d lag, approximately 3%(95%CI=2, 4)
51.	Zhao (2019)[1]	1814 cities across Brazil	N=49 145 997 admissions. N maternal admissions not reported	Percent increase in maternal admissions (ICD-10 O00-O99) at lagd07 per 5°C increase in daily Tmean=2.5% (95%CI=2.4, 2.6). Increase in hospitalisations for early hot season=2.7% (95%CI=2.3, 3.1; P<0.001) and late hot

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				season=2.1% (95%CI=1.6, 2.6; P<0.001). Larger effect on perinatal conditions 8.3% (CI=6.7, 9.9; p< .001) and late hot season 7.7% (CI=6.0,9.4; p<0.001)
52.	Qu (2021)	New York State, USA	N=1 934 918. N admitted= 835 465. N maternal admissions not reported.	EHE (>90th centile) by month in transition season and summer. Emergency department visits: lag0d: May OR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.04). Summer (June-Aug) OR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.03). Sept OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.00, 1.05). Summer lag significant to day 5. Lag0_3d OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.02, 1.05). Admissions during pregnancy: May lag0d OR=1.06 (95%CI=1.02, 1.09). June-Aug NS (all lags around 1.0). Sept lag0d OR=1.02 (95%CI=0.99, 1.05). HW emergency visits. Duration of HW lag4d >90th centile. Summer OR=1.10 (95%CI=1.05, 1.16). OR size increases with HW duration
53.	Kim (2021)	Arizona, New York and Washington, USA	N=2 240 000 mothers	Additional day between 1 and 2 SD temperature associated with reduction in prenatal hospitalisation r=-0.006 (SE0.002, p<0.05) and for emergency/urgent hospitalisation r=-0.009 (SE0.002, p<0.01). Additional day between 2 and 3SD of temperature, increase in hospitalisation r=0.014 (SE0.005, p<0.05). Exposure to additional day of temperature above 3SD, any prenatal hospitalisation increased r=0.010 (SE0.033, p<0.01) and emergency/urgent hospitalisations increased 0.071 (SE0.024, p<0.01). Exposed to temperatures above 3SD, increase in hospitalisations is driven by hypertension (r=0.013, SE0.006, p<0.05), excessive vomiting (r=0.007, SE0.004, p<0.05), and other less common conditions (r=0.042, SE0.013, p<0.10, and r=0.043, SE0.020, p<0.05). Secondary diagnosis of other diseases of urinary system (r=0.027, SE0.013, p<0.05), other diseases of the digestive system (r=0.007, SE0.003, p<0.01) and thrombocytopaenia increased (r=0.004, SE0.002, p<0.10) when exposed to temperature >3SD. In historically cooler counties, hepatisations for emergency/urgent cases increased by 0.111 (SE0.044, p<0.05) in association with one additional day of exposure to above 90°F.
Mental health				
54.	Lin (2017)	Shanghai, China	N=1 931	Emotional stress (symptom checklist-90 revised scale, Global Severity Index). U-shape base 20-25°C. Compared to daily mean 20-25°C, ≥95th (31.2-34.1°C) high maternal GSI (highest tercile) at lag1d OR=2.9 (95%CI=1.9, 4.6; P<0.001), and at lag2d OR=2.9 (95%CI=2.1, 4.2; P<0.001). Daily diurnal temperature

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				range also associated. Maternal life event stress during pregnancy (life event scale for pregnant women) NS (figures not reported)
55.	Qu (2021)	New York State, USA	N=1 934 918. N admitted= 835 465 for many adverse maternal outcomes	EHE (>90th centile) by month in transition season and summer. Lag0d. Mental illness admission Sept OR=1.29 (95%CI=0.99, 1.67)
Prelabour rupture of membranes				
56.	Yackerson (2008)	Negev desert, Israel	N=11 979. N PPROM=862	Change in temperature (Tmax-Tmin) increased PPROM r=0.9 (SE=0.3; P=0.003). Lag1d
57.	Ha (2018)	12 cities across USA	N=228 438 singletons ≥23 weeks gestation. N PROM=15 381. N PPROM=5 032. N term PROM=10 349	In warm season, 5% increase in PPROM per 1°C temperature increase in lag0_7d (95%CI=1.03, 1.06). Associations larger closer to childbirth than day 7. OR in hottest months with lag0d OR=1.08(95% CI=1.07, 1.09). Term PROM similar results
58.	Song (2019)	Xinxiang, North Henan, China	N=29 608. N PPROM=3 255	Threshold of association between PPROM and temperature at >29°C (91st centile),with risk relative to median (17°C) RR= 1.61 (95%CI= 1.01, 2.57). At 99th centile (32°C) vs median (17°C), RR=2.03 (95%CI=1.20, 3.43) lag0_1d. RR=2.16 (95%CI=1.24, 3.76) lag0_2d. RR=2.00 (95%CI=1.12, 3.57) lag0_3d. Effect estimates smaller, and non-significant for longer lags to 0_7d
59.	Gat (2021)	Nege, Southern Israel	N=84 476. N PPROM=986	Increase in Tmean. Jewish NS. Bedouin-Arabs lag0d RR=1.19 (95%CI=1.03, 1.37). Lag1d and lag2d also significant. Lag0_7d per quartile increase RR=1.15 (95%CI=0.10, 1.34; P=0.059). Quartile 3 vs Quartile 1 RR=1.488 (p<0.05). Quartile 4 vs Quartile 1 RR=1.11 (NS). Some CIs not available in article
60.	Yang (2021)	Shanghai, China	N PROM=11 873. N PPROM=3 347. N term PROM= 8 526	Baseline comparison: median temperature. 97.5th Tmean PROM (term PROM + PPROM) at lag6d RR=1.08 (95%CI=1.01, 1.16) to lag8d RR=1.050 (95%CI=1.000, 1.102). 97.5th Tmean term PROM lag5d RR=1.08 (95%CI=1.01, 1.16) to lag7d RR=1.09 (95%CI=1.02, 1.18). 90th Tmean also correlated with term PROM at lag6_7d. RR=1.23 of term PROM for diurnal temperature variation of 17°C (95%CI=1.03, 1.47) at lag0d. PPROM with 12°C diurnal temperature variation RR=1.11 (95%CI=1.03, 1.47)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
Foetal and Perinatal				
Composite outcome				
61.	Asamoah (2018)	10 administrative regions of Ghana	N=1 136 (34 stillbirths and 110 miscarriages)	Insignificant increase in odds of stillbirth or miscarriage with each additional increase in mean yearly WBGT across all administrative regions. OR=1.12 (95%CI=0.90, 1.39). Monthly WBGT exposure was not associated with stillbirths or miscarriages OR=1.03 (95%CI=0.84, 1.27). When analysing four selected regions (based on time-homogenous heat exposure), increase in odds of miscarriage or stillbirth with 1°C increase in yearly mean WBGT OR=1.27 (95%CI=0.89, 1.81).
Congenital anomalies				
62.	Tikkanen (1991)	Finland	cases: N=573, controls N=1 200	No association between self-reported exposure to workplace temperatures during the first trimester of pregnancy $\geq 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ and risk of cardiac malformation ($p > 0.05$)
63.	Davies (2000)	Mexico City, Mexico	cases N=38 lethal malformation deaths, controls N=335 other perinatal deaths no lethal malformations	Tmean exposure at week 5. OR=2.0 (95%CI=0.96, 4.15; $p=0.04$) of a perinatal death with a lethal malformation at a Tmean $> 18^{\circ}\text{C}$ versus $< 18^{\circ}\text{C}$
64.	Judge (2004)	New York state, USA	cases N=502, controls N=1 066	Self-reported exposure to $> 100^{\circ}\text{F}$ ($\sim 38^{\circ}\text{C}$) in early pregnancy (2.7% of women). OR of any cardiovascular anomaly=1.13 (95%CI=0.59, 2.19) for > 10 hours/week versus never OR=1.27 (95% CI=0.52, 3.13)
65.	Gu (2007)	Japan 11 sites	N=1 586, 0 controls	Highest incidence at Tmean of 5.4°C . Temperature negatively correlated with incidence (-0.89 ; $p < 0.001$).
66.	Aminzadeh (2010)	Ahvaz, southwest Iran	cases N=1 131 had an abnormal TSH level. N=142 cases, controls N=45 802	4% reduction per 1°C increase in Tmean at childbirth OR=0.96 (95%CI=0.94, 0.98; $p < 0.001$). Lowest incidence in hottest month, highest in coldest. Linear relationship between congenital hypothyroidism and temperature ($r=0.87$, $p < 0.001$)
67.	Van Zutphen (2012)	New York State, excluding New York City, USA	cases congenital cataracts (N=75), anophthalmia or	A 5°F (2.8°C) increase in the daily mean minimum universal apparent temperature (UAT) associated with an increase in congenital cataracts OR=1.51 (95%CI=1.14, 1.99). Congenital cataracts also associated with heat waves OR=1.97 (95% CI=1.17, 3.32), number of heat waves OR=1.45

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
			microphthalmia (N=34, controls N=59 328)	(95%CI=1.04, 2.02), and number of days above 90th centile OR=1.09 (95%CI=1.02, 1.17). Associations between heat and congenital cataracts were positive for weeks 4–7, but not from week 10 onwards. Higher mean minimum UAT associated with reduced anophthalmia or microphthalmia OR=0.71 (95% CI=0.54, 0.94), as was daily mean UAT OR = 0.70 (95% CI=0.53, 0.93) and daily maximum OR=0.70 (95%CI = 0.52, 0.93). No association detected between mean and maximum universal apparent temperature, heat waves, and days >90th centile and nervous system defects. Spina bifida without anencephalous OR=1.12 with daily minimum apparent temperature (95% CI=0.92, 1.35), OR=1.30 with heat wave exposure, (95%CI=0.82, 2.05). Microcephalus and heat waves exposure OR=1.10 (95%CI=0.77, 1.58). No associations detected between mean and maximum universal apparent temperature, heat waves and days >90th centile, cardiovascular defects, musculoskeletal defects, and craniofacial defects. Most point estimates around 1.00. A 5 °F (2.8 °C) increase in mean daily minimum universal apparent temperature (UAT) associated with renal agenesis/hypoplasia OR=1.17 (95% CI=1.00, 1.37). Odds of gastroschisis significantly decreased with heat wave events OR=0.48 (95% CI=0.28, 0.81) and number of heat waves OR=0.63 (95% CI=0.43, 0.92)
68.	Agay-Shay (2013)	Israel, Tel Aviv	cases N=1 630 (607 cases with multiple CHDs, 542 with isolated ASDs and 481 with isolated VSDs), controls N=130 402	Whole year period. OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.01; 1.05) for multiple congenital health disorders (CHDs) for exposure to Tmax (per 1 °C increase). Isolated ASD OR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.04) per 1 °C increase in Tmean. Quartile 3 temperature versus Q1 OR=1.34 (95% CI=1.06, 1.70), Q4 OR=1.27 (95% CI=1.00, 1.61). In the cold season exposure to the Tmean and Tmax (per 1 °C increase) increased risk for multiple CHDs OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00, 1.10) and OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.01, 1.05). Comparing the highest to lowest quartiles of Tmean, risk for multiple CHDs increased OR=1.41 (95%CI=1.03, 1.94). 1-day increase in the extreme heat events showed increased risk for multiple CHDs OR=1.13 (95% CI=1.06, 1.21) and also for isolated ASDs OR=1.10 (95% CI=1.02, 1.19). A 1-day increase in the extreme heat events based on the previous 90 days increased risk for multiple CHDs OR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.04). VSD point estimates

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				around 1.0, except per 1 °C increase in daily Tmean OR=1.08 (95% CI=1.00, 1.16)
69.	Kilinc (2016)	Ankara and Istanbul, Turkey	cases N=1 709 with hypospadias, controls N=4 946	More cases occurred in warmer than colder months. Tmax monthly in cases=36.4 ±10.8 vs controls 26.0 ±9.6 (P=0.01) and monthly Tmean, 22.5 ±13.9 in cases vs 18.7 ±11.3 in controls (p= 0.01). Mean monthly ambient temperatures in summer OR=1.32 (95%CI=1.08, 1.52) and maximum monthly ambient temperatures in summer OR=1.22 (95%CI=0.99, 1.54)
70.	Soim (2017)	USA 10 states	cases N=326, controls N=1 781	Heat event (2 consecutive days daily apparent temperature max 95th (HE95) or 3 consecutive days at 90th centile (HE90). No associations between NTDs and HE95 or HE90. HE90 (98°F) versus no HE90 in California OR=0.51 (95%CI=0.28–0.93). Overall population HE90 of 3 days duration versus 0 days OR=0.66 (95% CI=0.45–0.98) and OR=0.33 (95%CI=0.12–0.94) in California.
71.	Auger (2017)	Quebec, Canada	cases N=6 482 (n = 539 with critical heart defects and n = 5 943 noncritical heart defects), controls N= 704 209	10 days ≥30 °C higher prevalence versus 0 days, of transposition of great vessels (29.2 vs. 19.2 per 100,000), truncus arteriosus (12.2 vs. 5.5 per 100,000), coarctation of aorta (21.9 vs. 16.5 per 100,000), ASD (413.2 vs. 289.0 per 100,000), defects of the aorta (19.4 vs. 11.9 per 100,000), heterotaxy (14.6 vs. 8.2 per 100,000), and other defects (255.2 vs. 223.0 per 100,000). Single and multiple defects also higher. Higher differences with longer exposure, especially with ASD, 15 days ≥30 °C (PR = 1.37, 95% CI = 1.10, 1.70). ASD associations highest in weeks 2 and 8. PR highest week 7, e.g., 32 °C associated with 1.13 times (95% CI: 1.01, 1.26) risk relative to 20°C. Maximum temperatures of 32 °C associated with multiple defects week 8 (PR = 1.31, 95% CI = 1.04, 1.65) compared with 20 °C.
72.	Auger (2017)	Quebec, Canada	cases N=297 neural tube defects, including spina bifida, anencephalus and encephalocoele, controls N= 887 710	Overall neural tube defects no pattern with weekly Tmax during week 3 or 4 post-conception. Prevalence of spina bifida higher for weekly Tmax ≥30°C during week, 4 29.5 per 100,000 (95%CI=21.3, 37.8) vs 25.0 per 100,000 at 20-24.9°C (95%CI=18.2-31.7); CIs wide. No pattern with anencephalus or encephalocoele. Compared to 20°C, daily Tmax 30°C, OR=1.56 of any neural tube defect on day 5 (95%CI=1.04, 2.35) and OR=1.49 on day 6 (95%CI=1.00, 2.21) of week 4. Spina bifida and anencephalus or encephalocoele weak

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				associations at end of critical exposure window. Associations with neural tube defects with higher temperatures towards end of week 4
73.	Soim (2018)	USA 8 states	cases n = 907 live-born infants, stillbirths, and induced terminations with orofacial clefts or cleft lip with cleft palate, controls N=2 206	HE95: ≥2 consecutive days with apparent Tmax >95th centile. HE90: ≥3 consecutive days apparent Tmax >90th centile. For Southern regions, no association between heat wave exposure OR=0.87 (95%CI=0.58, 1.29), frequency OR=0.92 (95%CI=0.61, 1.39) and duration of exposure OR=1.02 (95%CI=0.52, 1.98) for EHE90 or EHE95. For Southeast region, significant association for EHE95 for 3 day versus 0 days OR=1.89 (95%CI=1.11, 3.23) and 4 days versus 0 days for EHE 90 OR=1.70 (95%CI=1.02, 2.81). For Northeast, no significant association for heatwave OR=1.52 (95%CI=0.73, 3.20), frequency and duration. For Southwest no significant association for heatwave, frequency or duration, highest effect estimate OR=0.67 (95%CI=0.17, 2.61). For West, no significant associations found for heatwave exposure, frequency and duration, OR=1.53 (95%CI=0.69, 3.40) for EHE 90 for 3 days vs 0 days. For Upper Midwest, significant protective effect for 2 EHEs vs 0 OR=0.49 (95%CI=0.28, 0.86) and EHE90 3 days vs 0 OR=0.42 (95%CI=0.22, 0.82). For all regions, overall, no significant associations were found, point estimates range from estimates ranged from 0.78 to 1.11
74.	Lin (2018)	USA 8 states	N controls=5 742. N cases=5 848 congenital heart defects	Study examines ≥2d with daily Tmax>95th centile (EHE95). ≥3d with Tmax >90th centile (EHE90). Duration of EHE90 or EHE95, total days and consecutive days. Most associations null with overall defects. All point estimates >1.0. VSD and ASD defects NS. Almost all estimates >1.0, higher in summer. VSD summer EHE95 OR=1.18 (95%CI=0.81, 1.72). VSD spring EHE95 OR=1.06 (95%CI=0.41, 2.74). ASD summer EHE95 OR=1.32 (95%CI=0.88, 1.99). ASD spring EHE95 OR=1.15 (95%CI=0.33, 4.04). VSD EHE 90 3-5d OR 2.17-2.57. All p<0.05 in summer. OR point estimates generally increased with additional duration of exposure. Higher effect sizes in some regions, e.g. OR=2.28 for EHE95 in spring in New York for VSD and 1.87 (95%CI=1.11, 3.16) for ASD and EHE95. EHE95 total days and left ventricular outflow tract obstruction in Utah OR=1.53 (95%CI=1.00, 2.35) and septal defects in Iowa OR=1.71 (95%CI=1.09, 2.69). EHE5 duration and conotruncal defects in Utah OR=1.34 (95%CI=1.00,

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				1.81), septal defects in New York OR=1.30 (95%CI=1.05, 1.62). Association between temperature and VSD increased with magnitude and duration of high temperature exposure
75.	Xu (2023)	11 Cities in Eastern China (Huzhou, Hangzhou, Jiaying, Shaoxing, Ningbo, Taizhou, Wenzhou, Jinhua, Quzhou, Lishui, Zhoushan)	N= 983 523 births, n= 5 904 infants with CHD	Increased risk of congenital heart defect with increasing temperature exposure during gestational periods 8-14 weeks and 20-26 weeks, with graph additionally showing significance at approx. 28-32 weeks. Maximum OR per 1°C increase at 24th week, of 1.85 (95% CI=1.335, 2.840). No other RR reported for other lag periods. CRR maximum at highest temperature of 3.78 (95%CI=1.46, 10.72)
76.	Zhang (2023)	United States (National)	N= 2 352 529, number of births with anomalies = 29 188 (incidence of 12.4 per 1000 births)	Moderate heat (85th percentile) and extreme heat (95th percentile) associated with increased risk of congenital anomalies, further strengthened when adjusted for PM2.5 in some instances. Total anomalies: Moderate heat- OR=1.06 (95% CI=1.02, 1.11) adjusted OR 1.25, 95% CI: 1.18, 1.32) Extreme heat- only significant with adjusted OR=1.05 (95% CI: 1.00, 1.11), to calculate, adjusted-OR=1.29 (95% CI=1.21, 1.38)
Non-reassuring foetal status				
77.	Bonell (2022)	West Kiang, The Gambia	N=40. N=17 adverse pregnancy outcomes	Foetal heart rate linear association with heat stress; 10.7 increase (95%CI=7.5, 13.8) beats/min for each 10°C UTCI increase and 13.4 (95%CI=9.5, 17.2) beats/min for each 10°C WBGT increase. Change in umbilical artery resistance index (RI) from cool baseline to working conditions reduced with increasing heat stress exposure up to 32°C UTCI/30°C WBGT, then increases with increased heat stress. U-shaped association with WBGT, base at 30°C. No statistical difference between RI and heat stress in those with and without adverse pregnancy outcomes
78.	Bonell (2022)	West Kiang, The Gambia	N=92	Increased foetal heart rate associated with UTCI OR=1.45 (95%CI=1.26, 1.64; p<0.0001) and WBGT OR=2.07 (95%CI=1.69, 2.46; p<0.0001). Each 1°C increase in UTCI associated with foetal strain OR=1.17 (95%CI 1.09, 1.29; p<0.0001) and adjusted OR of 1.12 (1.03, 1.21, p=0.010). For each 1°C increase in WBGT, increased foetal strain OR 1.21 (95%CI=1.12, 1.32, p<0.0001), adjusted OR=1.08 (95%CI=0.97, 1.21, p=0.137).

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
79.	Yuzen (2023)	Hamburg, Germany	N=386	Peripheral resistance of uterine artery decreased in pregnancies exposed to 4 consecutive days of exposure exceeding the 90th percentile, p=0.038.
80.	Shankar (2023)	Thatta, Pakistan	N=459	Association between Tmax in first trimester and reduced gestational age appropriate z-score for length $\beta=-0.04$ (95%CI=-0.06, -0.01; p<0.001) and head circumference $\beta=-0.03$ (95%CI=-0.05, -0.01; p<0.05). For each 5°C increase in Tmax in first trimester, length and height gestational age appropriate z-score decreased by 0.19 and 0.14 respectively. Association between Tmax in third trimester and gestation age appropriate length $\beta=0.03$ (95%CI=0.01, 0.05; p<0.05). Heat index exposure in first and second trimester negatively associated with adjusted length and height $\beta=-0.02$ (95%CI=-0.04, -0.01; p=0.001), $\beta=-0.02$ (95%CI= -0.03, -0.01; p=0.008) for length and $\beta=-0.02$ (95%CI= -0.04, -0.01; p=0.007) and $\beta=-0.02$ (95%CI= -0.03, -0.00; p=0.018) for head circumference. Severe heat exposure (>20 days when temperature >39°C) in first trimester associated with decreased gestational age adjusted length and head circumference.
81.	Leung (2023)	Boston, USA	N=9 446	5°C increase cumulative temperature exposure associated with head circumference, difference in mean z score at 16-32 weeks gestation -0.17 (95%CI=-0.27, -0.08) and 24-31 weeks gestation -0.31 (95%CI=-0.50, -0.12). Mean z score for biparietal diameter decreased for every 5°C increase cumulative temperature exposure during 16-23 weeks -0.23 (95%CI=-0.33, -0.13) and 24-31 weeks -0.21 (95%CI=-0.40, -0.03). Femur length associated with temperature during weeks 16-23, reduction in z score -0.16 (95%CI=-0.27, -0.06). Abdominal circumference reduction in z-score with 5°C increase cumulative temperature exposure during 16-23 weeks -0.14 (95%CI=-0.25, -0.030), 24-31 weeks -0.26 (95% CI=-0.44, -0.07) and weeks 32-40 -0.26 (95%CI=-0.48, -0.040)
Oligohydramnios				
82.	Sciscione (1997)	Baltimore, USA	N=42	Negative correlation between Tmean and amniotic fluid index (measured using ultrasound). At lag2d r=0.25 (p=0.003) , lag3d r=0.28 (p=0.002) and lag4d r=0.31, p=0.001.

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
83.	Luton (2004)	Paris, France	N total=131. N cases=11	Proportion of cases with oligohydramnios higher in 2003 than 2002 7/40 (17.5%) vs. 4/91 (4.4%) p=0.03
Perinatal mortality				
84.	Basagana (2011)	Catalonia region, Spain	N deaths=1 480	Lag0d. Perinatal deaths >95th centile vs ≤95th RR=1.53 (95%CI=1.16, 2.02). Female greater risks than males
85.	Schumann (2019)	Northern Sweden	N=28 239. N Sami population=14 045. N non-Sami=14 194. N perinatal mortality Sami=645. N perinatal mortality non-Sami=601.	Summer, non-Sami >90th centile in month of birth vs <10th centile. Odds of perinatal mortality OR=0.20 (95%CI=0.05, 0.81). No significant effects in summer-born Sami, however, odds ratio was increased, in positive direction of effect. NS in other seasons. Temperatures median <0°C in several months, July median 14.8°C. For high temperatures with lag 1 month before birth: OR:1.61 (0.90-2.89)
Placental outcome				
86.	Wang (2020)	Guangzhou, China	N=4 051	Reference 20°C. 95th centile (29°C) temperature exposure during late third trimester associated with -6.03g (95%CI=-11.28; -0.78g) change in placental weight and -16.15cm ³ (95%CI=-26.24; -6.07) change in placental volume. No significant associations found during other periods of pregnancy. Positive association between temperature and placental weight/birth ratio (PFR) β=0.26 (95%CI= 0.07; 0.45) at 29°C. Association found between high temperatures and PFR during 25-36 weeks gestation.
Spontaneous abortion				
87.	Bianchi-Demichelo (2001)	Lugano, Switzerland	N=56 emergency clinic visits for threatened abortion. N=54 spontaneous abortion	Tmin increase associated with emergency room visit for threatened abortion. At 1°C Tmin OR=1.08 (95%CI=1.03, 1.14). At 15°C Tmin, OR=3.3 (95%CI=1.6, 6.7). No association found for increased emergency room visit for spontaneous abortion.
88.	Sun (2020)	Guangdong, China	N=2 044 miscarriages, N=2 275 controls	Inverse U-shaped association between Tmean and miscarriage. Peak effects 1-2 months prior to hospitalisation and entire pregnancy. 50th centile (22-23°C) compared to 15°C. For month 1 prior to hospitalisation OR = 1.20 (95%CI: 1.04-1.37). Month 2 prior to hospitalisation OR=1.24 (95%CI=1.09-1.41). Entire pregnancy OR=1.39 (95%CI=1.19-1.63). No significant

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				associations at 75th and 95th centiles for first, second and third months prior to pregnancy and for the entire pregnancy, but OR all above 1.
89.	Dastoorpoor (2021)	Ahvaz, Khuzestan province, Iran	N=150 766 women, N=5 063 spontaneous abortion	Intensified thermal stress of PET index (type of heat index). Spontaneous abortion lag0d OR=1.10 (95%CI=0.89, 1.36)
90.	Bogan (2019)	Gaziantep, Turkey	N=6 410 admissions, N=6 053 cases of abortion	Increases in Tmax not associated with spontaneous abortion OR=0.99 (95%CI=0.99-0.99)
91.	Qu (2021)	New York State, USA	N=1 934 918. N admitted= 835 465 emergency department visit for threatened or spontaneous abortion	EHE (>90th centile) by month in transition season and summer. Lag0d. Threatened/spontaneous abortion visits May OR=1.03 (95%CI=0.99, 1.09). Summer OR=1.02 (95%CI=0.99, 1.05). Sept OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00-1.11)
92.	Khodadi (2022)	Ahvaz, Iran	N=150 766 women. N=5 063 spontaneous abortion	Hot thermal stress (UTCI) not associated with cumulative relative risk of spontaneous abortion at lag0d, lag0_2d, lag0_6d, lag0_13d and lag0_21d. For lag0d CRR=1.23 (95%CI=0.86, 1.77)
93.	Zhao (2022)	Nanjing, China	N=1 002 cases, N=2 004 controls	75th, 95th and Tmax compared to Tmean (17°C). At lag1d at 75th percentile OR=1.48 (95%CI=1.22, 1.80), 95th percentile OR=1.84 (95%CI=1.34, 2.51), Tmax OR=2.07 (95%CI=1.36, 3.16). At lag2d, 7th percentile OR=1.37 (95%CI=1.22, 1.54), 95th percentile OR=1.57 (95%CI=1.32, 1.88) and Tmax OR=1.68 (95%CI=1.33, 2.13). At lag4d, 7th percentile OR=1.18 (95%CI=1.08, 1.30) and 95th percentile OR=1.19 (95%CI=1.03, 1.38).
Stillbirths				
94.	Strand (2012)	Brisbane, Australia	N=101 870. N SB=653	Temperature in lag0_28d. Increasing Tmean increased risk of SB up to 21°C (reference group), e.g. HR of stillbirth at 12°C about 0.3 vs 21°C. Significant at 20-36w gestation, but not at ≥37w. Above 21°C plateau reduces risk (U shape), NS difference in HR at high temperature. Patterns with lag0_7d similar, except larger point estimate HR reduction at higher temperatures, e.g. 25°C vs 21°C RR=0.82 (95%CI=0.64, 1.02). At 15°C expect 353 stillbirths per 100,000 pregnancies, at 23°C 610 per 100,000 pregnancies

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
95.	Arroyo (2016)	Madrid, Spain	N=298705	Risk of late foetal death increased at lag1d by 1.2% RR=1.01 (1.01, 1.01; p<0.001) with exposure to Tmax in 2nd trimester. Risk of late foetal death increased with exposure to Tmin in 3rd trimester RR=1.04 (1.04, 1.04; p<0.001)
96.	Basu (2016)	California, USA	N SBs=8510	Lags associated lag2d, 3, 4, 5, 6, 23, 24, 25, 26. All results cumulative average of lag2_6d and percent increase per 10°F in apparent temperature: 10.4% (95%CI=4.4, 16.8) (ES 3x10°F=1.34; SE=0.10). Associations in week 20-25 and 31-33, but not 34-36 and 37-44 (near 0 point estimate). Cold season NS
97.	Ha (2017)	12 clinical centres across USA	N=223 375. N SBs=992	Compared to 10–90th centile temperatures during whole pregnancy. >90th centile OR of stillbirth=3.71 (95%CI=3.07, 4.47). Pre-conception OR=1.02 (95%CI=0.80, 1.30). 1st trimester OR=0.83 (95%CI=0.63-1.08). 2nd trimester OR=1.03 (95%CI=0.78-1.34). 3rd trimester not assessed as small. Warm season (May-Sept) lag0_6d OR=1.06 (95%CI=1.03, 1.09) per 1°C increase in temperature. Cold season (Oct-April) OR=1.00 (95%CI=0.98, 1.02)
98.	Auger (2017)	Quebec, Canada	N SBs=5047. N term SB=1693	Daily Tmax. All SBs. Lag2d ≥28°C vs 11.5-19.9°C OR=1.10 (95%CI=0.97, 1.25). Lag3d OR=1.08 (95%CI=0.95, 1.22) 28°C vs 15.5-19°C. Lag4d, lag5d similar. Lag6d OR=1.14 (95%CI=1.00, 1.29) ≥28°C vs 15-19.9°C. NS for preterm SBs. Term SB (all compared to 20°C) >28°C lag3d OR=1.16 (95%CI=1.02, 1.33). >30°C OR=1.22 (95%CI=1.02,1.46), 32°C OR=1.28 (95%CI=1.03, 1.60). Lag6d, compared to 15-19.9°C ≥28°C OR=1.32 for term SB (95%CI=1.06, 1.65). NS lag7d, lag8d
99.	Li (2018)	Brisbane, Australia	N=289 351. N SBs=1783	PTB prevalence with comparison daily Tmean and Tmin at different centiles. 75th centile 1st trimester HR=1.13 (95%CI=0.90, 1.42), 2nd trimester HR=1.11 (95%CI=1.04, 1.19), 3rd trimester HR=1.91 (95%CI=0.91, 4.02). 95th centile 1st trimester HR=1.05 (95%CI=0.96, 1.16), 2nd trimester HR=1.47 (95%CI=1.24, 1.74), 3rd trimester HR=2.23 (95%CI=1.02, 5.33)
100.	Weng (2018)	Taiwan, China	N=2 123 751. N SBs=20 475	Temperature at birth 21.5-23.4°C (reference group, lowest level). Temperature 23.5-25.4°C RR=1.08 (95%CI=1.01, 1.14). Temperature 25.5-27.4°C RR=1.09 (95%CI=1.03, 1.15). Temperature 27.5-29.4°C RR=1.16 (95%CI=1.10, 1.22). Temperature 29.5-30.8°C RR=1.17 (95%CI=1.09, 1.26)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
101.	Rammah (2019)	Harris county, Texas, USA	N SBs=709. N SBs with placental abruption=87	OR with 10°F increase in apparent temperature (ambient and dew point temperature). OR=1.25-1.37. Significant for lag1_6d (highest lag1d OR=1.37 (95%CI=1.16, 1.61). With moving averages (means of lag days) highest with lag0_6d: OR=1.45 (95%CI=1.18, 1.77). Analysis restricted to hottest months (June, July, Aug). Lag0_6d OR=2.57 (95%CI=1.72, 2.84)
102.	Wang (2019)	Brisbane, Australia	N=277 133. N SBs=705	Exposure in each gestation month binary variable, 6 HW definitions: 90th centile (2, 3, 4d duration); 95th centile (2, 3, 4d duration). All OR point estimates month 1-9 of pregnancy >1. Month 10 OR<1. For most HW definitions, point estimate OR higher in month 1-6 than in month 7, 9. HW definition 90th centile 2d, month 1-6 ranged from HR=1.54 (95%CI=1.27, 1.87) to HR=1.75 (95%CI=1.44, 2.12), but HR=0.97 (95%CI=0.74, 1.27) month 7, HR=1.46 in month 8 (95%CI=1.09, 1.96), lowered in month 9, 10. 95th centile for 4d highest risk in month 8 HR=1.52 (95%CI=1.11, 2.09)
103.	Ranjbaran (2020)	Tehran, Iran	N=516 570. N SBs=3460	Increasing temperature was associated with an increased relative risk of stillbirth of 1.25 (95%CI 0.95, 1.65) comparing the 99th percentile of mean temperature to the median.
104.	Davenport (2020)	Malawi, Mali, Nigeria, Zimbabwe, Madagascar, Senegal, Kenya, Uganda, Lesotho, Burkina Faso, Guinea, Rwanda, Zambia, Siera Leone, Liberia	N=65 327. N SBs=5 319	Likelihood of second or third trimester stillbirth or spontaneous/induced abortion increases with 10% increase in proportion of days >104°F to 1.9% (p-value<0.01). As proportion of days between 100-104°F increases by 10%, likelihood of a second or third term stillbirth increases by 1.4%. For observations with at least 2 months of potential exposure, there is an increase of 0.11 in the probability of stillbirth for extreme heat exposure in the pre-pregnancy months, and an increase of 0.1 in the probability of still birth for exposure to extreme heat in the first trimester (p<0.05). For observations with at least 7 months exposure, this is only statistically significant for exposure in the third trimester (increase of 0.4 in probability of stillbirth)
105.	Kanner (2020)	Utah, USA	N=112 005. N SBs=500	Average ambient temperature across whole pregnancy from LMP to delivery ang stillbirth risk. >90th percentile OR=5.06 (95% CI=3.34, 7.68) compared to moderate temperatures using generalised estimating equations. For case control models, exposure to extreme hot temperatures associated with

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				stillbirth OR= 6.79 (95% CI=4.61, 9.99). Acute analysis: temperature during the last week of pregnancy, average over whole week and per day. Using case-crossover models, 1.07 increased odds [95%CI= 1.04, 1.10] associated with each 1°C. When restricting to mean AT > 20°C, this increased to 1.32 (95%CI=1.20, 1.49] per 1°C increase.
106.	Savitz (2021)	California, USA	N=1876	Stillbirth all lag1_7d. >90th centile in June-Sept per 1°C OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00, 1.10). Quartile 4 >26°C vs quartile 1 OR=1.5 (95%CI=1.0, 2.1). April, May, Oct per 1°C OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00, 1.10). Quartile 2 OR=2.1 (95%CI=1.5, 2.9). Quartile 3 OR=1.8 (95%CI=1.3, 2.7). Quartile 4 OR=1.6 (95%CI=1.1, 2.5) vs Quartile 1
107.	Khodadi (2022)	Ahvaz, Iran	N=150 766. N SBs=1965	Hot thermal stress (UTCI) increased the cumulative relative risk of stillbirth for lag 0-13d, RR=2.05 (95%CI=1.01, 4.15)
108.	Yang (2022)	Taiwan	N SBs=22 796	Relative risk of stillbirth compared to 20-22°C. 1.10 (95%CI=1.04, 1.17; p<0.01) with mild heat 22-25°C, 1.15 (95%CI=1.09, 1.22; p<0.01) for moderate heat 25-29°C and 1.18 (95%CI=1.11, 1.25; p<0.01) when exposed to extreme heat (>29°C). The percentage of stillbirths that are attributable to mild heat, moderate heat and extreme heat are 9.18% (95%CI=0.04, 0.14), 13.69% (95%CI=0.05, 0.22) and 15.06% (95%CI=0.10, 0.20). The greatest cumulative effect of extreme heat temperature was found in the 97.5th percentile of temperature (29.8 °C) relative to the optimal temperature (21 °C) at lag 0-3 months, with a cumulative relative risk (CRR) of 2.49 (95% CI=1.24, 5.03).
109.	Nyadanu (2022)	Western Australia	N=474 835. N SBs=2 835	Relative to no thermal stress (median UTCI 13.9°C), risk of stillbirth for exposure to heat stress 95th and 99th percentile were significant for lag days 0, 0-1, 0-3, 0-6, 0-13 and 0-21. For lag day 0, RR=1.01 (95%CI=1.00, 1.01) and RR=1.01 (95%CI=1.01, 1.02)
110.	Richards (2022)	California, Florida, Georgia, Kansas, New Jersey and Oregon, USA	N controls= 553 928 and N SBs=140 428	For every 1°C increase in 7d average over threshold, odds of stillbirth increased OR 1.10 (95%CI=1.04, 1.17). When more than 4 consecutive hot days in previous week, risk of stillbirth increased 1.03 (95%CI=1.01, 1.06). NS compared to 20°C, average temperature of 35°C during exposure window increased risk of stillbirth 1.03 (95%CI=1.00, 1.06)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
111.	McElroy (2022)	14 LMICs (Angola, Benin, Burundi, Ethiopia, Haiti, Malawi, Nepal, Nigeria, Philippines, South Africa, Tajikistan, Timor-Leste, Uganda, and Zimbabwe)	N=103 535. N SBs=1 210	Stillbirth Tmax 20-30°C significant increased RR vs 20°C lag0_7d. Lag3_6d significant increased 39°C. Diurnal range significant increased RR for diurnal <16°C vs 16°C Tmax. Women with ≥1d diurnal range RR=2.1 (95%CI=1.01, 4.02) of stillbirth
112.	Nyadanu (2023)	Ghana	N=5 961 328. N=90 532 stillbirths	Odds of stillbirth increased with increasing UTCI exposure up to 90th percentile, with a reduction in odds, and a protective effect noted at 99th percentile for cumulative lag. Maximum OR =1.18 (95%CI=1.02, 1.36) for cumulative lag of 0-9 months at 90th percentile UTCI vs median. Maximum OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.01,1.05) at lag 1,2,3 months (non-cumulative) at 90th percentile UTCI vs median
Neonatal				
Low birth weight				
113.	Murray (2000)	Northern Ireland, United Kingdom	N=5 418 817	Estimates only provided for sub-group analyses: Females, with an increase of 1°C in mean daily Tmax in 2nd trimester mean birth weight rose 3.5gm (SE=0.88; p<0.001). Males 1.02gm (SE=0.88; P=0.25)
114.	Wells (2002)	140 populations worldwide, including: Africa (40 countries); Asia (30 countries); Central/South America (25 countries); and Europe, North America, Australia, New Zealand (35 countries)	Median sample size= 5 558. Mean sample size= 97 237	Annual heat index (0-4), drawn from monthly discomfort ratings using temperature and humidity data. Simple linear regression weight (grams) and heat index r=-0.59 (p<0.001). Analysis with 108 populations with full data: 1 unit rise in heat index birth weight decreases 2.7% (p=0.002). Linear relationship

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
115.	Tustin (2004)	Dunedin, New Zealand	N=7 039	Average birth weight did not differ as a function of ambient temperature (peak versus trough for trimesters 1 and 2) $F(1\ 953) = .31$, $p < 0.05$ in full term infants
116.	Elter (2004)	Istanbul, Turkey	N=3 333	Mean birth weight for each trimester of daily Tmean. Temperature in 2nd trimester associated with reduced BW ($\beta=0.001$; $p=0.018$). NS in other trimesters (data not provided)
117.	Lawlor (2005)	Aberdeen, Scotland, United Kingdom	N=12 150	Temperature around conception -2.4gm per 1°C (95%CI=-4.6, -0.2). Tmean in middle of 1st trimester and birth weight (hotter temperature associated with lower BW). Stepwise change -5.4gm/ 1°C (95%CI=-7.9, -2.9; p test for trend <0.001). Temp in mid-2nd trimester NS association. 3rd trimester step-wise increase in weight per quartile increase in temp (p test for trend=0.002). Gains 1.3gm / 1°C (95%CI=0.5, 2.1). Temperature around childbirth similar finding
118.	Chodick (2007)	Israel (whole country)	N=225 545. N LBW=12 724	Monthly Tmin. Month 1 of pregnancy regression coefficient for birth weight per $1^{\circ}\text{C}=0.77$ (95%CI=0.11, 1.42; $p=0.02$). Month 4 of pregnancy regression coefficient per $1^{\circ}\text{C}=1.45$ (95%CI=0.78, 2.13; $p < 0.01$)
119.	Madsen (2010)	Oslo, Norway	N=25 229. N LBW=303	NS birth weight and temperature (mean difference in birth weight per temperature quartile)
120.	Wolf (2012)	Saxony and Brandenburg, Germany	Saxony: N=162 913, N LBW=8 034. Brandenburg: N=128 604, N LBW=6 242.	Comparisons of Tmean in quintile (baseline, coldest to hottest), term LBW. Brandenburg. 2nd trimester: 2nd quintile OR=0.85 (95%CI=0.70, 1.02), 3rd OR=0.68 (95%CI=0.51, 0.91) 4th OR=0.70 (95%CI=0.48, 1.00) 5th OR=0.81 (95%CI=0.53, 1.25) $p=0.05$. Saxony 1st trimester: 2nd quartile OR=0.99 (95%CI=0.86, 1.14), 3rd OR=0.91 (95%CI=0.73, 1.14) 4th OR=0.97 (95%CI=0.72, 1.31) 5th OR=0.74 (95%CI=0.51, 1.06) $p=0.06$. Alternative analysis methods found associations between rise in temperature and higher LBW risk. Inconsistent findings.
121.	Jensen (2013)	68 countries and territories worldwide (all continents)	Data not provided	1°C increase in Tmax reduces birth weight by 23gm (0.75% change), $2^{\circ}\text{C}=45\text{gm}$ (1.46%), $3^{\circ}\text{C}=68\text{gm}$ (2.21% change). All significant. Reduction in birth weight by 1.05% per 1°C in range $20\text{--}25^{\circ}\text{C}$. LBW increases with Tmax ($p < 0.001$) and Tmin ($p < 0.001$)
122.	Bruckner (2014)	Uppsala, Sweden	N=13 657	Birth weight NS finding, coefficient=-0.24 (95%CI=-0.66, 0.18)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
123.	Dadvand (2014)	Barcelona, Spain	N=6 438. N LBW=190	LBW and Tmean over whole pregnancy. LBW OR=1.21 (95%CI=0.98, 1.49) per quartile increase in temperature [ES Q4 vs Q1=1.77; SE=0.47]. IQR= 2.4°C
124.	Grace (2015)	Burkina Faso, Central African Republic, Ethiopia, Guinea, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, Sierra Leone, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe (19 countries)	N=61 075. N LBW=6 694	Change in weight (gm) per day >100°F. 3 months pre-conception -0.45 (p<0.1), 1st trimester -0.71 (p<0.01), 2nd trimester -0.85 (p<0.001), 3rd trimester -0.24 (NS). Larger estimates with temperature threshold >105°F. LBW rises with temperature. Regression coefficient for LBW with n days >100°F 3 months pre-conception -0.17 (NS), 1st trimester -0.20 (p<0.1), 2nd trimester -0.33 (p<0.01), 3rd trimester -0.17 (NS). Also significant findings with days above 105°F
125.	Kloog (2015)	Massachusetts, USA	N=462 400. N LBW not provided	Birth weight. In predicted and weather station measures, at lag0_7d, lag0_14d, lag30d, 3rd trimester and all pregnancy, weight decreased with increased IQR temperature. With predicted temperature, 3rd trimester impacts larger than entire pregnancy impacts or the impacts in lag0_7d. Term birth weight was -5.0gm per IQR over all pregnancy (95%CI=-7.8, -2.3), -8.9gm (95%CI=-16.2, -1.5) at lag0_7d, but -16.6gm (95%CI=-27.4, -5.9) in lag30d and -16.7gm (95%CI=-29.7, -3.7) in 3rd trimester [ES=33.4; SE=13.3]. NS weather station temperature birth weight associations. LBW. OR for LBW with IQR rise in predictive temperature over entire pregnancy=1.04 (95%CI=0.96, 1.13). [ES=1.08; SE=0.087], and with weather station measures OR=1.02 (95%CI=0.45, 2.30)
126.	Yitshak-Sade (2016)	southern Israel	959	Temperature elevation (per 1°C) and birth weight (grams). Entire pregnancy 0.002g (95%CI -0.003, -0.0005; p<0.05), third trimester 0.02g (95% CI -0.04g, -0.008g; p<0.05) and last month of pregnancy -0.005g (95%CI -0.009, -0.002; p<0.05). Temperature IQR elevation in the third trimester was associate with 0.002g (95%CI -0.004, -0.001g) decrease in birth weight.

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
127.	Ngo (2016)	Manhattan, New York, USA	N=514 104	Birth weight inverted U-shape. Compared to 45-65°F. Each extra day of >85 °F in 1st trimester BW -1.12gm (p<0.1). 2nd trimester -1.15gm (p<0.05). Cumulative impact during whole of pregnancy birth weight -1.7gm (p<0.10). LBW Each extra day of >85°F probability of LBW in 2nd trimester increases 0.00046 (p<0.10). Other comparisons NS and small.
128.	Diaz (2016)	Madrid, Spain	N=298 705. LBW=3 290	LBW. NS association between a 'heat wave' week (mean Tmax in week >34) and term LBW (data not provided)
129.	Andalon (2016)	Colombia	N=1 250 000. N LBW=22 500	Birth weight. 'Heat shock' (temperature in ≥1 month anytime during pregnancy that is >0.7 z-scores from long-term mean (1901–1997): birth weight -3.6gm (p<0.05, SE: 1.62). LBW -0.1% NS
130.	Poeran (2016)	Netherlands (whole country)	n=1 460 401	Results are change in birth weight (gm) per 1°C increase in mean Tmin. 2nd trimester 0.4 (95%CI=0.0, 0.8; p<0.05). 3rd trimester 1.5 (95%CI=1.2, 1.7; p<0.001). T max. reduction in weight per 1°C increase: conception day +/- 3d) -0.4 (95%CI=-0.8, -0.1; p<0.001). 1st trimester -2.1 (95%CI=-2.4, -1.7; p<0.001). 2nd trimester -2.4 (95%CI=-2.8, -2.0; p<0.01). 3rd trimester -2.1 (95%CI=-2.5, -1.8; p<0.001). Lag0d -0.4 (95%CI=-0.6, -0.1; p<0.01).
131.	Rashid (2017)	Matlab, Bangladesh	N=3 267. N LBW=997	Daily Tmean correlated with outcome. Weight rises 5.97gm per 1°C temperature in week 12 (p=0.052), 4.7gm in week 19 (p=0.028). Reduction in birth weight at lag6weeks in some analyses.
132.	MacVicar (2017)	Kanungu District, Uganda	N=3 691. N LBW=237	Per 1°C increase in Tmean, birth weight increased 41.8gm in 3rd trimester (95%CI=0.64, 82.92). Other trimesters NS, low point estimates. Entire pregnancy change per 1°C temperature=26.03 (95%CI=35.33, 87.40). Driest season (June-Aug), 1°C increase in mean temperature in 3rd trimester=123.06gm rise (95%CI=18.95, 227.18; p<0.05). Rainy season (Sept.-Nov) 98.37gm rise per 1°C (95%CI=23.04, 173.7; p<0.05). Other seasons NS. LBW NS association (data not provided).
133.	Ha (2017)	12 sites across USA	N=220 572. N LBW=4 322	>95th percentile for temperature vs <95th. LBW preconception RR=1.01 (95%CI=0.88, 1.17); 1st trimester RR=1.02 (95%CI=0.88, 1.17); 2nd trimester RR=1.06 (95%CI=0.92, 1.22); 3rd trimester RR=1.31 (95%CI=1.15, 1.50); all pregnancy RR=2.49 (95%CI=2.20, 2.83)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
134.	Molina (2017)	Bolivia, Colombia, and Peru (Andean region)	N=86 021	Birth weight 19.7gm lower with 1SD above historical Tmean (p<0.01) in whole pregnancy period [ES=39.4; SE=7.64]. 1st trimester 1SD above mean lower birth weight by 16.4gm (p<0.05). 2nd and 3rd trimester NS. LBW 0.7% increase in absolute % of LBW with each SD > historical Tmean (p<0.05 [ES=1.014 (2sd); SE=0.007])
135.	Sienkiewicz (2018)	Podlaskie Province, Poland	N=205 cases, 205 controls	LBW. NS association between Tmean and LBW (data not provided)
136.	Li (2018a)	Brisbane, Australia	N=237 585	Birth weight. Tmax >30°C (reference group) vs 25–30 °C, 20–25°C, ≤20°C. Mean birth weight 1st week and 1st 4 weeks NS. lag7d >30°C vs 25-30°C 0.006kg (95%CI=0.000, 0.013;pP=0.066); 20–25°C 0.011kg (95%CI=0.008, 0.018; p=0.041), ≤20°C 0.018kg (95%CI=0.010, 0.031; p=0.024). lag028 >30°C vs 25-30°C 0.003kg (95%CI=-0.004, 0.011; p=0.349), 20–25°C 0.013kg (95%CI=0.002, 0.024; p=0.021) ≤20°C 0.008kg (95%CI=-0.016, 0.033; p=0.527). 'almost linear' relationship (stepwise)
137.	Kloog (2018)	Southern Israel	N=56 141. N LBW=1 716	LBW U shape (base +/- 20°C). Quartile 25-75 is reference group. Entire pregnancy Tmean exposure >75th OR=1.17 (95%CI=0.99, 1.38) 1st trimester Tmean >75th centile OR=1.03 (95%CI=0.82, 1.31); 2nd trimester OR=1.14 (95%CI=0.92, 1.41), 3rd trimester OR=1.02 (95%CI=0.92, 1.12). No lags significant.
138.	Weng (2018)	Taiwan, China	N=2 045 748. N LBW data not provided	LBW. Temperature at birth. Temperature 21.5-23.4°C (reference group). Temperature 23.5-25.4°C RR=1.05 (95%CI=1.02, 1.07). Temperature 25.5-27.4°C RR=1.07 (95%CI=1.04, 1.09). Temperature 27.5-29.4°C RR=1.09 (95%CI=1.07, 1.12). Temperature 29.5-30.8°C RR=1.07 (95%CI=1.04, 1.10)
139.	Basu (2018)	California, USA	N=2 076 230. N LBW=43,629	LBW. U-shaped in 1st, 3rd trimester and overall (base 12.8°C to 18.3°C). Linear in 2nd trimester. Reference value temperature above which OR rises. Apparent temperature (temperature and relative humidity). All outcomes are % change in OR of LBW per 10°F increase in temperature. Whole of pregnancy 13.0% (95%CI=4.1, 22.7) [ES 3X 10°F above base=1.09; SE=0.03]. 1st trimester -7.4% (95%CI=-12.5, -2.0). 2nd trimester 1.7% (95%CI=0.3, 3.2). 3rd trimester 15.8% (95%CI=5.0, 27.6). Lag0_28d NS, Lag0_14d 2.6% (95%CI=0.2, 5.0).

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
140.	Son (2019)	Seoul, South Korea	N=813 820. N term LBW=12 298	LBW. Heat Index (air temperature and relative humidity). HR for a quartile increase in heat index. Term LBW NS: whole pregnancy HR=1.01 (95%CI=0.96, 1.05) [ES Q4 vs Q1=1.018; SE=0.07]; lag028 HR=1.01 (95%CI=0.99, 1.02)
141.	Sun (2019)	403 counties across USA	N=29 597 735	Birth weight. Daily Tmean. Reference temperature 40-50th centiles. Entire pregnancy temperatures. Birth weight (difference in gm compared to reference group) >90th difference=-15gm (95%CI=-17, -13). 80-90th difference=-11gm (95%CI=-12, -9). Impacts in 2nd, 3rd trimesters were similar to temperature impacts in all pregnancy. Temperature 1st trimester NS, point estimates around 1.0. Largest impacts were in marine and cold/very cold climate zones. Inverse U-shape
142.	Lawrence (2020)	New York State, United States	22 615 cases of low birthweight, term newborns (<2500g) and 129 168 controls	One EHE90 exposure associated with LBW during first trimester, compared with no exposure OR=1.09 (95%CI=1.02, 1.16). One exposure occurrence to EHE97 during entire pregnancy and during trimester one, was associated with LBW; OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.01, 1.09) and OR=1.11 (95%CI=1.06, 1.16) respectively. Two day long EHE97 was associated with increase in LBW overall pregnancy OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.02, 1.09) and the first trimester OR=1.10 (95%CI=1.05, 1.15) with the strongest association for ≥3 d in the first trimester OR 1.13 (95%CI=1.03, 1.24). Occurrence of one EHE in the first trimester was associated with a decrease in mean birthweight for EHE90 -20.95g (95%CI=-33.57,-8.19) and EHE97 -11.89g (95%CI=-20.84, -2.94). EHE90 duration for 3 days was associated with overall -10.57g (95%CI=-19.77, -1.37) and the first trimester -22.34 g (95% CI=-37.75, -6.92) decrease in mean birthweight. The strongest association was observed for EHE97 for duration ≥3 d during the first trimester -34.19 g (95%CI=-52.96, -15.43).
143.	Ilango (2020)	California, US	N=1 967 300. N preterm births=127 039	May-September. Increasing associations with increasing duration of HW. HR size increases from 75th, to 90th, 95th, 98th used as a threshold for HW definition. HR ranged from 1.01 (95%CI: 1.00, 1.02) for HW 2 days >75th centile to 1.13 (95%CI=1.05, 1.21) with 4 days >98th centile
144.	Davenport (2020)	Malawi, Mali, Nigeria, Zimbabwe,	53 592 live births, 5 277 low birth weight	Linear Probability Models. No statistically significant result in relationship between low birth weight and temperature. As proportion of days between 95°F and 99°F increases by 10%, the likelihood of a low birth weight baby

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
		Madagascar, Senegal, Kenya, Uganda, Lesotho, Burkina Faso, Guinea, Rwanda, Zambia, Siera Leone, Liberia		decreases by 0.09% (p=0.069). As the proportion of days between 100 - 104°F increases by 10%, the likelihood of a low weight baby increases by 0.04% (p=0.898). As the proportion of days > 104°F increases by 10%, the likelihood of a low birth weight baby increases by 0.4% (p=0.188). In this model, there is some impact of heat. for every 10% increase in the proportion of days within 95-99°F, there is a 1.04% increase in the likelihood of low birth weight (p < 0.01)
145.	Jakpor (2020)	Poitiers, Nancy, and Brittany, France	4 589 mother-child pairs	No statistically significant association between Tmean and term birthweight. The association trended downwards. Association between SD of temperature and term birthweight between weeks 6 to 20; cumulative change in term birthweight was -124,5g (95%CI= -228.0; -20.9).
146.	Cho (2020)	162 cities, South Korea	N=2 300 000. N LBW not provided	No significant association between LBW and daily temperature >32°C, or 30-32°C, 0-12 months after weather event, relative to 28-30°C. At month 0 after weather event, r=-0.12 (SE 0.025) for exposure to daily Tmax >32°C relative to 28-30°C. At month 3 r=0.006 (SE 0.021) for exposure to daily Tmax >32°C relative to 28-30°C
147.	Chen (2020)	145 counties in 31 provinces, China	637 033 live singleton births	Additional day during gestation with temperature above 28°C relative to a day in 0-4°C range, leads to reduction in birth weight by 0.050% (1.66g, SE0.022, p<0.01). Exposure to an additional hot day above 28°C during gestation increases the probability of LBW by 0.035% (SE0.017, p<0.05). Effects of an additional day above 28°C relative to 0-4°C had significant effects in trimester 1 and trimester 3 (T1 log birth weight -0.031 (SE0.012, p<0.05) an T3 log birth weight -0.035 (SE 0.014, p<0.05, T3 LBW 0.037 (SE0.016, p<0.05). An additional day at 24-28°C relative to 0-4°C day, increased probability of LBW by 0.021% (SE0.010, p<0.05)
148.	Grace (2021)	Mali	9 542 children	Higher number of exposure to days over 100°F associated linearly with lower predicted birthweight in trimester 1,2 and 3 (r=0.94 for all trimesters)
149.	Du (2021)	Jinan City, Shandong Province, China	N = 6 202, n=78(1.26%)	High vs median temperature on whole of pregnancy an unadjusted OR=2.86 (95%CI=1.31, 5.53). No other results are statistically significant, but in same direction of effect, notably after approx. week 31 in dlnm model. U-shape non-linear relationship noted.

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
150.	Basagana (2021)	Israel	624 940 singleton term births	U-shaped association between odds of term birth weight according to climate zone specific centiles of average daily Tmean relative to the 41-50th centile. Whole pregnancy. Mean decrease of -10g (95%CI=-16, -3) at 71-80th percentile, -20g (95%CI=-17, -14) at 81-90th percentile and -65g (95%CI=-72, -58) above the 90th centile compared with the reference range. Positive association between term LBW for the pregnancy as a whole for 81-90th OR=1.24 (95%CI=1.12, 1.36) and OR=1.58 (95%CI 1.43, 1.74) >90th percentile. The biggest effects were observed in the third trimester for heat exposure >90th percentile compared to the reference range: -51g (95%CI=-59, -43) and OR=1.65 (95%CI=1.47, 1.86). In the DLNM models, associations between term birth weight and GA-week specific exposures to temperature above the 90th percentile were inverse during the GA weeks 3-9, 19-35, with the strongest associations estimated for hot temperature during GA week 3 -3.8g (95%CI=-7.1g, -0.4g) and during GA weeks 26-27 (-2.6g (95%CI=-4.6, -0.5). Associations between term LBW and GA-week specific temperature above the 90th percentile were close to the null through entire pregnancy.
151.	Tapia (2021)	Lima, Peru	N= 123 034 N(term births for LBW analysis)= 114 137 n= 2074(1.78%)	Comparing IQR of Tmax with Q1 as reference, Q4 Tmax in third trimester showed reduction in weight: -30.6g (95%CI=-37.67, -23.59) and decreased Z-score= -0.07 (95%CI=-0.097,-0.061). Protective effect noted in first trimester. When stratified to include only term births, effect was greater. For Q4 Tmax -33.0g (95%CI=-40.14, -25.86). LBW. Tmax in 3rd trimester OR=1.13 (95%CI=1.02,1.27) when stratified by PM2.5
152.	Zhang (2021)	Henan, China	1 539 117 births (5 790 low birth weights infants)	LBW associated with each SD unit increment in Tmean during entire pregnancy OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.02,1.09) and during second trimester OR=1.09 (95%CI=1.05,1.133. Exposure to extreme heat in the entire pregnancy and during second trimester increased the risk of LBW OR=1.25 (95%CI=1.14, 1.37), OR for trimester 2=1.19 (95%CI=1.08-1.31)
153.	Yitshak-Sade (2021)	Massachusetts, USA	N=712 438 term births	Positive non-significant difference in birth weight with higher temperatures. A 1°C rise in temperature from 23 to 24°C=-7.9g (95%CI =11.2; -4.6g). Cumulative exposure to a weekly temperature of 30°C=-133.4g (95%CI=-191.1; -80.12) and 22°C=-75.7g (95%CI -109.0; -35.7). Exposure to temperature

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				at 95th (23°C) percentile relative to the 5th percentile (-4°C) associated with a reduction in birthweight in weeks 0-16 and 29-37 of gestation.
154.	Khodadi (2022)	Ahvaz, Iran	150 766 women (863 low birth weight)	Hot thermal stress (UTCI) not associated with cumulative relative risk of LBW at lag 0d, 0_2d, 0_6d, 0_13d and 0_21d. For lag0d cumulative RR=0.89 (95%CI=0.38, 2.12) and for lag0_6d, cumulative RR=1.37 (95%CI=0.54, 3.49)
155.	Requia (2022)	Brazil(entire country, split by region)	N = 1 047 330 n = 51 245(4.89%)	Results stratified by region. North region positive and statistically significant results, other regions similar effects in some sub-analyses(e.g. temp 26-30°C). Maximum effect noted in second trimester with % increase in OR of LBW of 5.16%(95%CI=3.60, 6.74). South region with statistically significant protective effects of heat exposure on LBW.
156.	Bakhtisityarava (2022)	Brazil, Mexico and Chile	8 079 872 live births in Brazil. 6 405 777 live births in Mexico. 890 156 live births in Chile	Brazil. Tmean during entire gestation of 22.3°C and 37.4°C (50th and 95th percentiles) associated with a -10.41g (95%CI=-16.28; -4.54) and -36.99g (95%CI=-45.50; -28.49) decrease in birthweight as compared to 19°C. Mexico, a gestation average temperature of 28° C (95th percentile) associated with -8.55g (95%CI=-16.43; -0.68) decrease in birthweight as compared to 19°C. Chile. No statistical significance at increased temperatures. 23°C vs 19°C associated increased weight: 18 g (95%CI= -40, 50]. Significant decrease in birthweight associated with 5°C higher temperature in months 2,3,6, 7-9 of gestation in Brazil and 7, 8 and 9 months of gestation in Mexico relative to 19°C gestation average (month 9 in Brazil: -6.64g (95%CI=-9,0; -3,8) and month 9 in Mexico: -5.7g (95%CI=-7.8; -3.3))
157.	Carlson (2022)	Boston, United States	4 442 mother-child dyads	Weeks 10-29. 1°C increase in SD HI was associated with -16.3 g (95%CI=-5.4, -27.4) change in birth weight. The cumulative change in birthweight for this period was -287.4 g (95%CI=-474.1 g, -100.8 g). Effect of a 1°C increase in SD HI for each week in the second trimester was associated with a -201 change in term birth weight (95%CI=-334 g, -69 g), which was larger than the effect size for SD temperature (1°C increase in SD temperature=-151 g (95%CI=-283 g, -18 g).
158.	Conte Keivabu (2022)	50 provincial capital cities, Spain	N=4 314 381. N PTB=259 383	Percent increase in outcome per additional day at >32°C versus days at 5-25°C. LBW: 0.016 per day, p>0.05. VLBW 0.006, p>0.05.

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
159.	Cil (2022)	United States	34 700 000 births. N LBW = 2 197 793 (Converted from rate per 1000). ICD-10 low birthweight code: P07.1	For each additional day between 80-90°F, LBW increases by 0.026 per 1,000 (0.1% of mean; p<0.01), and VLBW by 0.008 per 1,000 (0.1% of mean; p<0.5). The same above-2 SD heat day appears to decrease the probability of LBW when pregnancies had greater exposure to winter months (i.e. low-exposure group); -0.023 (p<0.05) for VLBW
160.	Leung (2023)	Boston, Massachusetts, USA	8 641 term deliveries	Reduction in mean z-score of birthweight associated with a 5°C higher cumulative temperature exposure over entire pregnancy, -0.32 (95%CI=-0.51, -0.12) for term deliveries.
Neonatal admissions				
161.	Kakkad (2014)	Ahmedabad, India	N births=2 025. N admission=554. N heat related admissions=36	Per 1°C increase in daily Tmax ≥42°C, 43% increase in neonatal heat-related admissions (95%CI=9.2, 88%). Non-heat-related admissions 1% increase per 1°C when temperature ≥40°C (P=0.83). Moving to lower floor (reportedly hot top floor to reportedly cooler lower floor) 64% reduced heat-related admissions at 42°C (95%CI=3, 89%). 14% reduced non-heat-related admission when moving to a lower level at 42°C (P=0.13)
162.	Zhao (2019)	1814 cities, Brazil	N=49 145 997. N admissions not reported	Percentage increase in hospitalisation related to perinatal conditions lag07d per 5°C increase in daily Tmean=7.4% (95%CI=6.0, 8.5). Early hot season=8.3% (95%CI=6.7, 9.9; p<0.001). Late hot season=7.7% (95%CI=6.0, 9.4, P<0.001).
163.	Zhao (2019)	1814 cities, Brazil	N total admissions= 58 400 682. N perinatal admissions not reported	Risk of hospitalization for perinatal conditions higher during heatwaves for all 12 definitions of heatwaves. Perinatal admissions increase 5-33%. HW >97.5 th centile for 4 days 33% increase. HW >95 th centile 3 days=10% increase (95%CI=8, 12%)
164.	Cil (2022)	USA	N births= 34 700 000 births. N NICU admissions= 2 573 872	Additional day with Tmean above 90°F leads to additional 0.153 per 1000 NICU admissions (0.2% of mean; p<0.10). In births with greater exposure to summer months during gestation (i.e. high exposure group), an additional hot day with temperatures 2-3SD above the mean leads to an additional 0.295 NICU admissions per 1000 births (0.4% of the mean; p<0.01).

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
Neonatal morbidity				
165.	Scrafford (2013)	Sarlahi District, southern Nepal	N=18 985. N referred for jaundice=556	Increase per 1°C increase in Tmin RR=1.04. (RR 95%CI=1.03, 1.06). Neonatal jaundice diagnosed by visual assessment
166.	Andalon (2016)	Columbia	N=1 477 011 births	During HW (various definitions) Apgar 0.2 to 0.6% lower probability of being normal (p<0.05). Largest impacts with 2nd and 3rd trimester exposure. Maximum OR during 2nd trimester for HW 1.5-2.0 SD above historical mean 1.01 (SE=0.001)
167.	Cil (2017)	3000 counties, USA	N=570 000	HW (temperature and relative humidity >threshold). Exposure ≥1 HW in a trimester (or 3 months before conception). Additional cases/1000 births. HW 3rd trimester increased foetal distress 2.07 (SE=0.95; p<0.05). Other trimesters same direction, but NS. Assisted breathing of newborn on ventilator for >30 minutes NS. Meconium aspiration syndrome (inhalation of meconium by foetus/newborn affecting respiratory system) 2nd trimester increased 0.37 (SE=0.21, p<0.1) and 3rd trimester 0.41 (se=0.23, p<0.1). Any of the 3 outcomes. 3rd trimester increased 2.95 (SE=1.22; p<0.05). 1st increased by 2.23 (SE=1.20 p<0.1) and 2nd trimester 2.20 (SE=1.13, p<0.1).
168.	Tang (2021)	Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region, China	N=182 322 deliveries N=1 575 low Apgar scores	Compared to moderate temperature exposure, prenatal exposure to extreme heat (>90 th centile) associated with 13.9-47.9% increased risk of low Apgar scores in prenatal exposure windows. At lag1d, odds of lower Apgar score OR=1.31 (95%CI=1.07, 1.60). At lag0_7, odds of lower Apgar score OR=1.26 (95%CI=1.03, 1.55). At lag0_30d, odds of lower Apgar score OR=1.24 (95%CI=1.02, 1.53) with exposure to extreme heat
169.	Iijima (2021)	Hamatsu, Japan	N=3 344	Tmean lagd0 correlated with total serum bilirubin (p=0.04) (higher temperatures, lower bilirubin). Higher in summer than winter.
170.	Chen (2022)	Guangzhou, China	N=64 270 neonatal observations	For each unit increase in extreme temperature, corresponding 0.265 decrease in sum of Apgar scores. Apgar score will decrease by 0.008 (0.029%) when duration of extreme temperature (>95 th or <5 th percentile) increases by a day.

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
Neonatal mortality				
171.	Weng (2018)	Taiwan	N=2 045 748. N neonate deaths not reported.	Temperature at birth: Baseline: 21.5-23.4°C. 25.5-27.4°C RR=1.28 (95%CI=0.94, 1.73); 27.5-29.4°C RR=1.20 (95%CI=0.92, 1.57); 29.5-30.8°C RR=1.08 (95%CI=0.74, 1.57)
Preterm birth				
172.	Lajinian (1997)	Brooklyn, New York, USA	N not provided	Heat-humidity index (humidity, dry bulb temperature), calculated for 4 periods, each 7 days: coldest and hottest weeks in winter and summer. N PTB in that week/total pregnancies 20-36 weeks in that week. Coldest winter week 1.23% (12/972; HI=25.0); hottest winter week 1.25% (12/961; HI=42.7); coldest summer week 2.00% (21/1031; HI=63.3); hottest summer week 3.00% (30/1008; HI=79.5). Linear trend of % PTB over the 4 weeks P<0.002
173.	Porter (1999)	Chicago, USA	N=11 792. N PTB not provided	Maximum apparent temperatures categorised as <90°F, 90°F to 99°F, 100°F to 109°F, ≥110°F. NS for any comparisons of mean gestation. Lag0d: <90°F=38.6w. 90-99°F=38.7w. 100-110°F=38.7w. ≥110°F=38.9w. Lag1d <90°F=38.7w. 90-99°F=38.7w. 100-110°F=38.8w. ≥110°F=38.7w. Lag2d <90°F=38.6w. 90-99°F=38.7w. 100-110°F=38.8w. ≥110°F=38.8w. All comparisons NS
174.	Tustin (2004)	Dunedin, New Zealand	N=7 039. N PTB not provided	In each year, the 3 months with highest Tmean (peaks) compared with 3 months when Tmean were lowest (trough). All comparisons P>0.05. 1st trimester mean gestation weeks in peak months=36.7 (SD=0.05) vs mean gestation weeks in trough months=39.6 (SD=0.05). 2nd trimester mean gestation weeks in peak months=39.6 vs mean gestation weeks in trough months=39.7. 3rd trimester mean gestation weeks in peak months=39.6 (SD=0.05) vs mean gestation weeks in trough months=39.7 (SD=0.05)
175.	Yackerson (2008)	Negev, Israel	N=11 979. N PTB=992	PTB and Tmax regression coefficient=-0.09 (SE=0.03, p=0.008). Significant increase in PTB with change in temp (Tmax-Tmin regression) lag3d coefficient p=0.01.
176.	Lee (2008)	North West Thames region, London, United Kingdom	N=482 765. N PTB=29 716	Lag1d, 2d, 3d, 4d, 5d, 6d OR around 1.0, NS. lag0d daily Tmax OR=1.00 (95%CI=0.99, 1.00) daily Tmin OR=1.00 (95%CI=1.00, 1.00)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
177.	Basu (2010)	12 counties of California, USA	N PTB=58 681	8.6% increase (95%CI=6.0, 11.3) in PTB with a 10°F increase in mean apparent temperature in lag0_6d [ES 3X10°F=1.047; SE=0.007]. All lags day 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 were associated. Association strongest for PTB at weeks 34-35
178.	Dadvand (2011)	Barcelona, Spain	N=7 585. N PTB not provided	Temperature baseline (1983-2006). Regression coefficient is change in gestational days and exposure to HI90, HI95 and HI99 heat indexes. 90th centile: lag1d coefficient=-0.9 (95%CI=-2.1, 0.4; p=0.17). lag2d coefficient=-1.0 (95%CI=-2.1, 0.0; p=0.06. HI95 lag0d coefficient=-0.2 (95%CI=-0.4, -0.1; P<0.01). lag1d coefficient=-1.6 (95%CI=-3.5, 0.2; p=0.08). HI99 centile Lag1d coefficient=-5.3 (95%CI=-10.1, -0.5; p=0.03). lag1d estimates increase from 90th to 95th to 99th centile (dose response pattern)
179.	Wolf (2012)	Saxony and Brandenburg, Germany	Saxony: N=162 913, N PTB=10 277. Brandenburg: N=128 604, N PTB =8 717.	Comparisons of Tmean in quintile (baseline, coldest to hottest). Brandenburg. PTB 1st trimester 2nd quintile OR=1.00 (95%CI=0.92, 1.09), 3rd quintile OR=0.91 (95%CI=0.79, 1.04), 4th quintile OR=1.01 (95%CI=0.85, 1.20), 5th quintile OR=0.91 (95%CI=0.75, 1.10; p=0.06). All other comparisons NS. Saxony PTB 1st trimester: 2nd quintile OR=0.93 (95%CI=0.87, 1.01), 3rd quintile R=0.99 (95%CI=0.88, 1.11), 4th quintile OR=1.02 (95%CI=0.87, 1.19), 5th quintile OR=1.13 (95%CI=0.92, 1.37; p=0.09). Inconsistent findings
180.	Strand (2012)	Brisbane, Australia	N=101 870. N PTB not provided	Temperature in lag0_28d. Increasing temperature increased HR at gestation 28-36 weeks (significant), but NS at <28 weeks gestation. HR for PTB 28-36 weeks similar at lag0_7d to lag0_-28d. HR PTB lag0_28d 28-36 weeks gestation=1.20 at 27°C vs 21°C (95%CI=1.0, 1.40)
181.	Wang (2013)	Brisbane, Australia	N=50 848. N PTB=3 347	9 definitions of heat waves (90th centile, 95th, 98th, duration 2-4d). HR for exposure to ≥1 HW day in lag0_7d. All 9 definitions significant HR from 1.13 (95%CI=1.03, 1.24) to 2.00 (95%CI=1.37, 2.91). Highest HR with HW defined as >98th centile, 4 days duration.
182.	Schifano (2013)	Rome, Italy	N=132 691. N PTB 22-32 weeks=847. N PTB 33-36 weeks=6 412	Apparent temperature (includes air and dew-point temperature). Only lag0_2d significant in warm season (April-Dec). Percent change of 1.87% (95%CI=0.86, 2.87) per 1°C increase in temperature. 20.93% increase per IQR increase (95%CI=9.37, 33.72). Analysis by gestation, impact only significant for 33-36 weeks gestation: 1.93% change (95%CI=0.88, 2.98) vs 22-32 weeks: -1.02% change (95%CI not provided). Percent change in daily n PTB=19.21%

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				for HW days compared with non-HW days (95%CI=7.91, 31.69). HW defined as >2 days with Tmax >monthly 90th centile or daily Tmin >monthly 90th centile, and Tmax >median monthly value over time. NS impact in cold season. PTB-temperature association linear in warm season, also in cold season, but less steep slope
183.	Auger (2014)	Montreal, Quebec, Canada	N=206 929. N PTB=12 390	Tmax in week before childbirth and risk of delivery. Preterm: 3 consecutive days $\geq 32^{\circ}\text{C}$ HR=0.92 (95%CI=0.7, 1.14). N days $\geq 32^{\circ}\text{C}$, HR compared to 0 days. 1d HR=0.98 (95%CI=0.91, 1.06); 2d HR=1.03 (95%CI=0.90, 1.18); 3d HR=0.91 (95%CI=0.72, 1.15); 4-7d HR=0.82 (95%CI=0.55, 1.21). Early term (37-39w): HR compared to 0 days $\geq 32^{\circ}\text{C}$. 1d HR=1.02 (95%CI=0.98, 1.06); 2d HR=0.96 (95%CI=0.89, 1.04); 3d HR=1.08 (95%CI=0.97, 1.21); 4-7d HR=1.27 (95%CI=1.07, 1.52); 3 consecutive days $\geq 32^{\circ}\text{C}$ HR=1.17 (95%CI=1.06, 1.29); 10% greater hazard of delivery at 35°C relative to 20°C ($p<0.05$)
184.	Bruckner (2014)	Uppsala, Sweden	N=13 657. N PTB not provided	Compared to 50th centile, logHR of PTB rose with temperature. >75th centile PTB increased HR=1.52 (95%CI=1.22, 1.90) per 1°C increase in temperature vs 50th centile. J-shape (inflection at 7.5°C)
185.	Kent (2014)	Alabama, USA	N=543 980. N PTB=60 466	Positive associations between heat wave indices and PTB for 9/15 heat wave definitions. Heat index of daily Tmean >95th centile for ≥ 2 consecutive days: Lag6d. 11.6% (95%CI=0.9, 23.4%) higher % PTB on heat wave versus non-heat wave days. Heat Index of daily Tmean >98th centile for ≥ 2 days: 32.4% (95%CI=3.7, 69.1%). Heat indices using mean daily temperatures increased from 90th centile (1.5% higher PTB; 95%CI=-3.5, 6.9%) to 95th and 98th centiles (higher point estimates with increased cut-off value). NS for PTB and apparent temperature HIs. In 10/15 heat indices, the longer the duration of heat waves the larger the point estimate of associations (unknown if significant). Associations between heat wave days and the outcomes similar between 1st heat wave of the season and later ones, and between early and late-season heat waves
186.	Vicedo-Cabrera (2014)	Valencia, Spain	N=20 148. N PTB=1067	Apparent temperature measures. Tmax >50th centile vs <50th. Lag2d RR=1.17 (95%CI=0.99, 1.38). Lag3d RR=1.12 (95%CI=1.01, 1.24). Lag 8, 10, 11, 14days also significant (RR=1.02, 1.06). Tmax >90th centile vs <50th. Lag2d

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				RR=1.23 (95%CI=1.00, 1.52). Lag day 9, 10, 11, 12 also significant RR 1.06-1.07. Tmin. >50th centile vs <50th Lag days 4, 5 significant RR=1.04-1.05. 90th centile lag day 3, 4, 5, 6 significant RR=1.05 to 1.07
187.	Carmichael (2014)	468 counties, across the country, USA	N black=2 607 150. N black PTB=422 358. N white= 6 986 984. N white PTB=656 777	No overall population measures, only subpopulations (black and white women). Fit a multiple linear regression with socioeconomic and demographic features, environmental variables, and health-related variables from birth certificates. Report R(squared) and p value of individual variables. Warmer climate was associated with higher PTB in black and white women. Regression coefficient for warmer climate in black women 0.020 (NS) and 0.114 (p<0.001) for deliveries in weeks 20-31 and 32-36. For white women, regression coefficient is 0.010 (p<0.001) and 0.060 (p<0.001) for deliveries in weeks 20-31 and 32-36 weeks.
188.	Vicedo-Cabrera (2015)	Stockholm, Sweden	N=36 577. N PTB=1 204	Moderate heat: RR increase in daily Tmean from annual median value to 75th centile of warm season. Lag0_21d NS RR=1.02-1.03. Lag22d RR=1.04 (95%CI=1.00, 1.08). Lag0_23d RR=1.04 (95%CI=1.00, 1.08). Lag0_24d RR=1.04 (95%CI=1.00, 1.09). Lag0_25d RR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00, 1.09). Lag0_26d RR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00, 1.10). Lag0_27d RR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00, 1.11). Lag0_28d RR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00, 1.11). Slope of maximum cumulative temperature RR=2.50 (95%CI=1.02, 6.15) at 75th centile. Extreme heat >99th vs 75th centile of warm NS and point estimates around 1.0
189.	Kloog (2015)	Whole state of Massachusetts, USA	N=462 400. N PTB=11 993	Temperatures both from predictive modelling and weather stations. PTB with predicted temperature per IQR change in mean temperature in whole pregnancy OR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.05); OR=1.07 (95%CI=0.87, 1.27) [ES for 2 IQR change=1.05; SE=0.007] with temperature from weather stations. Some models using predictive temperatures showed increases gestation at higher temperatures, while weather station data showed gestation decrease
190.	Muresan (2016)	Cluj-Napoca, Transylvania, Romania	N PTB=138	Weekly Tmean and SD of mean, correlated with PTBs in that week (52w in total, lag7d). Weekly Tmean r=0.31 (P=0.027). SD in each week r=0.307 (P=0.007)
191.	Liang (2016)	Shenzhen, China	N=1 040 638. N PTB=58 411	Reference group is median of daily Tmean. Cumulative effects of high temperature 95th centiles RR=0.69 (95%CI=0.60, 0.80) and 99th centile

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				RR=0.62 (95%CI=0.52, 0.74). Negative associations with 95th centile (all p<0.05): lag10d RR=0.99 (95%CI=0.97, 1.00); lag15d RR=0.99 (95%CI=0.98, 1.00); lag20d RR=0.99 (95%CI=0.98, 1.00); lag25d RR=0.99 (95%CI=0.98, 1.00); lag30d RR=0.99 (95%CI=0.97, 1.00). 99th centile (all p<0.05): lag10d RR=0.98 (95%CI=0.97, 1.00); lag15d RR=0.98 (95%CI=0.97, 0.99); lag20d RR=0.98 (95%CI=0.97, 0.99); lag25d RR=0.98 (95%CI=0.97, 0.99); lag30d RR=0.98 (95%CI=0.96, 1.00)
192.	He (2016)	Guangzhou, China	N=838 146. N PTB=47 209	All estimates compared to Tmean in area (24.4°C). Moderate heat (95th centile, >30.7°C): lag07d HR=1.02 (95%CI=0.98, 1.06); last 4 weeks of pregnancy HR=1.08 (95%CI=1.02, 1.13); from week 20 onwards HR=1.07 (95%CI=1.02, 1.13); cumulative exposure over pregnancy HR=1.07 (95%CI=1.02, 1.14). Extreme heat (99th centile, >31.9°C): lag07d HR=1.03 (95%CI=0.98, 1.07); last 4 weeks of pregnancy HR=1.10 (95%CI=1.03, 1.18); from week 20 onwards; 1.010 (95%CI=1.02, 1.18); cumulative exposure over pregnancy HR=1.10 (95%CI=1.02, 1.18). Extreme heat in gestation windows: weeks 20–31 HR=1.45 (95%CI=1.15, 1.83), week 32–34 HR=1.29 (95%CI=1.08, 1.54) and weeks 35–36 was 1.08 (95%CI=0.97, 1.21). At moderate and extreme heat lag07d NS and stepwise HR with periods closer to birth. U shape (base at 25°C)
193.	Walfisch (2016)	Negev, Israel	N=263 709. N PTB=20 825	RR increase in PTB per 1 heat stress unit (mean wet and dry temperature)=1.06 (95%CI=1.04, 1.08). Spontaneous PTB IRR=1.07 (95%CI=1.05, 1.10). Induced PTB IRR=0.99, (95%CI=0.97, 1.01). [lag period uncertain]. Increase in 1 heat stress unit increases PTB by 3.7% for PTD <34 weeks (higher than PTB 34-36 weeks). Linear association
194.	Schifano (2016) Rome	Rome, Italy and Barcelona, Spain	Rome: N=78 633, N PTB 22-32 weeks=484, N 33-36 weeks=3 830. Barcelona: N= 27 255. N 22-32 weeks=173, N 33-36 weeks=1 071.	Maximum apparent temperature (includes air and dew-point temperature). Lag2d used as strongest in Rome, no clear difference in lags in Barcelona. Barcelona: HR per 1°C increase=1.00 (95%CI=0.10, 1.01); HR rise with quartile increase=1.03 (95%CI=0.98, 1.07) [ES Q4 vs Q1=1.08; SE=0.065]. Highest HR per 1°C Tmax increase in 22–26 week gestation HR=1.07 (95%CI=1.04 to 1.11), decreased stepwise by gestation period (5 periods in total) to 36th week HR=1.03 (95%CI=1.02, 1.05). Significant at all gestations. Rome: HR per 1°C

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				increase=1.01 (95%CI=1.01, 1.02). HR per quartile increase=1.13 (95%CI=1.10, 1.17) [ES Q4 vs Q1=1.45; SE=0.056]. As in Barcelona, highest HR per 1°C increase in 22–26 week of gestation HR=1.07 (95%CI=1.05, 1.09) and decreased stepwise to 1.03 (95%CI=1.03, 1.04) at 36 weeks. Significant at all gestations
195.	Ngo (2016)	Manhattan, New York, USA	N=510 781. N PTB not provided	Compared to 45-65°F. Each extra day >85°F gestation -0.0039 weeks (46 min). Other comparisons NS and small.
196.	Arroyo (2016)	Madrid, Spain	N=298 705. PTB=24 620	Results for an IQR increase in Tmax >34°C. lag 1d RR=1.06 (95%CI=1.02 to 1.09) [ES IQR 1 vs IQR2=1.11; SE=0.038]. IQR not noted.
197.	Andalon (2016)	Colombia (whole country)	N=1 250 000. N PTB=193 750	'Heat shock' (temperature in ≥1 month anytime during pregnancy that is >0.7 z-scores of SD from long-term mean (1901–1997)). -0.3% point reduction in probability of full-term pregnancy (95%CI=0.0, 0.6%; p<0.05). No step-wise impacts with increase in sd (0.7–1.0 to 1.0–1.5; to 1.5–2.0 to ≥2.0). NS pattern of heat exposure and trimesters, but impacts on PTB estimates highest in 2nd and 3rd trimester
198.	Cox (2016)	Flanders, Belgium	N=807 835. N PTB=27 076	Temperature centiles over whole study period, compared to median. Tmin lag1d 95th centile RR=1.09 (95%CI=1.02, 1.15). 99th centile RR=1.16 (95%CI=1.05, 1.28). Lag3d 95th centile RR=1.10 (95%CI=1.03, 1.18). Lag6d 95th centile RR=1.09 (95%CI=1.01, 1.18). Tmax lag1d 95th centile RR=1.10(95%CI=1.01 to 1.19). 99th centile RR=1.15 (95%CI=1.01 to 1.31). NS, but <32 weeks estimates higher than 32-36
199.	Mathew (2017)	Alice springs, Northern Territory, Australia	N=16 870. N PTB total=1 401. N Indigenous= 7996. N PTB=951. N Non-indigenous=8 873 N PTB=450	Compared to 50th centile temperature for whole period (30°C). RR>1 for temperature 41-45°C (Tmax). Increase in RR about 2%. Exponential increase in RR (2-3w before delivery) about 4.5% with ≥41°C. Only significant at lag15_20 at ≥45°C. Cumulative effects of exposure to Tmax 40°C for 21d increases PTB risk 8.3% (95%CI=1.03, 1.15)
200.	Ha (2017)	12 sites across USA	N=223 375. N early PTB =3 855.	RR >90th centile vs 10-90th, reference temperatures are 3 months preconception. Early PTB: weeks 1-7 gestation RR=1.11 (95%CI=1.01, 1.21); weeks 8-14 RR=1.06 (95%CI=0.96, 1.17); weeks 15-21 RR=1.18 (95%CI=1.07, 1.29); weeks 22-28 RR=1.08 (95%CI=0.98, 1.19) [data on weeks 29-36 not

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				provided]. Late PTB: weeks 1-7 RR=1.05 (95%CI=0.99, 1.11); weeks 8-14 RR=1.01 (95%CI=0.94, 1.08); weeks 15-21 RR=1.18 (95%CI=1.11, 1.27); weeks 22-28 RR=1.00 (95%CI=0.93, 1.07). Cumulative exposure (total pregnancy exposure) to hot temp was associated with PTB in pregnancies from weeks0_34 and weeks0_36. Case-crossover analysis: Increase in odds of early PTB per 5°F increase in temperature in lag6d: OR=1.16 (95%CI=1.12, 1.19); late PTB OR=1.12 (95%CI=1.10, 1.15)
201.	Basu (2017)* (Excluded from analysis because duplicate of Avalos (2017))	N. California, USA	N PTB=14 466	Mean daily apparent temperature lag0_6 before birth vs exposures for same mother at 7 and 28d before or after that week. Results are percent change per 10°F (5.6°C) increase in apparent temperature. Warm season 11.63% (95%CI=4.08, 19.72) (ES 3x10°F=1.06; 0.022). Cold season 6.18% (95%CI=-2.96, 16.18)
202.	Avalos (2017)	Northern California, USA	N PTB=14 466	All measures are % change in PTB with 10°F (5.6°C) increase in mean apparent temperature (temperature and dew-point temperature). Warm season mean apparent temperature lag0_6d, lag4, 5, 6d significant. Lag0_6d 11.6% (95%CI=4.1%, 19.7%). Cold season lag0_6d 6.2% (95%CI=-3.0%, 16.2%)
203.	Cil (2017)	3000 counties across USA	N=570 000. N PTB not provided	HW is heat index (temperature and relative humidity) above 'established thresholds'. Exposure ≥1 HW in each trimester (or 3 months before conception). HW in 2nd trimester lower gestational age at birth (coefficient=-0.019; P<0.05; other trimesters NS)
204.	Giorgis-Allemand (2017)	Denmark, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands, United Kingdom	N=71 493. N PTB=3 533	1st trimester exposure had stronger association than 2nd trimester, 1 or 4 weeks before childbirth and whole-pregnancy. Tmean. 1st trimester temperatures, compared to PTB<5°C, OR =1.13 (95%CI=1.00, 1.27) with 5°C-9.9°C; OR=1.14 (95%CI=0.99, 1.33) with 10°C-14.9°C, OR=1.20 (95%CI=0.99, 1.45) with ≥15°C (p for test for trend=0.08).
205.	Yu (2018)	Mayagüez, Ponce and San Juan, Puerto Rico	Mayagüez: N=71 390. N PTB=11 708. Ponce: N=118 820.	Lag0_28d. San Juan (capital city), Mayagüez small temperature impacts, even reduced PTB at high temperatures. Ponce PTB rises with temperature (warmest of the 3 regions). 90th centile similar patterns. Ponce Mayagüez lag0_28d smaller impacts than lag0d. San Juan lag0_28d and lag0d similar.

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
			N PTB=18 298. San Juan: N=213 729. N PTB=34 836	29.4°C vs 26.2°C in Mayagüez, cumulative RR=0.78 (95%CI=0.68, 0.90). 28.8°C vs 26.7°C in Ponce, cumulative RR is 1.1 (95% CI: 1.03, 1.2)
206.	Li (2018)	Brisbane, Australia	N=237 585. N PTB=15 047	1st week of pregnancy; 1st 4 weeks; lag0_6d, lag0_28d. Tmax >30°C (reference group) vs 25-30°C, 20-25°C, ≤20°C categories based on distribution of temperature, effect of temperature on outcomes. Mean duration of gestation similar in temperature groups for all 4 lags (38.92-38.98w). NS. Multivariate NS
207.	Li (2018)	Brisbane, Australia	N=289 351. N PTB=22 822	Similar findings for Tmax and Tmin daily temperatures. Comparison daily Tmean 75th centile and temperature at minimum PTB prevalence. 1st trimester HR=1.04 (95%CI=0.98, 1.09). 2nd trimester HR=1.03 (95%CI=0.99, 1.07). 3rd trimester HR=1.11 (95%CI=1.08, 1.15). 95th centile vs temperature at minimum PTB prevalence 1st trimester HR=1.07 (95%CI=1.00, 1.14). 2nd trimester HR=1.03 (95%CI=0.99, 1.08). 3rd trimester HR=1.21 (95%CI=1.16, 1.26). U shape in 3rd trimester (base 19.5°C)
208.	Zhong (2018)	Changsha, Hunan Province, China	N=3 509. N PTB=141	Whole pregnancy OR=1.34 (95%CI=1.11-1.62) per 1°C increase in Tmean. OR per increase of 1°C in 1st trimester whole period NS and all seasons aside from summer OR=1.93 (95%CI=1.32-2.82). 2nd trimester whole period OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.00, 1.06), spring OR=1.51 (95%CI=1.32, 1.74), summer OR=1.77 (95%CI=1.32, 2.37). 3rd trimester whole period NS, spring OR=1.44 (95%CI=1.17, 1.76). Whole pregnancy: spring OR=1.57 (95%CI=1.24, 1.97), summer OR=1.78 (95%CI=1.06, 2.98). Winter, autumn NS, point estimate around 1.0. OR for 1d increase in extreme heat exposure (>30°C). 1st trimester OR=1.00 (95%CI=0.99, 1.02). 2nd trimester OR=1.01 (95%CI=1.00, 1.02). 3rd trimester OR=0.98 (95%CI=0.96, 0.99). Whole pregnancy OR=0.99 (95%CI=0.97, 1.00)
209.	Zheng (2018)	Changsha, Hunan Province, China	N=3 604. N PTB=145.	OR is per 0.5°C increase. High temperatures (above median in each period). Conception month: OR=1.14 (95%CI=1.04-1.24). 1st trimester high temperature OR=1.23 (95%CI=1.12-1.35). 2nd trimester OR=0.86 (95%CI=0.80-0.93; P<0.001. 3rd trimester high temperature OR=1.22 (95%CI=1.10, 1.35). Birth month high temperature (>19.9°C) OR=1.00

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				(95%CI=0.91, 1.09). Whole pregnancy high temperature (>18.2°C) OR=2.57 (95%CI=1.98, 3.33). Extreme heat day (>90th centile). Odds of PTB per 2d/m increase in extreme heat days. Conception month OR=1.15 (95%CI=1.04, 1.26). 1st trimester OR=1.10 (95%CI=0.99, 1.23). 2nd trimester OR=0.59 (95%CI=0.49, 0.70). 3rd trimester OR=1.14 (95%CI=1.04, 1.25). Birth month OR=1.10 (95%CI=1.01, 1.19). Entire pregnancy OR=1.51 (95%CI=1.05, 2.18). U shape (base 18°C)
210.	Weng (2018)	Taiwan, China	N=2 045 748. N PTB not provided	Temperature at birth. 21.5-23.4°C (reference group, lowest risk). Temperature 23.5-25.4°C RR=1.00 (95%CI=0.97, 1.02). Temperature 25.5-27.4°C RR=1.04 (95%CI=1.02, 1.07). Temperature 27.5-29.4°C RR=1.11 (95%CI=1.08, 1.13). Temperature 29.5-30.8°C RR=1.05 (95%CI=1.02, 1.08). U shape (base 23.5-25.4°C)
211.	Guo (2018)	132 cities in 30 provinces in China	N=1 020 471. N PTB=73 240. Cold area PTB n=12 433. Medium temperature area PTB n=29 266. Hot area PTB n=25 665	>95% centile of local Tmean, compared to 5-95% centile. For cold areas, NS findings, but all in direction of effect. Medium areas NS preconception, weeks 1-7 gestation, weeks 8-14, weeks 15-21, all direction of protective effect; 4 weeks before birth OR=1.16 (95%CI=1.10 to 1.22); NS 1 week before birth, direction of effect. Hot areas preconception OR=1.23 (95%CI=1.17, 1.30); weeks 1-7 OR=1.11 (95%CI=1.05, 1.17); weeks 8-14 OR=1.15 (95%CI=1.09, 1.21); weeks 15-21 OR=1.11 (95%CI=1.05 to 1.17); 4 weeks before birth OR=1.06 (95%CI=0.10 to 1.12; p=0.060); 1 week before birth OR=1.07 (95%CI=1.01 to 1.13)
212.	Wang (2019)	Brisbane, Australia	N=277 133. N PTB=17 368	Exposure in each gestation month binary variable, 6 HWs: 90th centile (2, 3, 4d duration); 95th centile (2, 3, 4d duration). All definitions and 9 month gestation HRs were significant. For most definitions, HR point estimates were highest in months 1-6. In most months, the longer the duration of HW the higher the OR. OR similar in 90th and 95th centiles, 95th lower than 90th in some comparisons. In 42 of 72 measures HR>1.20, 16 measures>1.4. HR at 90th centile 2d duration highest in month 2=1.42 (95%CI=1.29, 1.56) and lowest in month 7 HR=1.09 (95%CI=0.99, 1.20), median in month 3 HR=1.29 (95%CI=1.17, 1.42)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
213.	Wu (2019)	Wuhan city, Hubei province, China	N=11 056. N PTB=618	Diurnal temperature range=Tmax minus the Tmin on the same day. Mean range during each period. Range PTB significant in lag0_14d 5.4% increase PTB risk per 1°C increase in range (95%CI=0.6 , 10.4). Tertiles of range lag0_14d: Low reference group. Medium OR=1.349 (95%CI=1.076, 1.692). High OR=1.420 (95%CI=1.078, 1.870; p test for trend=0.021)
214.	Asta (2019)	Rome, Palermo, Venice, Trieste, Bologna, and Turin, Italy	N=121 797, N PTB=6 135.	Tmax (temperature and dew point). 90th vs 75th centile in each city. lag2d Palermo RR=1.02 (95%CI=0.95, 1.09). lag1d Bologna RR=1.09 (95%CI=0.90, 1.32). lag3d Venice RR=1.94 (95%CI=1.32, 2.85). lag2d Rome RR=1.06 (95%CI=1.03, 1.10). lag3_6d Turin RR=1.03 (95%CI=0.97, 1.07). lag14_20d Trieste RR=1.06 (95%CI=0.95, 1.20). U shape in Venice (base 22.5°C)
215.	Mohammadi (2019)	Sabzevar, north eastern Iran	N PTB=3 140	Lag0d highest impact, lag1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8d also significant. NS findings at larger lags. PTB in heat wave days (daily Tmean >90th percentile ≥2 consecutive days) compared to non-HW days RR 1.21 (95%CI=1.08, 1.37). Compared to median value, lag0d. Mean temperature RR 75th centile=1.25 (95%CI=1.12, 1.4) RR 99th centile=1.6 (95%CI=1.37, 1.87). Tmax RR 75th centile=1.18 (95%CI=1.07 to 1.3) RR 99th centile=1.53 (95%CI=1.33, 1.76). Apparent temperature (dry bulb temperature, vapour pressure, air velocity) RR 75th centile=1.26 (95%CI=1.16, 1.37), RR 99th centile=1.55 (95%CI=1.36, 1.77)
216.	Son (2019)	Seoul, South Korea	N=813 820. N PTB=32 908	Heat Index (air temperature and relative humidity). HR are for a quartile increase in heat index. PTB whole pregnancy HR=1.03 (95%CI=1.01 to 1.06) [ES Q4 vs Q1=1.10; SE=0.044], lag028 HR=1.01 (95%CI=1.01 to 1.02) [ES Q4 vs Q1=1.04; SE=0.013], lag07 HR=1.01 (95%CI=1.00 to 1.02).
217.	Ward (2019)	Coast , Mountain and Piedmont, North Carolina, USA	Coast : N=79 994, PTB = 9 723. Mountain: N=29 923, N PTB=3 392. Piedmont: N=147 049, PTB = 9 723.	Lag0d. Tmin. Reference group temperature when OR became >1. Mountain region, 82-83 centile (reference group): 84-86 centile OR=1.01 (95%CI=1.01, 1.02), 86-88 OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.03, 1.04) 88-90 OR=1.06 (95%CI=1.05, 1.07), 90-92 OR=1.08 (95%CI=1.05, 1.11) 92-94 OR=1.10 (95%CI=1.05, 1.14), 94-96 OR=1.11 (95%CI=1.04, 1.17), 96-98 OR=1.12 (95%CI=1.04, 1.19). Piedmont Region 84-85 centile (reference group): 86-88 centile OR=1.01 (95%CI=1.00, 1.01), 88-90 OR=1.01 (95%CI=1.01, 1.02), 90-92 OR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.05), 92-94 OR=1.03 (95%CI=0.98, 1.07), 94-96 OR=1.03 (95%CI=0.97, 1.09), 96-98

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				OR=1.04 (95%CI=0.97, 1.11), 98-100 OR=1.04 (95%CI=0.97, 1.11). Coastal Plains Region 82-82 centile (reference group): 84-86 OR=1.01 (95%CI=1.01, 1.01), OR=86-88 1.02 (95%CI=1.02, 1.02), 88-90 OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.03, 1.03), 90-92 OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.03, 1.05), 92-94 OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.02, 1.08), 94-96 OR=1.06 (95%CI=1.01, 1.10), 96-98 OR=1.06 (95%CI=1.01, 1.12), 98-100 OR=1.07 (95%CI=1.00, 1.13) Clear dose-dependent rises in OR with temperature. Lag3d similar findings
218.	Sun (2019)	403 counties, USA	N=31 921 046. N PTB=2 973 909	95th centile vs median lag4d RR=1.03 (95%CI=1.02, 1.04), lag1d significant. Lag0d, lag2d lag3d NS. Linear shape
219.	Smith (2020)	Minnesota, United States	N=154 157. N PTB=14 542	HW lagd7 mean daily heat index >37°C [99th centile] (temperature and humidity) RR=1.13 (95%CI=0.99, 1.28) versus non-HW
220.	Wang (2020)	Guangzhou, China	N = 215 059. N PTB = 11 109	Except for 33°C-D2 and 33°C-D3, other 10 HW definitions associated with higher risk of PTB. The HRs of PTB ranged from 1.10 (95%CI=1.01, 1.20) to 1.92 (1.39, 2.64). In general, risk of PTB increased with HW intensity. When stratified by gestational age, all HW more intense than 75th-D2 were associated with higher risk of PTB at 35-36w, with HR ranging from 1.13 (95%CI=1.03, 1.25) to 1.72 (95%CI=1.26, 2.35). For PTB at 28-34w, very intense HW associated with PTB: 95th-D3 HR 1.56 (95%CI=1.07, 2.28) and 98th-D2 2.04 (95%CI=1.37, 3.03)
221.	Liu (2020)	Guangzhou, China	N = 4 101. N PTB=234	Increased HR for PTB with increasing temperatures. Maximum significant periods of exposure for 95th percentile at weeks 4-8:Max HR = 1.79(95% CI=1.26, 2.54) and 22-27weeks HR=1.83 (95%CI=1.27, 2.62). Dose-response effect noted.
222.	Spolter (2020)	Southern district of Israel	N=62 547. N late PTB= 5 336	Exposure to weekly Tmean over whole period, e.g. week 31-36 for late preterm vs middle quintile. Late preterm HR=1.31 (95%CI=1.11, 1.56). 5th quintile HR=1.13 (95%CI=0.98, 1.29). Early term highest quintile HR=1.24 (95%CI=1.13, 1.36). 4th quintile HR=1.16 (95%CI=1.07, 1.25). Quintile 5 >25.6°C. Quintile 4 22.2-25.4°C
223.	Gronlund (2020)	Detroit, Michigan, United States	N PTB=9 052	Hot season May - September. Total effects 10.6% [95% CI=3.8%, 17.2%] of PTBs attributable to apparent temperature (AT) exposure of 24.9°C versus

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				18.6°C. Direct effect, taking into account mediation by PM10, ozone and NO2= 10.4% [95%CI=2.2%, 17.5%].
224.	Cho (2020)	162 cities, South Korea	N=2 300 000. N PTB not provided	No significant association between PTB and daily temperature >32°C, or 30-32°C, 0-12m after weather event, relative to 28-30°C. At month 0 after weather event, r=-0.018 (SE 0.030) for exposure to daily Tmax >32°C relative to 28-30°C. At month 3, r=0.004 (SE 0.025) for exposure to daily Tmax >32°C relative to 28-30°C
225.	Barreca (2020)	Unites States	N= 56 030 127	Extreme heat associated with increase in deliveries on the day of exposure and on following day, and that additional births were accelerated by up to two weeks. 25 000 infants per year born earlier as a result of heat exposure, with a total loss of more than 150 000 gestational days annually. Absent adaptation, climate projections suggest additional losses of 250 000 days of gestation per year by the end of the century. Birth rates increase by 0.97 births per 100 000 women aged 15-44 years old on days with a maximum temperature ≥ 32.2 °C (90°F) compared to days with a maximum temperature of 15.6-21.1°C (60-70°F) - increase of 5% relative to average daily county birth rate. 0.66 increase on next day. Two days after exposure, birth rates decrease by 0.57, suggesting most births most affected births shift forward by one or two days.
226.	Wang (2020)	China	N = 1 282 859. N PTB=104 493	Whole of pregnancy: 95th percentile vs minimum risk HR=1.55 (95% CI=1.48, 1.61; p<0.05). First trimester 95th percentile vs minimum risk HR=1.96 (95%CI=1.85, 2.08; p<0.05), Second trimester 75th percentile vs minimum risk HR=1.41 (95%CI=1.34, 1.47; p<0.05), Third trimester 95th percentile vs minimum risk HR=1.04 (95%CI=1.02, 1.06; p<0.05).
227.	Li (2021)	Shenzhen, China	N=1 388 994. N PTB=78 920	Diurnal temperature range (Tmax-Tmin). HR 2nd trimester per 1°C increase=1.06 (95%CI=1.03, 1.08). 4 weeks preceding birth HR=0.96 (95%CI=0.95, 0.97). 1 week preceding birth HR=0.99 (95%CI=0.98, 0.10). For May to Oct HR 2nd trimester=1.10 (95%CI=1.06, 1.14). Tmean on a day - Tmean on previous day. HR 1st trimester per 1°C increase=1.08 (95%CI=1.05, 1.12), 2nd trimester HR=1.24 (95%CI=1.20, 1.28). 4 weeks before birth HR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.04). May to Oct HR 2nd trimester=1.44 (95%CI=1.37, 1.51)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
228.	Cushing (2021)	Harris County, Texas	N=198 013. N PTB=20 462	Risk of PTB 15% higher following extremely hot days HR=1.15 (95%CI=1.01, 1.30) for Tmax ≥40°C vs. <20°C; HR=1.15 (95% CI=1.02, 1.28) for Tmax and Tmin >99th centile. Censoring at earlier gestational ages suggested stronger associations earlier in pregnancy.
229.	Gat (2021)	Nege, Southern Israel	N=84 476. N PTB=8 076	Increase in Tmean. Jewish NS. Bedouin-Arabs lag0d RR=1.19 (95%CI=1.03, 1.37). Also lag1d and lag2d significant. Lag0_7d per quartile increase RR=1.15 (95%CI=0.10, 1.34; p=0.059). Quartile 3 vs Quartile 1 RR=1.49 (p=0.001). Quartile 4 vs Quartile 1 RR=1.10 (NS)
230.	Tapia (2021)	Lima, Peru	N= 123 034. N PTB=8 897	Comparing IQR of Tmax with Q1 as reference, Q4 Tmax in first trimester HR=1.06 (95% CI: 1.01, 1.14). Harmful effects noted for entire pregnancy and second trimester, but NS in third trimester. Minimum p-value for interaction 0.001.
231.	Cheng (2021)	Xuzhou, China	N=103 876 births. N=4 623 PTB	No effect for heat (99th percentile relative to median temperature_ RR 1.01 (95% CI=0.75-1.37) for lag0d. All other lags have RR point estimate < 1 for 99th and 75th percentile.
232.	Gong (2021)	Rural areas of Henan province, China	N=5 394. N PTB=186	For each 1°C increase in daily Tmean during entire pregnancy, PTB increased OR=1.21 (95%CI=1.10, 1.32) and gestational age decreased by -0.44d (95%CI=-0.61, -0.27). Gestational age decreased with each additional 1°C in daily Tmean in 1st trimester -0.06d (95%CI=0.01, 0.11). Odds of PTB increased with each 1°C increase in daily Tmean in last week of pregnancy OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.00, 1.06), last 2 weeks pregnancy OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.01, 1.06), last 3 weeks pregnancy OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.01, 1.07) and last 4 weeks pregnancy OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.01, 1.07). Gestational age decreased with each 1°C increase in daily Tmean for the last week of pregnancy: -0.08d (95%CI=-0.14, -0.03), last 2 weeks pregnancy -0.10 (95%CI=-0.15, -0.04), last 3 weeks pregnancy -0.11 (95%CI=-0.16, -0.05) and last 4 weeks pregnancy -0.11(95%CI=-0.17, -0.05). In cold season, PTB odds increased and gestational age decreased with ambient temperature fluctuations in last 1-4w pregnancy, but not in the warm season: Last 4w OR=1.05 (95%CI=1.02, 1.09)
233.	Kwag (2021)	South Korea	N = 1 329 991. NPTB=61 182	Increased OR for preterm birth with heat wave exposure hours >202.5 (90th percentile) compared to 0 hours of exposure in first trimester of 1.05 (95% CI:

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
				1.01; 1.09, P-value = 0.009). Increased OR for preterm birth with heat wave exposure hours >315.0 (88th percentile) compared to 0 hours of exposure in second trimester of 1.17 (95% CI: 1.13; 1.22, P-value < 0.001). Increased OR for preterm birth with heat wave exposure hours >315.0 (88th percentile) compared to 0 hours of exposure in first trimester with PM2.5 of 51-75percentile of 1.37 (95% CI: 1.25; 1.52, P-value <0.001)
234.	Jegasothy (2021)	New South Wales, Australia	N=916 678 N PTB=29 421	Exposure 95th centile of daily Tmean (25°C). Increased risk of PTB RR=1.14 (95%CI=1.07, 1.21) compared with median daily Tmean (17°C). Similar effect sizes seen for 95th centile of daily Tmin and Tmax vs median. Cumulative effect of daily Tmean difference from 17°C to 25°C peaked at lag7d RR=1.16 (95%CI=1.08, 1.25). Cumulative effect of Tmax difference from median (23°C) to 95th centile (33°C) also highest at lag7d with RR=1.12 (95%CI=1.05, 1.20)
235.	Khodadi (2022)	Ahvaz, Iran	N=150 766 women. N PTB=5 776	Hot thermal stress (UTCI) not associated with cumulative RR of PTB at lag 0d, 0_2d, 0_6d, 0_13d and 0_21d. For lag0d cumulative RR=0.90 (95%CI 0.67, 1.21) and for lag0_21d, cumulative relative risk for PTB was 1.38 (95%CI 0.71, 2.67)
236.	Nyadanu (2022)	Western Australia	N PTB=15 576	Exposure 75th (18.9°C) centile relative to median UCTI (13.8°C). At lag0d and lag0_6d RR=1.01 (95% CI=1.01, 1.01), lag0_13d RR=1.01 (95%CI=1.01, 1.02) and lag0_21d RR=1.04 (95%CI=1.03, 1.04). For the 95th (26.4°C) centile relative to median UCTI (13.8°C), lag0d and lag0_6d RR=1.01 (95%CI=1.01, 1.01), lag0_13d RR=1.03 (95%CI=1.03, 1.04) and lag0_21d RR=1.04 (95%CI 1.03, 1.05). For the 99th (31.2°C) centile relative to median UCTI (13.8°C), lag0d and lag0_6d RR=1.01 (95%CI=1.01, 1.02) and lag0_13d RR=1.05 (95%CI=1.04, 1.06). Excess of 11 (95%CI=9, 13) per 10,000 liveborn due to immediate (lag0d) and 36 (95%CI=29, 43) due to cumulative (lag0_6d) heat stress (99th centile). Transition season had higher risk at 95th and 99th centiles compared to winter and summer at lag0d, and at 99th percentile for lag0d, lag0_6d, lag0_13d and lag0_21d. At lag 0d at 99th percentile, RR=1.04 (95%CI=1.03, 1.04) in transition season compared to RR=0.99 (95%CI=0.99, 1.00) in winter and RR=1.02 (95%CI=1.00, 1.01) in summer

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
237.	Hough (2022)	Poitiers, Nancy, Brittany and Grenoble, France	N=5 347	Mean T _{min} (95th vs 50th; 15.7°C vs 7.4°C) during weeks 1–5 RR=2.00 (95%CI=1.05, 3.84) and 20–26 weeks RR=2.87 (95% CI=1.21, 6.79). Mean T _{min} 95th centile 15.7°C in individual weeks 1–5 or 21–26 all p<0.05, mean RR of 1.16 for all these weeks (95%CI=1.02–1.34). 90th smaller but significant effect in these windows. 99th percentile larger effect in weeks 21–26 RR=3.81 (95%CI=1.18, 12.32). 95th significant in last 5 days of gestation.
238.	Keivabu (2022)	50 provincial capital cities, Spain	N=4 314 381. N PTB=259 383	Unit is percent increase in outcome per additional day at >32°C vs days at 5–25°C. PTB: -0.026% reduced per day (p>0.05).
239.	McElroy (2022)	14 LMICs (Angola, Benin, Burundi, Ethiopia, Haiti, Malawi, Nepal, Nigeria, Philippines, South Africa, Tajikistan, Timor-Leste, Uganda, and Zimbabwe)	N=103 535. N PTB=5 882	Diurnal range <16°C (p<0.05) only lag ₀ 14°C RR=1.76 (95%CI=1.23–2.54). NS, but strong trend for increased risk of PTB at >20°C T _{max} lag _{0_7d}
240.	Cil (2022)	United States	N=34 700 000. N PTB = 3 425 098	An additional day during pregnancy with average temperature 90°F leads to additional 0.013 very preterm births per 1 000 (0.1% of mean; p <0.10), an additional 0.014 extremely preterm births per 1 000 births (0.23% of mean; p<0.01). In births with greater exposure to summer months during gestation (i.e. high exposure group), an additional hot day with temperatures 2–3 SD above the mean leads to an additional 0.104 preterm births per 1 000 (0.1% of the mean; p<0.05)
241.	Bont (2022)	Sweden	N=560 615. N PTB=28 221	When comparing 95th and 50th centile, OR=1.21 (95%CI=0.82, 1.78) in case-crossover design, reduction of -0.65 (95%CI=-9.67, 8.36) days in gestational age at birth in quantile regression, and HR=1.25 (95%CI=0.92, 1.70) in time-to-event analysis. NS
242.	Zhang (2022)	China	No population numbers provided. National and	HW associated PTBs in observed climate amounted to annual average of 13 262 (95%CI= 6 962, 18 802) cases. HW related PTBs induced by anthropogenic

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
			provincial prevalence of PTB, and heat-wave-PTB association in China were obtained from other studies.	climate change gave an average of 4609 (95%CI=711, 6110) cases annually amounting to 25.8% (95%CI=17.1%, 34.5%). The total economic costs of human capital losses caused by annual by anthropogenic climate change are expected to exceed \$1billion annually
243.	Yuzen (2023)	Hamburg, Germany	N=25 624. N PTB=2 181	RR of PTB after exposure to heat event (Tmax significant at the 98th percentile for minimum 3 consecutive days) RR=1.59 (95%CI 1.01, 2.43). PTB associated with apparent temperature at 90th percentile for 5 days RR=1.20 (95%CI=1.02, 1.40) and 99th percentile for 2 days exposure RR=1.45 (95%CI=1.04, 2.00). Late PTB (34-37 weeks) highest risk at 98th percentile for 3 day Tmax exposure RR=2.00 (95%CI=1.21, 3.21) and by apparent temperature at 99th percentile RR=1.67 (95%CI=1.14, 2.43)
244.	Wang (2023)	16 selected counties in 8 cities in China	N=21 652. N=10 826 sibling pairs. N PTB=804	Exposure to heat in trimester 3 and entire pregnancy associated with increased odds of PTB. In trimester 3, moderate heat (Tmin >85th percentile) OR=2.98 (95%CI=2.09, 4.26), severe heat (>90th percentile) OR=2.48 (95%CI=1.73, 3.55) and extreme heat (>95th percentile) OR=3.22 (95%CI=2.10, 4.92). Similarly for entire pregnancy, exposure to moderate heat OR=2.15 (95%CI=1.56, 2.98), severe heat OR=3.12 (95%CI=2.18, 4.46) and extreme heat OR=5.09 (95%CI=3.27, 7.92).
Small for gestational age				
245.	Ha (2017)	15 hospitals, USA	N=220 572. N=22 239 SGA	Temperature from conception to childbirth higher among SGA than non-SGA. Temperature >95th centile in whole pregnancy RR=1.05 (95%CI=0.97, 1.13)
246.	Molina (2017)	Andean region, across Bolivia, Colombia, and Peru	N=86 021	Outcome is change in absolute % with 1 SD above historical Tmean in location. SGA increase 0.9% (P<0.05)
247.	Kloog (2018)	Southern Israel	N=56 141. N=8 634 SGA cases	Quartile 25-75 is reference. Whole pregnancy Tmean exposure >75th percentile reduced SGA OR=0.91 (95%CI=0.84, 0.99). 1st trimester mean temp >75th centile OR=0.82 (95%CI=0.73, 0.92); 2nd trimester OR=0.94 (95%CI=0.85, 1.04), 3rd trimester OR=0.95 (95%CI=0.85, 1.05)

	Main Author (Year)	Location	Sample Size	Main Study Outcome and Effect Estimate
248.	Carlson (2022)	Boston, USA	N=4 442 mother-child dyads	Association between 1SD change in heat index and SGA significant between gestational week 9 and 26, a 1°C increase in weekly SD heat index associated with 10% (95%CI=2%, 18%) increase in SGA. Cumulative risk for SGA weeks 9-26 was OR=4.7 (95%CI=1.6, 14.1). Cumulative effect in the 2nd trimester (week 14-26) OR=3.2 (95%CI=1.4, 7.4)
249.	Li (2023)	Hubei Province, China	N=1 436 480 singleton newborns. N=108 825 cases of SGA	In Eastern region, significant association between SGA and heat exposure in the second trimesters OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.01, 1.08) and third trimester OR=1.17 (95%CI=1.13, 1.22). In middle region, SGA associated with heat exposure in third trimester OR=1.29 (95%CI=1.21, 1.37), but protective in second trimester OR=0.90 (95%CI=0.84, 0.98). In the Western region (highest altitude), no significant association between SGA and heat exposure.
250.	Sun (2019)	403 counties, USA	N=29 597 735 term births. N=3 018 969 SGA cases	Reference 40th-50th centile of daily Tmean for entire pregnancy and term SGA. >90th centile OR=1.04 (95%CI=1.03, 1.05). 80-90th centile OR=1.03 (95%CI=1.02, 1.04). Results similar if preterm births included. Linear association from 50th-100th centile. Impacts in 2nd and 3rd trimester similar to impacts in all pregnancy. Temperature 1st trimester NS, point estimates around 1.0. Largest impacts in marine and cold/very cold climate zones

7.3 Appendix C: Study references

1. Agay-Shay K, Friger M, Linn S, Peled A, Amitai Y, Peretz C. Ambient temperature and congenital heart defects. *Human reproduction (Oxford, England)*. 2013;28(8).
2. Agobe JT, Good W, Hancock KW. Meteorological relations of eclampsia in Lagos, Nigeria. *Br J Obstet Gynaecol*. 1981;88(7):706-10.
3. Algert CS, Roberts CL, Shand AW, Morris JM, Ford JB. Seasonal variation in pregnancy hypertension is correlated with sunlight intensity. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2010;203(3):215 e1-5.
4. Aminzadeh M, Chomeili B, Riahi K, Dehdashtian M, Cheraghian B, Valavi E. Effect of temperature changes on the occurrence of congenital hypothyroidism. *J Med Screen*. 2010;17(3):121-4.
5. Andalón M, Azevedo JP, Rodríguez-Castelán C, Sanfelice V, Valderrama-González D. Weather Shocks and Health at Birth in Colombia. *World Development*. 2016;82:69-82.
6. Arroyo V, Diaz J, Carmona R, Ortiz C, Linares C. Impact of air pollution and temperature on adverse birth outcomes: Madrid, 2001-2009. *Environ Pollut*. 2016;218:1154-61.
7. Arroyo V, Díaz J, Ortiz C, Carmona R, Sáez M, Linares C. Short term effect of air pollution, noise and heat waves on preterm births in Madrid (Spain). *Environ Res*. 2016;145:162-8.
8. Asamoah BK, T; Östergren, PO;. Is ambient heat exposure levels associated with miscarriage or stillbirths in hot regions? A cross-sectional study using survey data from the Ghana Maternal Health Survey 2007. *International Journal of Biometeorology*. 2023;62(3):319-30.
9. Asta F, Michelozzi P, Cestari L, Fantaci G, Perlangeli V, Pizzi L, et al. [Effects of high temperature and air pollution on the risk of preterm births. Analysis in six Italian cities, 2001-2010]. *Epidemiol Prev*. 2019;43(2-3):152-60.
10. Auger N, Fraser W, Smargiassi A, Bilodeau-Bertrand M, Kosatsky T. Elevated outdoor temperatures and risk of stillbirth. *International journal of epidemiology*. 2017;46(1).
11. Auger N, Fraser WD, Arbour L, Bilodeau-Bertrand M, Kosatsky T. Elevated ambient temperatures and risk of neural tube defects. *Occup Environ Med*. 2017;74(5):315-20.
12. Auger N, Fraser WD, Sauve R, Bilodeau-Bertrand M, Kosatsky T. Risk of Congenital Heart Defects after Ambient Heat Exposure Early in Pregnancy. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2017;125(1):8-14.
13. Auger N, Naimi AI, Smargiassi A, Lo E, Kosatsky T. Extreme heat and risk of early delivery among preterm and term pregnancies. *Epidemiology*. 2014;25(3):344-50.
14. Auger N, Siemiatycki J, Bilodeau-Bertrand M, Healy-Profitos J, Kosatsky T. Ambient Temperature and Risk of Preeclampsia: Biased Association? *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*. 2017;31(4):267-71.
15. Avalos LA, Chen H, Li DK, Basu R. The impact of high apparent temperature on spontaneous preterm delivery: a case-crossover study. *Environ Health*. 2017;16(1):5.
16. Bakhtsiyarava M, Ortigoza A, Sánchez BN, Braverman-Bronstein A, Kephart JL, Rodríguez López S, et al. Ambient temperature and term birthweight in Latin American cities. *Environ Int*. 2022;167:107412.
17. Barreca A, Schaller J. The impact of high ambient temperatures on delivery timing and gestational lengths. *Nature Climate Change*. 2019;10(1):77-82.
18. Basagaña X, Michael Y, Lensky IM, Rubin L, Grotto I, Vadislavsky E, et al. Low and High Ambient Temperatures during Pregnancy and Birth Weight among 624,940 Singleton

Term Births in Israel (2010-2014): An Investigation of Potential Windows of Susceptibility. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2021;129(10):107001.

19.Basagaña X, Sartini C, Barrera-Gómez J, Dadvand P, Cunillera J, Ostro B, et al. Heat waves and cause-specific mortality at all ages. *Epidemiology.* 2011;22(6):765-72.

20.Basu R, Chen H, Li DK, Avalos LA. The impact of maternal factors on the association between temperature and preterm delivery. *Environ Res.* 2017;154:109-14.

21.Basu R, Malig B, Ostro B. High ambient temperature and the risk of preterm delivery. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2010;172(10):1108-17.

22.Basu R, Rau R, Pearson D, Malig B. Temperature and Term Low Birth Weight in California. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2018;187(11):2306-14.

23.Basu R, Sarovar V, Malig B. Association Between High Ambient Temperature and Risk of Stillbirth in California. *American journal of epidemiology.* 2016;183(10).

24.Bianchi-Demicheli F, Lüdicke F, Spinedi F, Major AL, Kulier R, Campana A, et al. Association between weather conditions and the incidence of emergency gynecological consultations. *Gynecologic and obstetric investigation.* 2001;51(1).

25.Bider D, Sivan E, Seidman DS, Dulitzky M, Mashiach S, Serr DM, et al. Meteorological factors in hypertensive disorders, vaginal bleeding and premature rupture of membranes during pregnancy. *Gynecol Obstet Invest.* 1991;32(2):88-90.

26.Bogan M, Al B, Kul S, Zengin S, Oktay M, Sabak M, et al. The effects of desert dust storms, air pollution, and temperature on morbidity due to spontaneous abortions and toxemia of pregnancy: 5-year analysis. *Int J Biometeorol.* 2021;65(10):1733-9.

27.Bonell A, Sonko B, Badjie J, Samateh T, Saidy T, Sosseh F, et al. Environmental heat stress on maternal physiology and fetal blood flow in pregnant subsistence farmers in The Gambia, west Africa: an observational cohort study. *Lancet Planet Health.* 2022;6(12):e968-e76.

28.Bonell A, Vannevel V, Sonko B, Mohammed N, Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Haines A, et al. A feasibility study of the use of UmbiFlow™ to assess the impact of heat stress on fetoplacental blood flow in field studies. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet.* 2023;160(2):430-6.

29.Booth GL, Luo J, Park AL, Feig DS, Moineddin R, Ray JG. Influence of environmental temperature on risk of gestational diabetes. *CMAJ.* 2017;189(19):E682-E9.

30.Bruckner TA, Modin B, Vågerö D. Cold ambient temperature in utero and birth outcomes in Uppsala, Sweden, 1915-1929. *Ann Epidemiol.* 2014;24(2):116-21.

31.Busowski JD, Chez RA. Climatic factors and the incidence of pyelonephritis during pregnancy. *Infect Dis Obstet Gynecol.* 1995;3(6):226-8.

32.Carlson JM, Zanobetti A, Ettinger de Cuba S, Poblacion AP, Fabian PM, Carnes F, et al. Critical windows of susceptibility for the effects of prenatal exposure to heat and heat variability on gestational growth. *Environ Res.* 2023;216(Pt 2):114607.

33.Carmichael SL, Cullen MR, Mayo JA, Gould JB, Loftus P, Stevenson DK, et al. Population-level correlates of preterm delivery among black and white women in the U.S. *PLoS One.* 2014;9(4):e94153.

34.Chen F, Liu M, Yang C, Hao X, Chen Z. Effect on the health of newborns caused by extreme temperature in Guangzhou. *Journal of environmental management.* 2022;311:114842.

35.Chen X, Tan CM, Zhang X, Zhang X. The Effects of Prenatal Exposure to Temperature Extremes on Birth Outcomes: The Case of China. *J Popul Econ.* 2020;33(4):1263-302.

- 36.Cheng P, Peng L, Hao J, Li S, Zhang C, Dou L, et al. Short-term effects of ambient temperature on preterm birth: a time-series analysis in Xuzhou, China. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int.* 2021;28(10):12406-13.
- 37.Cho GJ, Ahn KH, Kim LY, Hwang SY, Hong SC, Oh MJ, et al. Effect of relative humidity on preeclampsia. *Clin Exp Obstet Gynecol.* 2017;44(2):264-7.
- 38.Cho H. Ambient temperature, birth rate, and birth outcomes: evidence from South Korea. *Popul Environ.* 2020;41(3):330-46.
- 39.Chodick G, Shalev V, Goren I, Inskip PD. Seasonality in birth weight in Israel: new evidence suggests several global patterns and different etiologies. *Ann Epidemiol.* 2007;17(6):440-6.
- 40.Cil G, Cameron TA. Potential Climate Change Health Risks from Increases in Heat Waves: Abnormal Birth Outcomes and Adverse Maternal Health Conditions. *Risk Anal.* 2017;37(11):2066-79.
- 41.Cil G, Kim J. Extreme temperatures during pregnancy and adverse birth outcomes: Evidence from 2009 to 2018 U.S. national birth data. *Health Econ.* 2022;31(9):1993-2024.
- 42.Conte Keivabu R, Cozzani M. Extreme Heat, Birth Outcomes, and Socioeconomic Heterogeneity. *Demography.* 2022;59(5):1631-54.
- 43.Cox B, Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Gasparrini A, Roels HA, Martens E, Vangronsveld J, et al. Ambient temperature as a trigger of preterm delivery in a temperate climate. *J Epidemiol Community Health.* 2016;70(12):1191-9.
- 44.Cushing L, Morello-Frosch R, Hubbard A. Extreme heat and its association with social disparities in the risk of spontaneous preterm birth. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol.* 2022;36(1):13-22.
- 45.Dadvand P, Basagana X, Figueras F, Sunyer J, Nieuwenhuijsen MJ. Climate and group B streptococci colonisation during pregnancy: present implications and future concerns. *Bjog.* 2011;118(11):1396-400.
- 46.Dadvand P, Basagaña X, Sartini C, Figueras F, Vrijheid M, de Nazelle A, et al. Climate extremes and the length of gestation. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2011;119(10):1449-53.
- 47.Dadvand P, Ostro B, Figueras F, Foraster M, Basagaña X, Valentín A, et al. Residential proximity to major roads and term low birth weight: the roles of air pollution, heat, noise, and road-adjacent trees. *Epidemiology.* 2014;25(4):518-25.
- 48.Dastoorpoor M, Khanjani N, Khodadadi N. Association between Physiological Equivalent Temperature (PET) with adverse pregnancy outcomes in Ahvaz, southwest of Iran. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2021;21(1):415.
- 49.Davenport FD, Audrey; Grace, Kathryn. Investigating the linkages between pregnancy outcomes and climate in sub-Saharan Africa. *Population and Environment.* 2020;41(4):397-421.
- 50.Davies BR. The seasonal conception of lethal congenital malformations. *Arch Med Res.* 2000;31(6):589-91.
- 51.Davis RE, Novicoff WM. The Impact of Heat Waves on Emergency Department Admissions in Charlottesville, Virginia, U.S.A. *International journal of environmental research and public health.* 2018;15(7).
- 52.de Bont J, Stafoggia M, Nakstad B, Hajat S, Kovats S, Part C, et al. Associations between ambient temperature and risk of preterm birth in Sweden: A comparison of analytical approaches. *Environ Res.* 2022;213:113586.
- 53.Díaz J, Arroyo V, Ortiz C, Carmona R, Linares C. Effect of Environmental Factors on Low Weight in Non-Premature Births: A Time Series Analysis. *PLoS One.* 2016;11(10):e0164741.

54. Dieckmann WJ. The geographic distribution and effect of climate on eclampsia, toxemia of pregnancy, hyperemesis gravidarum, and abruptio placentae. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*. 1938;36(4):623-31.
55. Du S, Bai S, Zhao X, Lin S, Zhai Y, Wang Z, et al. The effect and its critical window for ambient temperature and humidity in pregnancy on term low birth weight. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*. 2022;29(36):54531-42.
56. Elter K, Ay E, Uyar E, Kavak ZN. Exposure to low outdoor temperature in the midtrimester is associated with low birth weight. *Aust N Z J Obstet Gynaecol*. 2004;44(6):553-7.
57. Gat R, Kachko E, Kloog I, Erez O, Yitshak-Sade M, Novack V, et al. Differences in environmental factors contributing to preterm labor and PPRM - Population based study. *Environ Res*. 2021;196:110894.
58. Giorgis-Allemand L, Pedersen M, Bernard C, Aguilera I, Beelen RM, Chatzi L, et al. The Influence of Meteorological Factors and Atmospheric Pollutants on the Risk of Preterm Birth. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2017;185(4):247-58.
59. Gong Y, Chai J, Yang M, Sun P, Sun R, Dong W, et al. Effects of ambient temperature on the risk of preterm birth in offspring of adolescent mothers in rural henan, China. *Environ Res*. 2021;201:111545.
60. Grace K, Davenport F, Hanson H, Funk CC, Shukla S. Linking climate change and health outcomes: Examining the relationship between temperature, precipitation and birth weight in Africa. *Global Environmental Change*. 2015;35:125-37.
61. Grace K, Verdin A, Dorélien A, Davenport F, Funk C, Husak G. Exploring Strategies for Investigating the Mechanisms Linking Climate and Individual-Level Child Health Outcomes: An Analysis of Birth Weight in Mali. *Demography*. 2021;58(2):499-526.
62. Griswold DM, Cavanagh D. Eclampsia and the Weather. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 1965;91:847-51.
63. Gronlund CJ, Yang AJ, Conlon KC, Bergmans RS, Le HQ, Batterman SA, et al. Time series analysis of total and direct associations between high temperatures and preterm births in Detroit, Michigan. *BMJ Open*. 2020;10(2):e032476.
64. Gu YH, Kato T, Harada S, Inomata H, Saito T, Aoki K. Seasonality in the incidence of congenital hypothyroidism in Japan: gender-specific patterns and correlation with temperature. *Thyroid*. 2007;17(9):869-74.
65. Guo T, Wang Y, Zhang H, Zhang Y, Zhao J, Wang Y, et al. The association between ambient temperature and the risk of preterm birth in China. *Sci Total Environ*. 2018;613-614:439-46.
66. Ha S, Liu D, Zhu Y, Kim SS, Sherman S, Grantz KL, et al. Ambient Temperature and Stillbirth: A Multi-Center Retrospective Cohort Study. 2017.
67. Ha S, Liu D, Zhu Y, Kim SS, Sherman S, Mendola P. Ambient Temperature and Early Delivery of Singleton Pregnancies. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2017;125(3):453-9.
68. Ha S, Liu D, Zhu Y, Sherman S, Mendola P. Acute Associations Between Outdoor Temperature and Premature Rupture of Membranes. *Epidemiology*. 2018;29(2):175-82.
69. Ha S, Nguyen K, Liu D, Männistö T, Nobles C, Sherman S, et al. Ambient temperature and risk of cardiovascular events at labor and delivery: A case-crossover study. *Environmental research*. 2017;159.
70. Ha S, Zhu Y, Liu D, Sherman S, Mendola P. Ambient temperature and air quality in relation to small for gestational age and term low birthweight. *Environ Res*. 2017;155:394-400.

71. Hampel R, Lepeule J, Schneider A, Bottagisi S, Charles MA, Ducimetière P, et al. Short-term impact of ambient air pollution and air temperature on blood pressure among pregnant women. *Epidemiology*. 2011;22(5):671-9.
72. He JR, Liu Y, Xia XY, Ma WJ, Lin HL, Kan HD, et al. Ambient Temperature and the Risk of Preterm Birth in Guangzhou, China (2001-2011). *Environ Health Perspect*. 2016;124(7):1100-6.
73. He S, Kosatsky T, Smargiassi A, Bilodeau-Bertrand M, Auger N. Heat and pregnancy-related emergencies: Risk of placental abruption during hot weather. *Environment international*. 2018;111.
74. Hough I, Rolland M, Guilbert A, Seyve E, Heude B, Slama R, et al. Early delivery following chronic and acute ambient temperature exposure: a comprehensive survival approach. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2023;52(3):761-73.
75. Iijima S, Baba T, Kondo M, Fujita T, Ohishi A. Effects of Season of Birth and Meteorological Parameters on Serum Bilirubin Levels during the Early Neonatal Period: A Retrospective Chart Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(5).
76. Ilango SD, Weaver M, Sheridan P, Schwarz L, Clemesha RES, Bruckner T, et al. Extreme heat episodes and risk of preterm birth in California, 2005-2013. *Environ Int*. 2020;137:105541.
77. Immink A, Scherjon S, Wolterbeek R, Steyn DW. Seasonal influence on the admittance of preeclampsia patients in Tygerberg Hospital. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand*. 2008;87(1):36-42.
78. Jakpor O, Chevrier C, Kloog I, Benmerad M, Giorgis-Allemand L, Cordier S, et al. Term birthweight and critical windows of prenatal exposure to average meteorological conditions and meteorological variability. *Environ Int*. 2020;142:105847.
79. Jamelle RN. Eclampsia: Is there a seasonal variation in incidence? 1998.
80. Jegasothy E, Randall DA, Ford JB, Nippita TA, Morgan GG. Maternal factors and risk of spontaneous preterm birth due to high ambient temperatures in New South Wales, Australia. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*. 2022;36(1):4-12.
81. Jensen PM, Sørensen M. Differences in human birth weight and corollary attributes as a result of temperature regime. *Ann Hum Biol*. 2013;40(5):385-95.
82. Judge CM, Chasan-Taber L, Gensburg L, Nasca PC, Marshall EG. Physical exposures during pregnancy and congenital cardiovascular malformations. *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*. 2004;18(5):352-60.
83. Kakkad K, Barzaga ML, Wallenstein S, Azhar GS, Sheffield PE. Neonates in Ahmedabad, India, during the 2010 heat wave: a climate change adaptation study. *J Environ Public Health*. 2014;2014:946875.
84. Kanner J, Williams A, Nobles C, Ha S, Ouidir M, Sherman S, et al. Ambient temperature and stillbirth: Risks associated with chronic extreme temperature and acute temperature change. *Environmental research*. 2020;189.
85. Katsarou A, Claesson R, Ignell C, Shaat N, Berntorp K. Seasonal Pattern in the Diagnosis of Gestational Diabetes Mellitus in Southern Sweden. *J Diabetes Res*. 2016;2016:8905474.
86. Kent ST, McClure LA, Zaitchik BF, Smith TT, Gohlke JM. Heat waves and health outcomes in Alabama (USA): the importance of heat wave definition. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2014;122(2):151-8.
87. Khodadadi N, Dastoorpoor M, Khanjani N, Ghasemi A. Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) and adverse pregnancy outcomes in Ahvaz, Iran. *Reprod Health*. 2022;19(1):33.

- 88.Kilinc MF, Cakmak S, Demir DO, Doluoglu OG, Yildiz Y, Horasanli K, et al. Does maternal exposure during pregnancy to higher ambient temperature increase the risk of hypospadias? *J Pediatr Urol.* 2016;12(6):407.e1-.e6.
- 89.Kim J, Lee A, Rossin-Slater M. What to Expect When It Gets Hotter: The Impacts of Prenatal Exposure to Extreme Heat on Maternal and Infant Health. 2019.
- 90.Kim J, Lee A, Rossin-Slater M. What to Expect When it Gets Hotter: The Impacts of Prenatal Exposure to Extreme Temperature on Maternal Health. *American Journal of Health Economics.* 2021;7(3):249-360.
- 91.Kloog I, Melly SJ, Coull BA, Nordio F, Schwartz JD. Using Satellite-Based Spatiotemporal Resolved Air Temperature Exposure to Study the Association between Ambient Air Temperature and Birth Outcomes in Massachusetts. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2015;123(10):1053-8.
- 92.Kloog I, Novack L, Erez O, Just AC, Raz R. Associations between ambient air temperature, low birth weight and small for gestational age in term neonates in southern Israel. *Environ Health.* 2018;17(1):76.
- 93.Kwag Y, Kim MH, Oh J, Shah S, Ye S, Ha EH. Effect of heat waves and fine particulate matter on preterm births in Korea from 2010 to 2016. *Environ Int.* 2021;147:106239.
- 94.Lajinian S, Hudson S, Applewhite L, Feldman J, Minkoff HL. An association between the heat-humidity index and preterm labor and delivery: a preliminary analysis. *Am J Public Health.* 1997;87(7):1205-7.
- 95.Lawlor DA, Leon DA, Davey Smith G. The association of ambient outdoor temperature throughout pregnancy and offspring birthweight: findings from the Aberdeen Children of the 1950s cohort. *Bjog.* 2005;112(5):647-57.
- 96.Lawrence WR, Soim A, Zhang W, Lin Z, Lu Y, Lipton EA, et al. A population-based case-control study of the association between weather-related extreme heat events and low birthweight. *J Dev Orig Health Dis.* 2021;12(2):335-42.
- 97.Lee SJ, Hajat S, Steer PJ, Filippi V. A time-series analysis of any short-term effects of meteorological and air pollution factors on preterm births in London, UK. *Environ Res.* 2008;106(2):185-94.
- 98.Leung M, Laden F, Coull BA, Modest AM, Hacker MR, Wylie BJ, et al. Ambient temperature during pregnancy and fetal growth in Eastern Massachusetts, USA. *Int J Epidemiol.* 2023;52(3):749-60.
- 99.Li C, Bloom MS, Lin S, Ren M, Hajat S, Wang Q, et al. Temperature variation and preterm birth among live singleton deliveries in Shenzhen, China: A time-to-event analysis. *Environ Res.* 2021;195:110834.
- 100.Li S, Chen G, Jaakkola J, Williams G, Guo Y. Temporal change in the impacts of ambient temperature on preterm birth and stillbirth: Brisbane, 1994-2013. *The Science of the total environment.* 2018;634.
- 101.Li S, Wang J, Xu Z, Wang X, Xu G, Zhang J, et al. Exploring associations of maternal exposure to ambient temperature with duration of gestation and birth weight: a prospective study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2018;18(1):513.
- 102.Li X, Ma J, Cheng Y, Feng L, Wang S, Dong G. The relationship between extreme ambient temperature and small for gestational age: A cohort study of 1,436,480 singleton term births in China. *Environ Res.* 2023;232:116412.
- 103.Liang Z, Lin Y, Ma Y, Zhang L, Zhang X, Li L, et al. The association between ambient temperature and preterm birth in Shenzhen, China: a distributed lag non-linear time series analysis. *Environ Health.* 2016;15(1):84.

- 104.Lin S, Lin Z, Ou Y, Soim A, Shrestha S, Lu Y, et al. Maternal ambient heat exposure during early pregnancy in summer and spring and congenital heart defects - A large US population-based, case-control study. *Environ Int.* 2018;118:211-21.
- 105.Lin Y, Hu W, Xu J, Luo Z, Ye X, Yan C, et al. Association between temperature and maternal stress during pregnancy. *Environmental research.* 2017;158.
- 106.Liu X, Xiao J, Sun X, Chen Q, Yao Z, Feng B, et al. Associations of maternal ambient temperature exposures during pregnancy with the risk of preterm birth and the effect modification of birth order during the new baby boom: A birth cohort study in Guangzhou, China. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2020;225:113481.
- 107.Luton D, Alran S, Fourchette V, Sibony O, Oury JF. Paris heat wave and oligohydramnios. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2004;191(6):2103-5.
- 108.MacVicar S, Berrang-Ford L, Harper S, Huang Y, Namanya Bambahi D, Yang S. Whether weather matters: Evidence of association between in utero meteorological exposures and foetal growth among Indigenous and non-Indigenous mothers in rural Uganda. *PLoS One.* 2017;12(6):e0179010.
- 109.Madsen C, Gehring U, Walker SE, Brunekreef B, Stigum H, Naess O, et al. Ambient air pollution exposure, residential mobility and term birth weight in Oslo, Norway. *Environ Res.* 2010;110(4):363-71.
- 110.Mathew S, Mathur D, Chang AB, McDonald E, Singh GR, Nur D, et al. Examining the Effects of Ambient Temperature on Pre-Term Birth in Central Australia. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2017;14(2).
- 111.McElroy S, Ilango S, Dimitrova A, Gershunov A, Benmarhnia T. Extreme heat, preterm birth, and stillbirth: A global analysis across 14 lower-middle income countries. *Environment international.* 2022;158:106902.
- 112.Melo B, Amorim M, Katz L, Coutinho I, Figueiroa JN. Hypertension, pregnancy and weather: is seasonality involved? *Rev Assoc Med Bras (1992).* 2014;60(2):105-10.
- 113.Metoki H, Ohkubo T, Watanabe Y, Nishimura M, Sato Y, Kawaguchi M, et al. Seasonal trends of blood pressure during pregnancy in Japan: the babies and their parents' longitudinal observation in Suzuki Memorial Hospital in Intrauterine Period study. *J Hypertens.* 2008;26(12):2406-13.
- 114.Minisha F, Mohamed M, Abdulmunem D, El Awad S, Zidan M, Abreo M, et al. Bacteriuria in pregnancy varies with the ambiance: a retrospective observational study at a tertiary hospital in Doha, Qatar. *J Perinat Med.* 2019;48(1):46-52.
- 115.Mohammadi D, Naghshineh E, Sarsangi A, Zare Sakhvidi MJ. Environmental extreme temperature and daily preterm birth in Sabzevar, Iran: a time-series analysis. *Environ Health Prev Med.* 2019;24(1):5.
- 116.Molina O, Saldarriaga V. The perils of climate change: In utero exposure to temperature variability and birth outcomes in the Andean region. *Economics & Human Biology.* 2017;24(C):111-24.
- 117.Molina-Vega M, Gutierrez-Repiso C, Munoz-Garach A, Lima-Rubio F, Morcillo S, Tinahones FJ, et al. Relationship between environmental temperature and the diagnosis and treatment of gestational diabetes mellitus: An observational retrospective study. *Sci Total Environ.* 2020;744:140994.
- 118.Muresan D, Staicu A, Zaharie G, Marginean C, Rotar IC. The influence of seasonality and weather changes on premature birth incidence. *Clujul Med.* 2017;90(3):273-8.

119. Murray LJ, O'Reilly DP, Betts N, Patterson CC, Davey Smith G, Evans AE. Season and outdoor ambient temperature: effects on birth weight. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2000;96(5 Pt 1):689-95.
120. Nasiri R, Ahmadi Shadmehri A, Khajeh Ghiassi P, Sarafray Yazdi M, Mazloun Farsi Baf M. Association of meteorological factors and seasonality with preeclampsia: a 5-year study in northeast of Iran. *Clin Exp Hypertens.* 2014;36(8):586-9.
121. Neela J, Raman L. Seasonal trends in the occurrence of eclampsia. *Natl Med J India.* 1993;6(1):17-8.
122. Neutra R. Meteorological factors and eclampsia. *J Obstet Gynaecol Br Commonw.* 1974;81(11):833-40.
123. Ngo NS, Horton RM. Climate change and fetal health: The impacts of exposure to extreme temperatures in New York City. *Environ Res.* 2016;144(Pt A):158-64.
124. Nyadanu SD, Tessema GA, Mullins B, Kumi-Boateng B, Ofosu AA, Pereira G. Prenatal exposure to long-term heat stress and stillbirth in Ghana: A within-space time-series analysis. *Environmental research.* 2023;222:115385.
125. Nyadanu SD, Tessema GA, Mullins B, Pereira G. Maternal acute thermophysiological stress and stillbirth in Western Australia, 2000-2015: A space-time-stratified case-crossover analysis. *The Science of the total environment.* 2022;836:155750.
126. Nyadanu SD, Tessema GA, Mullins B, Pereira G. Prenatal acute thermophysiological stress and spontaneous preterm birth in Western Australia, 2000-2015: A space-time-stratified case-crossover analysis. *Int J Hyg Environ Health.* 2022;245:114029.
127. Part C, le Roux J, Chersich M, Sawry S, Filippi V, Roos N, et al. Ambient temperature during pregnancy and risk of maternal hypertensive disorders: A time-to-event study in Johannesburg, South Africa. *Environ Res.* 2022;212(Pt D):113596.
128. Poeran J, Birnie E, Steegers EA, Bonsel GJ. The Impact of Extremes in Outdoor Temperature and Sunshine Exposure on Birth Weight. *J Environ Health.* 2016;78(6):92-100.
129. Porter KR, Thomas SD, Whitman S. The relation of gestation length to short-term heat stress. *Am J Public Health.* 1999;89(7):1090-2.
130. Qu Y, Zhang W, Ryan I, Deng X, Dong G, Liu X, et al. Ambient extreme heat exposure in summer and transitional months and emergency department visits and hospital admissions due to pregnancy complications. *Sci Total Environ.* 2021;777:146134.
131. Rammah A, Whitworth KW, Han I, Chan W, Hess JW, Symanski E. Temperature, placental abruption and stillbirth. *Environment international.* 2019;131.
132. Ranjbaran M, Mohammadi R, Yaseri M, Kamari M, Habibelahi A, Yazdani K. Effect of ambient air pollution and temperature on the risk of stillbirth: a distributed lag nonlinear time series analysis. *J Environ Health Sci Eng.* 2020;18(2):1289-99.
133. Rashid H, Kagami M, Ferdous F, Ma E, Terao T, Hayashi T, et al. Temperature during pregnancy influences the fetal growth and birth size. *Trop Med Health.* 2017;45:1.
134. Requia WJ, Koutrakis P, Papatheodorou S. The association of maternal exposure to ambient temperature with low birth weight in term pregnancies varies by location: In Brazil, positive associations may occur only in the Amazon region. *Environ Res.* 2022;214(Pt 2):113923.
135. Retnakaran R, Ye C, Kramer CK, Hanley AJ, Connelly PW, Sermer M, et al. Impact of daily incremental change in environmental temperature on beta cell function and the risk of gestational diabetes in pregnant women. *Diabetologia.* 2018;61(12):2633-42.

136. Richards M, Huang M, Strickland MJ, Newman AJ, Warren JL, D'Souza R, et al. Acute association between heatwaves and stillbirth in six US states. *Environmental health : a global access science source*. 2022;21(1):59.
137. Savitz DA, Hu H. Ambient heat and stillbirth in Northern and Central Florida. *Environ Res*. 2021;199:111262.
138. Schifano P, Asta F, Dadvand P, Davoli M, Basagana X, Michelozzi P. Heat and air pollution exposure as triggers of delivery: A survival analysis of population-based pregnancy cohorts in Rome and Barcelona. *Environ Int*. 2016;88:153-9.
139. Schifano P, Lallo A, Asta F, De Sario M, Davoli M, Michelozzi P. Effect of ambient temperature and air pollutants on the risk of preterm birth, Rome 2001-2010. *Environ Int*. 2013;61:77-87.
140. Schumann B, Häggström Lundevaller E, Karlsson L. Weather extremes and perinatal mortality - Seasonal and ethnic differences in northern Sweden, 1800-1895. *PLoS One*. 2019;14(10):e0223538.
141. Sciscione AC, Costigan KA, Johnson TR. Increase in ambient temperature may explain decrease in amniotic fluid index. *Am J Perinatol*. 1997;14(5):249-51.
142. Scraftford CG, Mullany LC, Katz J, Khatry SK, LeClerq SC, Darmstadt GL, et al. Incidence of and risk factors for neonatal jaundice among newborns in southern Nepal. *Trop Med Int Health*. 2013;18(11):1317-28.
143. Shankar K, Ali SA, Ruebel ML, Jessani S, Borengasser SJ, Gilley SP, et al. Maternal nutritional status modifies heat-associated growth restriction in women with chronic malnutrition. *PNAS Nexus*. 2023;2(1):pgac309.
144. Shashar S, Kloog I, Erez O, Shtein A, Yitshak-Sade M, Sarov B, et al. Temperature and preeclampsia: Epidemiological evidence that perturbation in maternal heat homeostasis affects pregnancy outcome. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(5):e0232877.
145. Shen EX, Moses RG, Oats JJN, Lowe J, McIntyre HD. Seasonality, temperature and pregnancy oral glucose tolerance test results in Australia. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2019;19(1):263.
146. Smith ML, Hardeman RR. Association of Summer Heat Waves and the Probability of Preterm Birth in Minnesota: An Exploration of the Intersection of Race and Education. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2020;17(17).
147. Soim A, Lin S, Sheridan SC, Hwang SA, Hsu WH, Luben TJ, et al. Population-based case-control study of the association between weather-related extreme heat events and neural tube defects. *Birth Defects Res*. 2017;109(18):1482-93.
148. Soim A, Sheridan SC, Hwang SA, Hsu WH, Fisher SC, Shaw GM, et al. A population-based case-control study of the association between weather-related extreme heat events and orofacial clefts. *Birth Defects Res*. 2018;110(19):1468-77.
149. Son JY, Lee JT, Lane KJ, Bell ML. Impacts of high temperature on adverse birth outcomes in Seoul, Korea: Disparities by individual- and community-level characteristics. *Environ Res*. 2019;168:460-6.
150. Song J, Lu J, Wang E, Lu M, An Z, Liu Y, et al. Short-term effects of ambient temperature on the risk of premature rupture of membranes in Xinxiang, China: A time-series analysis. *Sci Total Environ*. 2019;689:1329-35.
151. Spolter F, Kloog I, Dorman M, Novack L, Erez O, Raz R. Prenatal exposure to ambient air temperature and risk of early delivery. *Environ Int*. 2020;142:105824.

152. Strand L, Barnett A, Tong S. Maternal exposure to ambient temperature and the risks of preterm birth and stillbirth in Brisbane, Australia. *American journal of epidemiology*. 2012;175(2).
153. Su WL, Lu CL, Martini S, Hsu YH, Li CY. A population-based study on the prevalence of gestational diabetes mellitus in association with temperature in Taiwan. *Sci Total Environ*. 2020;714:136747.
154. Sun S, Spangler KR, Weinberger KR, Yanosky JD, Braun JM, Wellenius GA. Ambient Temperature and Markers of Fetal Growth: A Retrospective Observational Study of 29 Million U.S. Singleton Births. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2019;127(6):67005.
155. Sun S, Weinberger KR, Spangler KR, Eliot MN, Braun JM, Wellenius GA. Ambient temperature and preterm birth: A retrospective study of 32 million US singleton births. *Environ Int*. 2019;126:7-13.
156. Sun X, Luo X, Cao G, Zhao C, Xiao J, Liu X, et al. Associations of ambient temperature exposure during pregnancy with the risk of miscarriage and the modification effects of greenness in Guangdong, China. *Sci Total Environ*. 2020;702:134988.
157. Tam WH, Sahota DS, Lau TK, Li CY, Fung TY. Seasonal variation in pre-eclamptic rate and its association with the ambient temperature and humidity in early pregnancy. *Gynecol Obstet Invest*. 2008;66(1):22-6.
158. Tang Z, Wu M, Song G, Yang R, Wang Y. Impact of ambient temperature exposure on newborns with low Apgar scores in northwest China. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int*. 2021;28(27):36367-74.
159. Tapia VL, Vasquez-Apestegui BV, Alcantara-Zapata D, Vu B, Steenland K, Gonzales GF. Association between maximum temperature and PM(2.5) with pregnancy outcomes in Lima, Peru. *Environ Epidemiol*. 2021;5(6):e179.
160. Teyton A, Sun Y, Molitor J, Chen JC, Sacks D, Avila C, et al. Examining the Relationship Between Extreme Temperature, Microclimate Indicators, and Gestational Diabetes Mellitus in Pregnant Women Living in Southern California. *Environ Epidemiol*. 2023;7(3):e252.
161. Tikkanen J, Heinonen OP. Maternal hyperthermia during pregnancy and cardiovascular malformations in the offspring. *Eur J Epidemiol*. 1991;7(6):628-35.
162. Tran TC, Boumendil A, Bussieres L, Lebreton E, Ropers J, Rozenberg P, et al. Are Meteorological Conditions within the First Trimester of Pregnancy Associated with the Risk of Severe Preeclampsia? *Paediatr Perinat Epidemiol*. 2015;29(4):261-70.
163. Tustin K, Gross J, Hayne H. Maternal exposure to first-trimester sunshine is associated with increased birth weight in human infants. *Dev Psychobiol*. 2004;45(4):221-30.
164. Van Zutphen AR, Lin S, Fletcher BA, Hwang SA. A population-based case-control study of extreme summer temperature and birth defects. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2012;120(10):1443-9.
165. Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Iñíguez C, Barona C, Ballester F. Exposure to elevated temperatures and risk of preterm birth in Valencia, Spain. *Environ Res*. 2014;134:210-7.
166. Vicedo-Cabrera AM, Olsson D, Forsberg B. Exposure to seasonal temperatures during the last month of gestation and the risk of preterm birth in Stockholm. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2015;12(4):3962-78.
167. Walfisch A, Kabakov E, Friger M, Sheiner E. Trends, seasonality and effect of ambient temperature on preterm delivery. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med*. 2017;30(20):2483-7.

168. Wang J, Liu X, Dong M, Sun X, Xiao J, Zeng W, et al. Associations of maternal ambient temperature exposures during pregnancy with the placental weight, volume and PFR: A birth cohort study in Guangzhou, China. *Environ Int.* 2020;139:105682.
169. Wang J, Tong S, Williams G, Pan X. Exposure to Heat Wave During Pregnancy and Adverse Birth Outcomes: An Exploration of Susceptible Windows. *Epidemiology (Cambridge, Mass).* 2019;30 Suppl 1.
170. Wang J, Williams G, Guo Y, Pan X, Tong S. Maternal exposure to heatwave and preterm birth in Brisbane, Australia. *Bjog.* 2013;120(13):1631-41.
171. Wang Q, Li B, Benmarhnia T, Hajat S, Ren M, Liu T, et al. Independent and Combined Effects of Heatwaves and PM2.5 on Preterm Birth in Guangzhou, China: A Survival Analysis. *Environ Health Perspect.* 2020;128(1):17006.
172. Wang Q, Yin L, Wu H, Ren Z, He S, Huang A, et al. Effects of gestational ambient extreme temperature exposures on the risk of preterm birth in China: A sibling-matched study based on a multi-center prospective cohort. *Sci Total Environ.* 2023;887:164135.
173. Wang YY, Li Q, Guo Y, Zhou H, Wang QM, Shen HP, et al. Ambient temperature and the risk of preterm birth: A national birth cohort study in the mainland China. *Environ Int.* 2020;142:105851.
174. Ward A, Clark J, McLeod J, Woodul R, Moser H, Konrad C. The impact of heat exposure on reduced gestational age in pregnant women in North Carolina, 2011-2015. *Int J Biometeorol.* 2019;63(12):1611-20.
175. Wells JC, Cole TJ. Birth weight and environmental heat load: a between-population analysis. *Am J Phys Anthropol.* 2002;119(3):276-82.
176. Weng Y, Yang C, Chiu Y. Adverse neonatal outcomes in relation to ambient temperatures at birth: A nationwide survey in Taiwan. *Archives of environmental & occupational health.* 2018;73(1).
177. Wolf J, Armstrong B. The association of season and temperature with adverse pregnancy outcome in two German states, a time-series analysis. *PLoS One.* 2012;7(7):e40228.
178. Wu M, Song L, Zheng X, Zhang L, Liu B, Wang L, et al. Prenatal exposure of diurnal temperature range and preterm birth: Findings from a birth cohort study in China. *Sci Total Environ.* 2019;656:1102-7.
179. Xiong T, Chen P, Mu Y, Li X, Di B, Li J, et al. Association between ambient temperature and hypertensive disorders in pregnancy in China. *Nat Commun.* 2020;11(1):2925.
180. Xu W, Li D, Shao Z, You Y, Pan F, Lou H, et al. The prenatal weekly temperature exposure and neonatal congenital heart disease: a large population-based observational study in China. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int.* 2023;30(13):38282-91.
181. Yackerson N, Piura B, Sheiner E. The influence of meteorological factors on the emergence of preterm delivery and preterm premature rupture of membrane. *J Perinatol.* 2008;28(10):707-11.
182. Yackerson NS, Piura B, Friger M. The influence of weather state on the incidence of preeclampsia and placental abruption in semi-arid areas. *Clin Exp Obstet Gynecol.* 2007;34(1):27-30.
183. Yang D, Chen L, Yang Y, Shi J, Xu J, Li C, et al. Influence of ambient temperature and diurnal temperature variation on the premature rupture of membranes in East China: A distributed lag nonlinear time series analysis. *Environ Res.* 2021;202:111145.
184. Yang HY, Lee JKW, Chio CP. Extreme temperature increases the risk of stillbirth in the third trimester of pregnancy. *Scientific reports.* 2022;12(1):18474.

185. Yitshak-Sade M, Kloog I, Schwartz JD, Novack V, Erez O, Just AC. The effect of prenatal temperature and PM(2.5) exposure on birthweight: Weekly windows of exposure throughout the pregnancy. *Environ Int.* 2021;155:106588.
186. Yitshak-Sade M, Novack L, Landau D, Kloog I, Sarov B, Hershkovitz R, et al. Relationship of ambient air pollutants and hazardous household factors with birth weight among Bedouin-Arabs. *Chemosphere.* 2016;160:314-22.
187. Ylostalo P, Kauppila A, Sotaniemi E. Environmental temperature and the occurrence of toxemia of pregnancy in a subarctic area. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand.* 1972;51(2):165-8.
188. Yu X, Feric Z, Cordero JF, Meeker JD, Alshawabkeh A. Potential influence of temperature and precipitation on preterm birth rate in Puerto Rico. *Sci Rep.* 2018;8(1):16106.
189. Yüzen D, Graf I, Tallarek AC, Hollwitz B, Wiessner C, Schleussner E, et al. Increased late preterm birth risk and altered uterine blood flow upon exposure to heat stress. *EBioMedicine.* 2023;93:104651.
190. Zhang H, Wang Q, Benmarhnia T, Jalaludin B, Shen X, Yu Z, et al. Assessing the effects of non-optimal temperature on risk of gestational diabetes mellitus in a cohort of pregnant women in Guangzhou, China. *Environ Int.* 2021;152:106457.
191. Zhang JX, Yang M, Ji PH, Li QY, Chai J, Sun PP, et al. The Association between Outdoor Ambient Temperature and the Risk of Low Birth Weight: A Population-Based Cohort Study in Rural Henan, China. *Biomed Environ Sci.* 2021;34(11):905-9.
192. Zhang Y, Hajat S, Zhao L, Chen H, Cheng L, Ren M, et al. The burden of heatwave-related preterm births and associated human capital losses in China. *Nature communications.* 2022;13(1):7565.
193. Zhang Y, Sun F, Yuan K, Du Y, Wu L, Ge Y, et al. Ambient temperature and major structural anomalies: A retrospective study of over 2 million newborns. *Sci Total Environ.* 2023;882:163613.
194. Zhao Q, Li S, Coelho M, Saldiva PHN, Hu K, Abramson MJ, et al. Assessment of Intraseasonal Variation in Hospitalization Associated With Heat Exposure in Brazil. *JAMA network open.* 2019;2(2):e187901.
195. Zhao Q, Li S, Coelho M, Saldiva PHN, Hu K, Huxley RR, et al. The association between heatwaves and risk of hospitalization in Brazil: A nationwide time series study between 2000 and 2015. *PLoS medicine.* 2019;16(2):e1002753.
196. Zhao S, Xu J, Li W, Lu Y, Huang L, Xu H, et al. High-temperature exposure and risk of spontaneous abortion during early pregnancy: a case-control study in Nanjing, China. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int.* 2023;30(11):29807-13.
197. Zheng X, Zhang W, Lu C, Norbäck D, Deng Q. An epidemiological assessment of the effect of ambient temperature on the incidence of preterm births: Identifying windows of susceptibility during pregnancy. *J Therm Biol.* 2018;74:201-7.
198. Zhong Q, Lu C, Zhang W, Zheng X, Deng Q. Preterm birth and ambient temperature: Strong association during night-time and warm seasons. *J Therm Biol.* 2018;78:381-90.

7.4 Appendix D: Effect modification

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Antenatal bleeding	He (2018)	Age	Higher association for <35. No association for ≥35
Antenatal bleeding	He (2018)	Parity	No association for multiparous. Association with nulliparous
Antenatal bleeding	Rammah (2019)	Race	Only significant in Hispanic and black race. Not significant in white women
Antenatal bleeding	He (2018)	Socioeconomic status	Higher for low SES, no association for high SES
Cardiovascular event	Ha (2017)	Race	Highest in black women
Congenital anomalies	Zhang (2023)	Age	NS but positive direction of effect for all other ages in reference to 25-29 years old
Congenital anomalies	Zhang (2023)	Education	Educational attainment: NS but positive direction of effect for decreasing education levels.
Congenital anomalies	Xu(2023)	Education	Education status, higher risk in lower education levels (p=0.026)
Congenital anomalies	Zhang (2023)	Parity	Parity: NS but positive direction of effect for increasing party
Congenital anomalies	Van Zutphen (2012)	Race	Cleft lip with or without cleft palate in Hispanic OR=3.02 (95% CI=1.44, 6.33) versus non-Hispanic OR=0.83 (95%CI=0.67, 1.05)
Congenital anomalies	Zhang (2023)	Race	Yes, NS but in positive direction of effect for non-Hispanic Black, Hispanic, and Other.
Congenital anomalies	Gu (2007)	Sex	Correlation highest in males
Congenital anomalies	Xu(2023)	Sex	Sex: girls had higher risk, but NS (p=0.106)
Congenital anomalies	Zhang (2023)	Socioeconomic status	OR of 1.15 (95%CI=1.05, 1.25; p=0.01) for poverty rate of 10-14.9% vs <10%. Positive direction of effect but NS for increasing poverty rates beyond 15%
Gestational diabetes	Teyton (2022)	Urbanicity	Odds of GDM higher with increased evapotranspiration canopy RERI=0.008 (95%CI=0.001, 0.015). Odds reduced with increased water use efficiency RERI=-0.106 (95%CI=-0.177, -0.035). Increases odds of GDM with increased non-NDVI RERI=0.022 (95%CI=0.012, 0.032), land surface temperature RERI=0.001(95%CI=0.0004, 0.002), and global human settlement RERI=0.062 (95%CI=0.032, 0.091). Global human settlement indicator was associated with increased odds of GDM, RERI=0.065 (95%CI=0.022, 0.108). All other interactions between microclimate indicators and increased odds of GDM were not significant.

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Hypertension in pregnancy	Shashar (2020)	Race	Higher RR in Bedouin-Arab communities (more rural, temporary housing) as compared to Jewish communities in urban areas
Low birth weight	Andalon (2016)	Age	Impacts on birth weight appear higher in women ≤ 23 years
Low birth weight	Ngo (2016)	Age	Compared to overall population, point estimates higher in <18-year-olds.
Low birth weight	Basu (2018)	Age	Highest to lowest point estimates. Age: ≥ 40 years, 11-18 years, 19-24, 25-29, 30-39. Unsure if statistical significance in effect modification
Low birth weight	Davenport (2020)	Age	For every additional year of age, there is a 0.002% decrease in the likelihood of a low weight birth ($p=0.01$)
Low birth weight	Du (2021)	Age	Yes, but effect estimates for age not reported
Low birth weight	Zhang (2021)	Age	Mums <30 year old with higher odds of low birth weight OR=1.25 (95%CI=1.14-1.37)
Low birth weight	Leung (2023)	Age	Decrease in mean z-scores more pronounced in younger mothers, but not significant difference: <22 year -0.35 (95%CI=-0.54, -0.15) compared to -0.32 (95%CI= -0.51, -0.12) for 22-40 year olds and -0.28 (95%CI=-0.28 (-0.48, -0.08) for >40 year olds respectively.
Low birth weight	Tapia (2021)	Air pollution	Noted to have increased effect with higher PM2.5 (minimum P for interaction: BW- 0.002; Z-Score - 0.006, but Beta for BW is lower at -28.7(95% CI: -34.8, -22.6) and for Z-score at -0.06(95% CI: -0.07, -0.04).
Low birth weight	Rashid (2017)	BMI	Higher impacts in women with BMI <18.5kg/m ² significant at more susceptible time periods
Low birth weight	Basu (2018)	BMI	Data not provided on whether differences between subgroups are significant. Highest to lowest point estimates. BMI underweight, overweight, normal.
Low birth weight	Zhang (2021)	BMI	Women with BMI >24 and women with BMI 18.5-23.9 had higher odds of LBW ($p=0.005$)
Low birth weight	Andalon (2016)	Education	Impacts on birth weight higher with only primary education (unknown if significant)
Low birth weight	Ngo (2016)	Education	<12 years education larger estimates than tertiary education
Low birth weight	Basu (2018)	Education	Data not provided on whether differences between subgroups are significant. Highest to lowest point estimates. Education: <high school, high school, college.

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Low birth weight	Zhang (2021)	Education	Women with middle school or below had higher risk PTB
Low birth weight	Bakhtisityarava (2022) - Mexico	Education	Mothers with lower education (uncompleted secondary and lower) had decrease in birthweight associated with 5°C higher temperature in each month gestation in Mexico and Brazil. In Mexico, with cumulative exposure to average temperature in 95th percentile (28°C), there was an associated -15.44g (95% CI -25.40; -5.47) decrease in birthweight for women with lower education levels as compared to a reference temperature of 19C.
Low birth weight	Poeran (2016)	Geography	Inland areas higher temperature impacts than coastal
Low birth weight	Yitshak-Sade (2016)	Housing status	Pregnant women residing in a permanent locality had a higher decrease in birth weight -0.047g (95%CI=-0.081, -0.013g) compared to those that reside in temporary location -0.002g (-0.003, -0.0003g)
Low birth weight	Carlson (2022)	Housing status	Lower term birth weight for homeless individuals, during the second and third trimesters (2nd trimester mean=-420 (95% CI=-748, -92) 3rd trimester mean=-419 (95%CI=-757, -81) and an increased risk of SGA (2nd trimester odds= 47.7 (95%CI=4.9, 460.0); 3rd trimester odds=12.7 (95% CI=1.5, 109.8). For women that were not homeless, there was decrease in birthweight in second trimester (-175g (95%CI=-320, -29), and no increased risk of SGA
Low birth weight	Du (2021)	Medical comorbidities	Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy noted to have significantly different effects (p<0.05), but estimates not provided
Low birth weight	Du (2021)	Mode of delivery	Mode of delivery noted to have significantly different effects (p<0.05), but estimates not provided
Low birth weight	Davenport (2020)	Parity	For every additional birth, there is a 0.003% increase in the likelihood of LBW (p=0.001).
Low birth weight	Ngo (2016)	Race	Largest to smallest impact: Hispanics, Blacks, Whites
Low birth weight	MacVicar (2017)	Race	Higher effects in vulnerable indigenous population
Low birth weight	Basu (2018)	Race	Data not provided on whether differences between subgroups are significant. Highest to lowest point estimates for race: Black, White, Asian, Hispanic
Low birth weight	Yitshak -Sade (2021)	Race	Birthweight of infants from white women decreased by -10.1g (95%CI=-14.2; -5.9g) compared to -2.8g (95%CI=-9.3g; 3.5g) for non-white women

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Low birth weight	Cil (2022)	Race	Non-Hispanic Black (0.019 increase in LBW per 1000 births; p<0.10) and Hispanic (0.049 increase in LBW per 1000 births; p<0.10). Hispanic women had increased very low birthweight 0.017 per 1000 birth increase (p<0.01), and non-Hispanic Black women had 0.068 (p<0.05) increase in very low birthweight per 1000 births.
Low birth weight	Requia(2022) North region	Race	Black babies had higher effect estimate with wider CI (approx. 19% (95%CI=6, 34) vs approx. 4% (95%CI=2, 7) for white babies in North Region.
Low birth weight	Requia(2022) Northeast region	Race	In Northeast region, white babies alone showed increased risk 1.45% (95%CI=0.06, 2.86)
Low birth weight	Leung (2023)	Race	Higher cumulative reduction in birthweight z score in Asian women -0.43 (95%CI=-0.63, -0.22), followed by black women, -0.40 (95%CI=-0.60, -0.19) compared to Hispanic and white women
Low birth weight	Basu (2018)	Season	Data not provided on whether differences between subgroups are significant. Highest to lowest point estimates for season: warm, cold.
Low birth weight	Murray (2000)	Sex	Males had lower increase in birthweight with increased temperatures 1.02gm (SE=0.88; p=0.25) compared to females 3.5gm (SE=0.88; p<0.001)
Low birth weight	Basu (2018)	Sex	Data not provided on whether differences between subgroups are significant. Highest to lowest point estimates for sex: male, female
Low birth weight	Chen (2020)	Sex	Female infants had increased % of low birth weight compared to male infants
Low birth weight	Jakpor (2020)	Sex	Male infants had decrease in birthweight from week 1 to 21, cumulative change was -124.5g (95%CI=-228.0; -20.9)
Low birth weight	Yitshak -Sade (2021)	Sex	No significant difference between male and female infants. Birthweight for female infants decreased by 12.1g (95%CI=-16.9; -7.3g) compared to -5.7g (95%CI=-10.6g; -0.9g) for male infants
Low birth weight	Carlson (2022)	Sex	Male infants associated with decreased birthweight in trimester 2 -203g (95%CI=-389, -16). Females had no significant association with low birth weight
Low birth weight	Basu (2018)	Socioeconomic status	Data not provided on whether differences between subgroups are significant. Highest to lowest point estimates for WIC enrolment (marker of low SES): yes, no

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Low birth weight	Yitshak -Sade (2021)	Socioeconomic status	Birthweight of infants from women that received governmental support for prenatal care visits decreased by -17.1g (95%CI=-22.9; -11.3g) compared to -3.4g (95%CI=-7.7g; 0.9g) for women that did not receive governmental support
Low birth weight	Du (2021)	Socioeconomic status	NS effect modification for SES
Low birth weight	Requia (2022)	Socioeconomic status	Effect modification for SES but effect estimates not reported
Low birth weight	Conte Keivabu (2022)	Socioeconomic status	Increased LBW in low SES: 0.026 percent per additional heat day. Risks of LBW reduced in high SES groups. VLBW increase associated with low SES; 0.023/day in 2nd trimester
Maternal admissions	Kim (2021)	Race	Hispanic Black mothers associated with increased hospitalisations (r=-394, SE0.136; p<0.01) as compared to non-Hispanic whites (r=0.092, SE0.033; p<0.05). No significant associations between heat and hospitalisation in Hispanic (r=-0.157, SE0.314) and other mothers (r=0.214, SE0.176)
Mental health	Lin (2017)	Education	Associations higher in low education level
Mental health	Lin (2017)	Socioeconomic status	Associations higher in low SES
Neonatal admissions	Cil (2022)	Race	Non-Hispanic white babies had increased NICU admissions 0.159 (p<0.05) per 1000 births
Neonatal morbidity	Chen (2022)	Education	Women with low education had more than twice greater absolute regression value decrease in Apgar score with exposure to extreme temperatures as compared to high education group
Neonatal morbidity	Iijima (2021)	Sex	Significant in boys, not girls
Non-reassuring foetal status	Leung (2023)	Age	Reduction in foetal head circumference higher for women aged <22 -0.23 (95%CI=-0.33, -0.12) compared to women aged 22-40 -0.17 (95%CI=-0.27, -0.07) and aged >40 years -0.19 (95%CI=-0.30, -0.09). Similar findings for abdominal circumference; 22 years old -0.38 (95%CI=-0.60, -0.15), 22-40 years old -0.27 (95%CI=-0.49, -0.04) and 32-40 years old -0.18 (95%CI=-0.41, 0.04)
Non-reassuring foetal status	Leung (2023)	Season	Reduced foetal parameters with exposure in autumn compared to other seasons of conception. At weeks 24-31, decrease in biparietal diameter of -0.29 (95%CI=-0.49, -0.08) in autumn compared to -0.07 (95%CI=-0.32, 0.17) in

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
			summer, -0.14 (95%CI=-0.35, 0.07) in spring, and -0.14 (95%CI=-0.36, 0.09) in winter
Non-reassuring foetal status	Leung (2023)	Sex	Association higher in females compared to males in biparietal diameter, head circumference, and abdominal circumference. For weeks 24-31, biparietal diameter reduced by -0.31 (95%CI=-0.50, -0.12) in females, compared to -0.06 (95%CI=-0.25, 0.13) in males
Perinatal mortality	Schumann (2019)	Race	Significant effect in non-Sami population, no effect in Sami population
Perinatal mortality	Basagana (2011)	Sex	Females more affected than males
Prelabour rupture of membranes	Song (2019)	Age	Not significant for women ≥ 35 , but significant for women < 35
Prelabour rupture of membranes	Gat (2021)	Race	Yes. No effect in Jewish, but effects in Bedouin-Arabs
Preterm birth	Basu (2010)	Age	Highest risk in maternal age < 20 years 14.0% (95%CI=6.6 to 22.0) compared to < 25 11.0% (95%CI=6.6 to 15.5), 25-34 9.4% (95%CI=4.8 to 14.2), > 35 3.6% (95%CI=-2.4 to 10.0). < 20 years of age vs > 35 years $p=0.04$
Preterm birth	Wang (2013)	Age	Significant in women > 34 years, NS in other age groups
Preterm birth	Schifano (2013)	Age	PTB risk higher in women < 20 years
Preterm birth	Liang (2016)	Age	NS in women 15-19 years RR=1.04 (95%CI=0.56 to 1.94). Significant in women 20-34 years RR=0.70 (95%CI=0.60 to 0.82) and women > 35 RR=0.66 (95%CI=0.45 to 0.98)
Preterm birth	Cox (2016)	Age	Impacts highest in women ≥ 35 years
Preterm birth	Ngo (2016)	Age	Point estimates higher in < 18 year olds
Preterm birth	Basu (2017)	Age	NS. Highest effect for maternal age 18-19 years 30.99% (95%CI=-1.00 ,75.06%), compared to 20-24 years 12.74% (95%CI=-8.61 to 39.09%), 25-35 years 11.62% (95%CI=2.02 to 22.14) ≥ 35 years 11.62% (95%CI=-2.96 to 28.40%).
Preterm birth	Zhong (2018)	Age	OR in ≥ 30 year olds higher than < 30 years
Preterm birth	Wu (2019)	Age	Highest to lowest risk: Age ≥ 28 , < 28 .
Preterm birth	Son (2019)	Age	Statistically significant HR for whole pregnancy exposure higher in women < 25 . Also elevated in women > 29

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Preterm birth	Asta (2019)	Age	Interaction (p<0.05) noted in Rome only: higher RR in women <20 years
Preterm birth	Sun (2019)	Age	Statistically significant higher effect in women <25 years RR=1.04 (95%CI=1.02 to 1.06) as compared to 25-34 years RR=1.02 (95%CI=1.01 to 1.03), ≥35 years RR=0.99 (95%CI=0.97 to 1.02)
Preterm birth	Gronlund (2020)	Age	Higher PTB risk in mothers 16-19 years old, and >30 years old
Preterm birth	Li (2021)	Age	Age interaction test NS, but effect sizes highest in women ≥36 years
Preterm birth	Cheng (2021)	Age	Significance found for 1st percentile for both < 35 years (lag 0, lag 0_1 RR 1.50 [95% CI=1.02,2.21]) and ≥35 years (lag 0, lag0_1 , lag 0_2, lag 0_3, lag 0_4 RR 2.55 [95% CI: 1.01-6.40]).
Preterm birth	Nyadanu (2022)	Age	Women less than 19 years at higher risk of PTB RR=1.46 (95%CI=1.44, 1.47)
Preterm birth	Barreca (2020)	Air conditioning coverage	Interaction with residential air conditioning coverage in county. Full air conditioning coverage mitigates three quarters of the impact of hot days
Preterm birth	Basu (2017)	Alcohol Consumption	NS. Mother that consumed alcohol at higher risk 34.98% (95%CI=-29.54 to 161.16%) as compared to those that did not drink 11.62% (95%CI=4.08 to 19.72)
Preterm birth	Wu (2019)	BMI	Highest to lowest risk: BMI >20, BMI<20.
Preterm birth	Wang (2020)	BMI	Overweight compared to normal weight, HR=1.84 (95%CI=1.66, 2.04) in overweight group compared to HR=1.57 (95%CI=1.49, 1.66) in normal weight group
Preterm birth	Sun (2019)	Climate Zone	Highest in hot-dry/mixed-dry climate zone RR=1.06
Preterm birth	Wang (2020)	Climate Zone	HR=2.48 (95%CI=2.37, 2.59) pregnant women living in temperate zones, HR=1.39 (95%CI=1.33, 1.46) pregnant women living in subtropical zones; HR=1.62 (95%CI=1.36, 1.93) pregnant women living in tropical zones. Highest risk in temperate zones.
Preterm birth	Li (2018b)	Study period	Decreased HR from 1994 HR=1.53 (95%CI=1.44 to 1.63) to 2013 1.19 (95%CI=1.13 to 1.25)
Preterm birth	Porter (1999)	Education	<12 years education 0.0 weeks. >12 years education 0.4 weeks
Preterm birth	Basu (2010)	Education	Higher PTB risk for high school only education 9.7% (95%CI=6.2 ,13.2) compared to college 7.0% (95%CI=2.7, 11.6).
Preterm birth	Schifano (2013)	Education	Lower PTB risk in women with tertiary education

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Preterm birth	Ngo (2016)	Education	Largest to smallest impact: <12 years education higher impact compared to Bachelor or higher education
Preterm birth	Son (2019)	Education	NS differences in sub-groups: ≤12 years education 1.046 vs >12 1.026
Preterm birth	Sun (2019)	Education	<9 years education RR=1.030 (95%CI=1.016, 1.044), ≥9 years RR=1.009 (95%CI=0.994, 1.025)
Preterm birth	Li (2021)	Education	Lower education significantly modified hazard ratio
Preterm birth	Ward (2019)	Geography	Highest impacts in mountain regions, then coastal plains, then Piedmont. Socioeconomic status in coastal plains poorest, mountain region, then Piedmont
Preterm birth	Schifano (2013)	Medical comorbidities	Increase in percent PTB rise higher in women hospitalised for chronic disease in 2 years preceding delivery (7.32%)
Preterm birth	Basu (2017)	Medical comorbidities	Sub-group comparisons NS. Hypertension 37.71% (95%CI=5.12, 80.39%), diabetes 23.36% (95%CI=1.00, 52.19%), preeclampsia 18.53% (95%CI=-3.92, 47.70%), depression 17.35% (95%CI=-5.83, 44.77%) without depression 11.62% (95%CI=3.04, 20.92%)
Preterm birth	Asta (2019)	Medical comorbidities	Higher RR in women with chronic conditions in 2 years before childbirth
Preterm birth	Jegasothy (2021)	Medical comorbidities	Pre-existing medical conditions NS difference RR=1.43 (95%CI=0.95, 2.14)
Preterm birth	Li (2021)	Medical comorbidities	Interaction test NS, but effect size greatest in women with chronic conditions
Preterm birth	Wang (2013)	Marital status	Significant in married or stable cohabiting relationships, NS for other women
Preterm birth	Nyadanu (2022)	Marital status	Unmarried women at higher risk of PTB RR=1.23 (95%CI 1.21, 1.24)
Preterm birth	Wang (2020)	Occupation	Increased risk in farmers HR=1.90 (95%CI=1.80, 1.99) compared to workers at HR=1.05 (95%CI=1.00, 1.10)
Preterm birth	Wang (2013)	Parity	Primiparous women (p=0.09)
Preterm birth	Jegasothy (2021)	Parity	Parity 2nd-3rd max RR=1.2 (95%CI=1.3, 1.1) mean RR=1.25 (95%CI=1.3,1.15) min RR=1.2 (95%CI=1.3,1.1)
Preterm birth	Wang (2023)	Parity	Firstborn at higher risk OR=4.57 (95%CI=3.37, 6.19) than second born OR=2.12 (95%CI=1.55, 2.87)

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Preterm birth	Gronlund (2020)	Prenatal Care	RERI for low prenatal care were statistically significantly greater than 0, indicating a stronger association between PTB and temperature
Preterm birth	Porter (1999)	Race	Hispanic 0.0 weeks, White 0.2 weeks, Black 0.4 weeks
Preterm birth	Basu (2010)	Race	Race subgroups NS. Black 14.9% (95%CI=5.0, 25.8), Asian 10.2% (95%CI=2.0, 19.1), Hispanic 8.1% (95%CI=4.6, 11.7), White 6.6% (95%CI=0.9, 12.7)
Preterm birth	Wang (2013)	Race	Significant in indigenous women, NS with non-indigenous
Preterm birth	Carmichael (2014)	Race	Black women 0.02% increase in PTB at 20-31 weeks and 0.114% for 32-36 weeks PTB (p<0.001). Whites: 0.01% for 20-31 weeks PTB (p<0.001). 0.06% for 32-36 weeks PTB (p<0.001)
Preterm birth	Ngo (2016)	Race	Compared to overall population, largest to smallest impact: Hispanics, Blacks, Whites
Preterm birth	Mathew (2017)	Race	Effects sizes higher in non-indigenous than indigenous population
Preterm birth	Basu (2017)	Race	Sub-group comparisons NS. Black 24.60% (95%CI=1.00, 55.27%), Hispanic 17.35% (95%CI=3.04 to 34.98%), Asian 7.25% (95%CI=-11.31, 30.99%), White 7.25% (95%CI=-6.77, 22.14%)
Preterm birth	Sun (2019)	Race	White RR=1.03 (95%CI=1.01 to 1.04) Non-white RR=1.02 (95%CI=0.99 to 1.04)
Preterm birth	Barreca (2020)	Race	Greater impact on black mothers versus white mothers. Effect on day 0 is similar, but cumulative is larger on day 1. Rebound in births persist until 30 days for black mothers, as opposed to 15 days for white mothers, implying the loss in gestational length is greater for black mothers
Preterm birth	Gronlund (2020)	Race	RERIs for black mothers lower than for non-black mothers, but not statistically significant
Preterm birth	Cil (2022)	Race	Non-Hispanic Black and Hispanic births most vulnerable. Hispanic women increased extremely preterm birth, 0.013 per 1000 (p<0.050). Non-Hispanic Black women 0.094 per 1000 (p<0.01) increase in very preterm birth, 0.072 (p<0.01) increase in extremely preterm birth per 1000 deliveries. Non-Hispanic White had increased extremely preterm 0.014 (p<0.05) per 1000 deliveries
Preterm birth	Nyadanu (2022)	Race	Non-Caucasian women at higher risk of PTB RR=1.07 (95%CI=1.06; 1.08) compared to Caucasian women

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Preterm birth	Smith (2020)	Race and Education	Higher PTB risk in Black women with college degrees exposed to heat waves RR=2.97 (95%CI=1.45, 6.07) than White women with college degrees in a heat wave
Preterm birth	Wu (2019)	Season	Highest to lowest risk for season: cold, warm. Tests for interaction NS
Preterm birth	Avalos (2017)	Geography	Warm season, coastal region 12.75% (95%CI=3.05%, 23.37%) vs inland regions 7.25% (95%CI=-7.69%, 25.86%). All tests for interaction between sub-groups in warm season NS. Cold season: Coastal region 12.8% (95%CI=3.1%, 23.4%) vs inland region -4.9% (95%CI=-20.5%, 12.75%), test for interaction p=0.08
Preterm birth	Avalos (2017)	Sex	Warm season: Females 13.9% (95%CI=4.1%, 25.9%), males 10.5% (95%CI=1.01%, 20.9%). All tests for interaction between sub-groups in warm season NS. Cold season: Females 13.88% (95%CI=3.05%, 25.9%), males 1.01% (95%CI=-7.7%, 10.5%). Interaction p=0.01
Preterm birth	Basu (2010)	Sex	Female 10.1% (95%CI=5.9, 14.4), male 7.8% (95%CI=4.2, 11.6)
Preterm birth	Wang (2013)	Sex	Significant male gender, NS females
Preterm birth	Liang (2016)	Sex	Female RR=0.64 (95%CI=0.52 to 0.78). Males RR=0.74 (95%CI=0.62 to 0.88)
Preterm birth	Cox (2016)	Sex	Impacts of heat on females higher than males
Preterm birth	Zhong (2018)	Sex	OR in males > females
Preterm birth	Zheng (2018)	Sex	Higher for females compared to males. Males with exposure in conception month OR=1.11 (95%CI=1.02, 1.20), birth month OR=0.95 (95%CI=0.84, 1.07), and entire pregnancy OR=2.22 (95%CI=1.61, 3.06). Females, high temperature in conception month OR=1.31 (95%CI=1.12, 1.52), birth month OR=1.05 (95%CI=0.93, 1.19) and entire pregnancy OR=2.76 (95%CI=1.88, 4.04)
Preterm birth	Wu (2019)	Sex	Highest to lowest risk: Sex: female, male. Tests for interaction NS
Preterm birth	Son (2019)	Sex	NS diffs in sub-groups: female 1.04 vs male 1.03
Preterm birth	Sun (2019)	Sex	Male RR=1.03 (95%CI=1.02, 1.05), female 1.01 (95%CI=0.10 to 1.03)
Preterm birth	Gong (2021)	Sex	Higher odds of PTB in males OR=1.05 (95%CI 1.00; 1.09)
Preterm birth	Nyadanu (2022)	Sex	Male infants at higher risk than female infants RR1.15 (95%CI=1.14, 1.17)

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Preterm birth	Basu (2017)	Smoking Status	Sub-group comparisons NS. Mothers who smoked during pregnancy 30.99% (95%CI=0, 71.6%) did not smoke 10.51% (95%CI=2.02, 18.53%).
Preterm birth	Gronlund (2020)	Smoking Status	RERI for tobacco smoking were statistically significantly greater than 0, indicating a stronger association for PTB risk and temperature
Preterm birth	Jegasothy (2021)	Smoking Status	Significant for women who smoked. Tmin RR=1.28 (95%CI=1.10, 1.49), Tmean RR=1.27 (95%CI=1.09, 1.47) and Tmax RR=1.19 (95%CI=1.04, 1.36)
Preterm birth	Nyadanu (2022)	Smoking Status	Women that smoke were at higher risk of PTB RR=1.19 (95%CI=1.17; 1.21) compared to non-smokers
Preterm birth	Son (2019)	Socioeconomic status	NS diffs in sub-groups: lower SES 1.05 vs high SES 1.02
Preterm birth	Jegasothy (2021)	Socioeconomic status	Most disadvantage quintile at Tmax OR=1.3 (95%CI=1.1, 1.4) Tmean OR=1.29 (95%CI=1.05, 1.4)
Preterm birth	Nyadanu (2022)	Socioeconomic status	Low SES lower risk of PTB RR=0.89 (95%CI=0.85; 0.94) compared to high SES
Preterm birth	Conte Keivabu (2022)	Socioeconomic status	Low SES had reduced risk of PTB in 3rd trimester
Preterm birth	Son (2019)	Socioeconomic status and education	Women with both low education and low SES HR=1.10 (95%CI=1.03, 1.17), highest of all sub-groups examined
Preterm birth	Jegasothy (2021)	Urbanicity	Urban areas have significant impacts Tmax OR=1.2 (95%CI=1.25, 1.15) Tmean OR=1.25 (95%CI=1.3, 1.2), Tmin OR=1.2(95%CI=1.25,1.15) as compared to rural with no significant impact
Preterm birth	Porter (1999)	Socioeconomic status	Lowest income 0.4 weeks, highest income 0.1 weeks.
Small for gestational age	Li (2023)	Air pollution	Evidence of effect modification for PM2.5 in Eastern province. Higher odds of SGA with exposure to above median PM2.5 RR=1.31 (95%CI=1.23, 1.39) compared to below median PM2.5 OR=1.10 (95%CI=1.04, 1.15)
Small for gestational age	Sun (2019)	Climate Zone	Largest impacts in marine and cold/very cold climate zones
Small for gestational age	Carlson (2022)	Housing status	For homeless individuals, heat exposure during the second and third trimesters associated with an increased risk of SGA OR= 47.7 (95% CI=4.9, 460.0) for second trimester, OR=12.7 (95%CI=1.5, 109.8) for third trimester. For women that were not homeless, there was no increased risk of SGA
Small for gestational age	Carlson (2022)	Sex	Male infants associated with increased risk of SGA in trimester one OR=4.54 (95%CI=1.14, 18.15) and trimester two OR=4.36 (95%CI=1.23, 15.44). Females had no significant association with SGA

Outcome theme	Author (year)	Subgroup	Summary and effect estimate
Spontaneous abortion	Sun (2020)	Urbanicity	Modifying effect of NDVI. Weaker effects of temperature on risk of miscarriage in participants exposed to Q3 greenness OR 0.78 (95%CI=0.57, 1.05) compared to patients exposed to Q1 and Q2 greenness OR=1.39 (95%CI=0.95, 2.02) and OR=1.59 (95%CI=1.12, 2.26). However, for Q4 greenness, higher OR as compared to Q3 OR=1.26 (95%CI=0.927, 1.712)
Stillbirths	Davenport (2020)	Age	For each additional year of age, there is a 0.007% increase in the likelihood of still birth (p<0.01)
Stillbirths	Nyadanu(2023)	Air pollution	PM2.5, results NS but in positive direction of effect
Stillbirths	McElroy (2022)	Education	Stillbirth association only significant for low, not high education
Stillbirths	Nyadanu(2023)	Socioeconomic status	Lower GDP OR=1.63 (95%CI=1.16,2.28) increased risk relative to higher GDP
Stillbirths	Nyadanu(2023)	Urbanicity	Population density in positive direction of effect but NS.
Stillbirths	Savitz (2021)	Race	Non-Hispanic Black OR=1.6 (95%CI=1.0, 2.4), other races NS. Hispanic significant in some analyses. Whites NS.
Stillbirths	Richards (2022)	Race	White women had increased odds of stillbirth OR=1.18 (95%CI=1.06; 1.30). Black, Hispanic and other had no association
Stillbirths	Nyadanu(2023)	Season	Season in positive direction of effect but NS
Stillbirths	Davenport (2020)	Socioeconomic status	Floor type as proxy for socioeconomic status is significant. Natural compared to finished floor results in a 0.025% increase in probability of stillbirth (p<0.01)
Stillbirths	Savitz (2021)	Socioeconomic status	Q4 lowest SES, p<0.05. Q1-3 SES only significant in few analyses.
Stillbirths	Davenport (2020)	Urbanicity	Urban residence associated with a 0.038% decrease in likelihood of a stillbirth (p<0.01)
Stillbirths	McElroy (2022)	Urbanicity	Stillbirth association only significant for rural, not urban